

**Stakeholders' Perspective Of The Higher Education Service
Quality And Its Contribution Towards The Personal
Development Of Students In Pakistan**

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Doctor of Business Administration

By

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Under the Supervision of

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis is my original work and is done for the research degree at the University of West of Scotland. I confirm that where I have consulted the published work of others or quoted the work from others, the source is always clearly attributed.

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Dedication

I want to dedicate this study to my late parents.

Muhammad Yasin Qazi and Ghulam Kubra

Abstract

HESQ is an integral part of the service industry of any country. It plays a critical role in the country's economic development by providing employment opportunities and human resources to nearly all the other sectors. Pakistan is a developing country with over two hundred government and private HEIs. The HE services environment in the country is becoming very competitive and focused on quality assurance.

The stakeholders' perspective has been the focus of research on the HESQ. Several research studies have been conducted from students' perspectives, and there is a gap in the perspective of the other stakeholder, particularly in Pakistan. All of the HE stakeholders uniquely perceive HESQ. The students as the direct receivers, academic and non-academic staff as the giver and the industry as the employer and indirect receiver of the HE services. This study is focused on the three key stakeholders' perspectives of HESQ and its contribution towards the personal development of HE students.

This study proposes a model to analyse the impact of service quality aspects on the student experience and personal development. The model has been used as a base to explore the difference in the perspective of key stakeholders. The data collection instruments were devised based on the constructs presented in the model. The data was collected using a mixed method: the quantitative data was collected from the students of HEIs using a self-administered online questionnaire, while the qualitative data was collected from the teaching and non-teaching staff and the industry professionals using semi-structured interviews. The interviews were conducted online due to the restrictions of the pandemic.

The findings from the study revealed the positive influence of the service quality aspects on the student experience, also reflecting the positive influence of student satisfaction from the HEE on the personal development of the students. The study aimed to explore the differences in the key stakeholder's perceptions; the differences are presented alongside some similarities. The study's objective was to present viable suggestions for the improvement of HESQ in the institutes of Pakistan.

Keywords: Service Quality, Higher Education, Stakeholders, Higher Education Institutes, Perception, Satisfaction, Student Experience, Personal development.

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Abbreviations

Higher Education	HE
Higher Education Institute	HEI
Higher Education Experience	HEE
Higher Education Commission	HEC
Higher Education Service Quality	HESQ
Higher Education Commission Pakistan	HECP
National Business Education Accreditation Council	NBEAC
National Computing Education Accreditation Council	NCEAC
National Accreditation Council for Teachers Education	NACTE

Chapter 1: Research Introduction

1.1. Introduction

Human resources are the most critical factor in any country's development (Maher, 2018). Human resources are described as the learning, skill set, experiences, education, and capabilities ascribed to individuals in the nation that impacts the achievement of the country's objectives; this starts with citizens' intellectual wealth (Saleem and Bontis, 2013). Following the economic collapse in Asia in 1997, several regional governments have been actively trying to get their young people to stay in their home countries and complete their education there. Around that time, several of the world's developing economies began adopting bold measures to expand access to high-quality education (Gupta and Kaushik, 2018). This has caused a fast change, evident during the last twenty years. Gradually but surely, an emphasis on quality emerged as the most effective strategy for controlling competition (Sohail and Shanmugham, 2003). This has pushed higher education institutes (HEIs) to the forefront of knowledge production and innovation while also serving as a key factor in boosting economic competitiveness (Sing and Prasad, 2016).

HEIs play a significant role in supplying human resources (Ahmed, 2020; Raza et al., 2020). The HE segment has been rapidly expanding (Shauchenka, 2015), and it is now classed as a full-fledged service business worldwide (Latif et al., 2017). HEIs are increasingly recognised as service industry players (Galeeva, 2016). Higher education service quality (HESQ) has been increasingly acknowledged and given more attention by policymakers of HEIs over the past decades, in addition to the commercial sectors, as it contributes significantly to the development of a necessarily qualified workforce for any nation (Ramzi et al., 2022).

In recent years, the service sector has fostered economic growth (Dam and Dam, 2021). Organisations, irrespective of the segment in which they conduct operations, place a strong emphasis on the quality of service provided to their clients. This is because the quality of these services performs an essential part in the creation of competitive advantage, as well as in the recruitment of new clients and the retention of existing clients (Ugboma et al., 2007, Latif et al., 2021). The current higher education (HE) environment is very dynamic and competitive (Dehghan et al., 2014). The HEIs operating in this dynamic and competitive environment need to optimise their efforts for the continuous improvement of their service (Teeroovengadam et al., 2016). The leading factors of the scenario are the internationalisation of HE (Sultan and

Wong, 2010), the rising number of private-sector HEIs (Halai, 2013) and the reduced number of funds for government HEIs (Quinn et al., 2009).

Due to globalisation, HE's quest for quality assurance is climbing to the top of many countries' policy agendas (Tan, 2017). In addition to highlighting the importance of students' interest in learning, this also emphasises the student learning and level of personal development due to their HE experiences (Mok, 2018; Deem, 2019; Altbach et al., 2019). The requirement for regulation aids in developing and institutionalising quality assurance in HEIs and focusing on accountability and performativity in HEI administration (Shore and Wright, 2016). There are expectations from educational institutions to evolve into learning communities to provide stakeholders holistic skills to help them adjust to a more global noesis society (Marginson and Van der Wende, 2018).

Change and reconstruction are ongoing in HE (Porter, 2019). Changes in education are the result of mutually reinforcing factors that finally yield something new (Vasudevan, 2021). The days are long gone when HEIs could reliably count on a steady demand for their services. HEIs that were once solely available to the most affluent members of society now have to compete with one another to enrol students and increase their market share (Teeroovengadum et al., 2019). HEIs must promote themselves to draw in more students to survive. HEIs must thus carefully research the characteristics that draw in and keep students (Vo, 2021). In recent years, HEIs have been working to integrate information technologies that make it possible for them to manage their resources and business in a manner that is more aligned with the demands of the market. Students are able to actively connect with the entire scope of their course, including their instructors, learning materials, evaluations and other classmates, which ultimately leads to an increased level of performance and achievement for all involved parties (Martins et al., 2019).

Due to growing organisational needs and the expanding number of professionals with degrees of bachelor's, master's and doctorate, including specialised certificates, these credentials have become crucial differentiators for filling job openings (Sultan and Wong, 2011; Choudhury, 2015). HEIs have been focusing on the quality of service to boost their competitiveness and appeal to new graduate students' applications in response to the increased demand for graduate degrees and institute offerings as a result of the job market climate (Aleu et al., 2021). Service quality has received much recognition from academia and industry (Guo, 2018). Focusing on service quality is crucial for businesses running in the service industries (Lewis and Mitchell,

1990). It is considered a strategic weapon for improving performance and attaining proficiency (Zethaml et al., 1993). The education industry provides services to students at various stages of their learning and personal development. Quality implies various things to various individuals in different situations (Lovell and Wirtz, 2011), and the perception of service quality is affected by various cultural variances (Aleu et al., 2021).

Institutions that wish to thrive in a cutthroat climate must look for adaptable and efficient ways to draw in students and build long-term ties with them (Ganic et al., 2018). The majority of educational institutions are forced to contend in an open market that is defined by a broad range of options. Nevertheless, only a select few prominent institutes still have the ability to accept students of their choosing (Latif et al., 2017). The globalisation of HE, the emergence of private HEIs and a decline in state financing for public institutes are some of the reasons that have contributed to the development of such a competitive environment (Wong and Sultan, 2021). Students' overall rating of service as part of their higher education experience (HEE) determines service quality (Sultan and Wong, 2019). It covers a wide range of educational service aspects, such as teaching and learning, faculty member/student relations, physical environment, administrative connections, and more (Guo, 2018).

For HEIs, it is becoming gradually significant and prevalent to identify any emerging issues and improve their service performance, which they refer to as service quality, for the concept's continuous adaptation aims to increase their tuition fee-based revenues (Hwang and Choi, 2019). This approach aids the institutions in attracting and retention of valuable students (Sharabi, 2013). As the amount and types of programmes offered by HEIs are comparable internationally and locally, the universities must focus on marketing their unique element and developing their reputation. HEIs, like other businesses, require a considerable infrastructure to deliver great service (Hasbullah et al., 2018). Thus, efforts by HEIs to improve their reputation in the HE sector can help the institute compete effectively (Khalid et al., 2019).

HE is increasingly being marketed globally, which has increased rivalry among institutes for students (Latif et al., 2019). This has led to the establishment of thousands of new public and private HEIs in past decades, and each year many students go to other countries to pursue their field of study (Acer and Guclu, 2017; Jupiter et al., 2017; Abbas, 2020). As students start to identify as customers, universities are being run more like companies (Bunce et al., 2017), and metrics like customer satisfaction are becoming crucial to determining how successful a university is. Students are considered as the primary customers of the HEIs since they pay

tuition fees in exchange for the service; therefore, it is important to guarantee their satisfaction with the service (Guilbault, 2018). Some scholars like Tholen et al. (2016) have argued against perceiving students as customers and HEIs as business-line enterprises. If students are considered consumers, then institutions ought to provide them with what they want, which may clash with the provision of excellent education (Liu, 2016; Abbas, 2020). Although King and Bunce (2020), along with others, argue that comparing students to customers and universities to service providers is uncomfortable for academics and may even be detrimental to academic achievement, effective universities, like successful businesses, must prioritise customer satisfaction (Latif et al., 2021).

The adoption of marketing theories, concepts, and policies that have been demonstrated to be effective in the corporate sector has sparked pedagogical, moral, educational, and political concerns about the massive paradigm shift toward a consumer-focused HE market (Naidoo et al., 2011; Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka, 2016; Gibbs, 2019). This approach has led chiefly to concerns about HE being viewed as a business, whereas it is viewed as a commodity in the global phenomena of marketisation (Yang, 2017; Gibbs, 2019). HE is considered a service provided by HEIs; hence they are naturally service-oriented and function as commercial organisations focused on managing the service provider according to the market (Yeo, 2019). HEIs are becoming more market-oriented and market-driven. As a result, they have to be more concerned with the customers' perception of the HESQ and satisfaction, as customers are the ones who define quality in the service sector (Li, 2018). HEIs should be considerate of customer satisfaction as well because one of the factors that determine an organisation's level of success is the degree to which its clients are pleased with the service quality (Campos et al., 2017; Abbas, 2020).

In contrast to other goods and services, education and knowledge cannot be measured in monetary terms alone (Ramirez-Hurtado, 2021). HEIs have the weighty duty of educating their students for success in all aspects of life, not only in the workplace (Sundar, 2016). Managing and measuring the quality of service delivered by HEIs is crucial to the long-term health of economies and the fulfilment of national goals. For this reason, HEIs are under increasing pressure to improve their efficiency, effectiveness and focus on the demands of their customers (Khalid et al., 2019). To provide high-quality service, it is vital to incorporate students' perspectives, ideas and wants. If students' ideas and opinions are neglected, all services given will fall short of meeting students' needs and desires (Vasudevan, 2021).

Managing quality at HEIs is a difficult task. Academic and service quality are the two most significant areas to be focused on. Academic quality focuses on the learning result or acquiring knowledge and skills in particular subject areas (Saleem et al., 2017). In contrast quality of service provided tends to focus on institutional services. Both tangible and intangible qualities are included in the service components. The inappropriate understanding of the service provision concept in HEIs has made them more focused on the physical and measurable aspects such as the building, equipment, and other tangible assets (Saleem et al., 2017). As a result, the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan (HECP) supports HEIs based on these impressions and assesses them accordingly. In addition to their infrastructure, Pakistani HEIs must promote the brains they employ and invest more money in human resources.

According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), quality of service is measured by comparing the customer's expectation of the service they anticipate before deliverance and the perception of the service they received. At the time, this was the most accurate description available, and other scholars agreed that it was the most suitable. Based on his notion of service quality difference or gap, Parasuraman et al. (1985), created the first method for evaluating service quality. Through a succession of studies, Parasuraman et al. (1985,1986, 1988, 1990, 1991, 1993, 1994), Zeithaml et al. (1990, 1991), and Zeithaml et al. (1992, 1993) presented the SERVQUAL model to quantify service quality. The SERVQUAL model is a commonly widely used tool for measuring service quality in different service environments.

The South Asian nation of Pakistan is still in the process of evolving. The field of HE in Pakistan is now going through a great deal of change because of the interplay of political, social and financial variables (Raza et al., 2020). The industry requires significant changes for it to become a contributor to the national economy, which will, in turn, promote democracy and the peace process. As a direct result of this, it will begin to influence the economy's development, the political process and the decrease of unemployment. According to Jamjoom (2009), graduates who have received quality education are equipped with the requisite skills that increase their employability. Research also indicates that HEIs all around the globe have concerns about the quality of HE (Angell et al., 2008). In addition, they are interested in evaluating HESQ, which is a social, professional and economic requirement. Nevertheless, the perceived degree of customer satisfaction should be raised by assuring HESQ by HEIs (Jelena, 2010; Raza et al., 2020).

Between 2000 and 2015, the number of educational establishments in Pakistan rose. According to the HECP, 45 universities and degree-granting institutions in 2000 climbed to 173 in 2015. This number of recognised universities in Pakistan rose further to 246 in 2022, including 147 public sector institutes and 99 private sector institutes (HECP, 2022). Many of the 246 universities have multiple campuses in different cities in Pakistan. Since education is seen as a valuable resource in every economy, and economic success and educational attainment are inextricably linked in every country (Husain et al., 2009), the increasing number of HEIs has raised the requirement to develop an understanding of the importance of service quality for improvement and the provision of better service to the current as well as future students so they can play their role efficiently and effectively in the economic growth of Pakistan.

Many stakeholders are involved in HE, including the government, the students' employers, teachers and students themselves. These parties are frequently viewed as the institutions' consumers (Raaper, 2019). In terms of offering education, high-impact research and outreach that will eventually help their business, industry and society at large, they want high-quality educational service from HEIs (Camilleri, 2021). A person's degree of education will typically indicate their level of work. When services are ineffective, it indirectly influences both students and institutions (Vasudevan, 2021).

HE quality should reflect stakeholders' perspectives and be determined by them (Marshall, 2018). Because of their unique demands, each stakeholder group in HE has its own sense of service quality. Undoubtedly, students are the most critical stakeholders in HEIs since they are the service consumers (Guo, 2018). Their presence is essential to the survival of HEIs. The staff of HEIs which is directly involved with the delivery of service and the industry with is the indirect receiver of the service as employers of the graduates are also considered as critical stakeholders of HE service. According to Freeman (1984), organisations must consider the differences in evaluations and expectations of various stakeholder groups that can impact the organisation's outcomes.

Due to the increasing number of HEIs in Pakistan, the competition amongst HEI increased along with the pressure of improving the perception of service quality for key stakeholders. HEIs can be considered organisations with public purposes, getting closer to where they are seen as another societal participant. HEIs include students, various individuals, academic staff, operational staff and managers, and other society representatives in their formal governance

structure. However, stakeholders and their contributions and perception of HESQ vary dependent on the HEI's governance and regulations (Ferrero-Ferrero et al., 2018).

1.2. Research Context

In the mid-1980s, discourse on the construct of HESQ first emerged in services marketing literature (Abdullah and Mohammad, 2016), quality assurance literature (Ismail and Yunan, 2016), and literature on HE administration (Ho and Wearn, 1996; Quinn et al., 2009; Ismail and Yunan, 2016). Since Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) conceptualised the service quality model (SERVQUAL), the existing material on the quality of service has been nourished with the discourse upon many aspects and measurements of quality of service (O'Neill and Palmar, 2014; Sultan and Wong, 2019). Since the mid-1980s, various academics have used Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988), as a framework to learn about the quality of service in HE. However, it is still clear that the majority of study on this topic still focuses on consumer service, primarily on concerns of service deliverance, whereas research studies about professional services in connection to service quality, particularly in HE, remains scarce (Schneider and White, 2014; Sultan and Wong, 2019). According to the current research on the service quality in HE, it is sufficient as a competing advantage for HEIs for attracting and retaining students for as long as possible (Ismail and Yunan, 2016; Guo, 2018).

Several scholars advocate for models that quantify stakeholders' satisfaction as a metric for service quality, either locally or nationally (Zhang et al., 2016). The models of customer satisfaction have successfully produced content on students' satisfaction that HEIs required to improve the services they provide to students (Serenko, 2011). Even though various research on service quality has improved the services marketing domain (Sultan and Wong, 2019) although, from a strictly marketing linear standpoint, the conceptualisation of quality of service in HE is debatable (Tan, 2017). While HEIs are continuously under pressure to show the quality of their offered service and to supply substantial service to attract and accommodate students (Jones and Lee, 2011; Volet and Jones, 2012), they are specifically focused on offering great educational experience to students (Ismail and Yunan, 2016). To sustain market competitiveness, the quantity, context of use, and purpose of providing quality service with all have significance (Stimac and Simic, 2012; Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016).

This research study focused on the perception of three key HE stakeholders in Pakistan. The study presents the difference in the stakeholders' perceptions of the service quality of HEIs and

its contribution towards the personal development of the students as prime consumers of the service. A proposed conceptual model is presented on the basis of SURVQUAL dimensions analysing the service quality of the student experience and the resultant personal development of the student.

1.3. The Rationale For The Research

The examination of the research studies in the areas of service marketing, service quality, and HE showed gaps in the literature that should be filled. The identified research gap provides a rationale for the study's purpose and perspective. HE as a service is an idea that has been around for a long time, but its implications for students' personal development due to the HEEs have yet to be explored in Pakistan. HEIs have a more challenging role to play in balancing between marketing the services and academic freedom. (Gibbons, 1998; Michael, 1997). Consequently, it is vital to comprehend how market-driven interventions such as service quality and student experience impact students' personal development.

The majority of research on the HESQ has been executed from the student's point of view, who are treated as HE clients (Darlaston-Jones, 2003). However, the organisational and industrial perspectives must also be considered (Reynoso and Moores, 1995; Michael, 1997; Schneider and White, 2004; Naidoo et al., 2011). Saleem et al. (2017) conducted a research study on service quality and student satisfaction in HE. The study was focused on the perspective of the students only. They suggested that a study be conducted in the Pakistani HEI context to explore the perspective of the other stakeholders including the academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs. This study looks at the procedural factors of service quality from the angle of student experiences. The organisational and industrial views contribute towards overall conceptual knowledge of HE as a service and its impact on student's personal development as a result of the HEE.

1.4. Research Questions, Aim And Objectives

The initial assessment of the study backdrop and rationale demonstrates the need and opportunity to examine and understand the disparities in stakeholder perceptions of the students' HESQ, service quality experience and its influence on their personal development in Pakistan. The following is the study's main research question:

Q. How do the stakeholders' perception of the HESQ experience and its contribution towards the personal development of students differ from each other, and how can it be improved in Pakistan?

The study has the following sub-questions to answer this research question,

Q.1. How do the aspects of HESQ contribute to the HESQ experience of the students?

Q.2. What is the importance of student satisfaction in the student experience of HESQ and its contribution to their personal development?

Q.3. What are the differences in the perception of HESQ amongst the key stakeholders of HESQ in Pakistan?

Q.4. How can HESQ be enhanced to improve the personal development of students due to their HESQ experiences in Pakistan?

Research aims and objectives are formed based on the research questions.

This research is aimed to present the differences among the stakeholders' perception of HESQ and its contribution to the personal development of the students in Pakistan and, based on the findings of this study, identify the aspects of the service which can be improved.

- The first objective is to identify the contribution of HESQ to the student's experience.
- The second objective is to examine the importance of student satisfaction from the HESQ experience contributing to personal development.
- The third objective is to investigate the distinctions in the perceptions of HESQ amongst the stakeholders of HESQ.
- The fourth objective is to make suggestions based on the study to enhance the HESQ to improve students' personal development due to their HESQ experiences.

1.5. Research Design

Literature was reviewed on each service quality aspect, quality of experience, student satisfaction, HE and student personal development resulting from HESQ and HESQ stakeholders. The determination of the conceptual model was on the basis of theories and evidence in the literature. The construct was operationalised into measurable variables primarily by conducting a literature review for each construct. The constructs were interpreted

similarly for each stakeholder group, although they were phrased differently. The philosophical assumptions, methodological approach, data collection, analysis, and interpretation procedures influence the research design (Creswell, 2019). The researcher used a pragmatic research philosophy for this study, based on the concept that there are many alternative ways to perceive the world. A single point of view cannot convey the complete picture, and there can be numerous truths (Saunders et al., 2012).

An online survey questionnaire was developed for the students of HEIs to conduct an online survey to collect the primary quantitative data. The qualitative data from the other two stakeholder groups was collected using a semi-structured interview guide script. The semi-structured interviews were conducted via Zoom. The other two stakeholder groups consist of (i) academic and non-academic staff of HEI and (ii) professionals from the industry. These data collection methods were used to fully understand and explore the differences in stakeholders' perceptions about the service quality of HESQ and its contribution to students' personal development.

The quantitative data collected was cross-examined using statistical measures, the tool used for quantitative analysis was SPSS, and the collected qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis. The quantitative results are presented with the aid of statistical tables and figures for the effective representation of the findings, and the qualitative results are presented based on the themes and sub-themes identified in the qualitative data. The research questions were answered based on the findings from the study in Chapter 5: Finding and Discussion.

1.6. Research Significance

The study's practical consequences will improve the service quality of HEIs in general and have a favourable impact on student's overall personal development, as there is little thought given to the implications of HESQ on students' personal development. This research was carried out at the crossroads, offering insight into the consequences of a service marketing viewpoint on HE from the viewpoints of key stakeholder groups, including students, HEI staff, and industry professionals. The results of this may also inspire researchers to re-examine prevailing concepts on services and the HESQ from a strictly market-oriented standpoint.

1.6.1. Theoretical Significance

This study has the following theoretical significance.

- In this study, a framework was developed to examine key stakeholders' perceptions of HESQ and its contributions to the personal development of HEI students. This approach further investigates various internal and external stakeholder groups' perceptions of the HEI's service quality and students' personal development.
- The focus of this research was on HESQ in one of the developing nations. This research might lead to more research into the differences in HESQ stakeholders' perceptions, such as a comparative study of two developing nations or a comparative study of a developing and developed country.
- This study presents the perspective of three key stakeholders who are most directly related to the service process and its outcomes, students as direct receivers, HEI staff as direct providers and industry as the indirect receiver and consumer of the service in Pakistan.

1.6.2. Managerial Significance

This study has the following managerial significance.

- This research has uncovered several service quality factors critical to stakeholders' perceptions and students' personal development. The management of HEIs can explore these aspects deeper in the alignment of their particular institute to enhance the perception of the HEI's service quality and personal development of the students.
- The service delivery perspective should not be limited to a single moment in time; it should continue to extend for a long time after that. As mentioned in the Findings and Discussion chapter, this perception of the experiences of the participants also changes with the passage of time and exposure. There is a need to develop the service aspects by keeping students as a central focus rather than the management or administration of HEI.
- This study presents the finding that the managers of HEIs can utilise to improve different aspects of the HESQ. These aspects need to be focused on by HEI managers to improve the perception of HESQ and the students' experience. The aspects of teacher-student interaction and industry-academia collaboration were one the most persistent elements. These elements perform an important part in the personal development of the students during and even after their HESQ experience.
- The management of the HEIs needs to understand the importance of providing opportunities for learning, training, and development to students and the academic and non-

academic staff to improve service. The provision of knowledge and training opportunities about new teaching methods, new research in their fields, relevant field training, and top-up courses for the teaching and non-teaching staff. Academic scholarships in general, performance-based scholarships, in specific, to motivate the students, arrangement of training seminars and workshops, and internship programs for the students are some of the aspects being suggested by many participating stakeholders.

- There is a need to adopt service evaluation practices as a continuous approach for the continuous improvement of HE service in alignment with industry trends and advancements in technology.

1.7. Thesis Structure

The thesis comprises six chapters, including an introduction, literature review, research methodology, findings and discussion, and conclusion. A brief overview of each chapter is as follows.

1.7.1. Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the research study, which includes the subject area background of the research, the research context, the rationale for the study to be conducted in order to answer the research question, the research question and sub-questions and objectives of this research study, the brief research design followed theoretical and managerial significance of this research along with the overall structure of the thesis.

1.7.2. Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter includes a comprehensive analysis of the most recent literature that is available in the fields of service quality concerning HE, as well as an examination of the service quality dimensions that are pertinent to the context of HE and the service quality measurements. This chapter also provides a review of the relevant literature in the context of HE, especially the HE system in Pakistan and the outcomes that are anticipated from HE. The latter portion of this chapter is dedicated to doing a literature study on the subject of stakeholders, more especially the three key stakeholders of HE. The last topic of this chapter was justifying the research gap that this study intended to fill.

1.7.3. Chapter 3: Research Framework

This chapter provides an overview of the proposed conceptual model used in this study to examine how service quality affects the student's perception of their own learning and personal

development and how this is perceived by the key stakeholders. The proposed relation between the five dimensions of service quality and the student experience, as well as the proposed relation between student satisfaction, form the experience and personal development. The proposed relations were evaluated. A literature review for each construct of the model was conducted to justify and define the construct. This led to the item generation for the questionnaires.

1.7.4. Chapter 4: Research Methodology

In this chapter, the rationales for the methodological choices that were selected in accordance with the research onion guideline are presented. The chapter provides justifications for the choices made about the research methodology, research strategy, research design and the choice of techniques for data collection. The quantitative data was collected from the students of HEIs via the use of an online questionnaire, and the qualitative data were collected using semi-structured interviews. Qualitative data was collected from the two groups (i) academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs and (ii) industry professionals. This chapter examined aspects of data analysis for both the qualitative and the quantitative data. The last section of this chapter discusses the ethical considerations that are related to this research study.

1.7.5. Chapter 5: Findings And Discussion

This chapter contains the findings from the data that was collected using both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Additionally, this chapter includes a discussion about the sample demographics, statistics from the quantitative data, and the themes that were discovered from the qualitative data. The tabular and graphical representations of the results were used to present the findings from quantitative data, and the presentation of the qualitative findings followed the structure of the thematic table presented. The various perspectives held by the HEI stakeholders were also compared and contrasted in this chapter. The chapter also addresses each of the four sub-questions in detail that this research aimed to answer.

1.7.6. Chapter 6: Conclusion

The conclusion chapter concludes the research study by providing a summary of the research in the form of four concise answers to research questions, presenting the contribution made by the research study in the body of knowledge, presenting the theoretical and managerial implications of the research study as well as the limitations experienced during the research and the perspective for future research.

1.8. Chapter Summary

The thesis' foundation was built in this chapter by the introduction of the research topic along with the background of the topic. The most important resource for every nation to prosper is its people. Among the key contributors to this pool of talent is the HEIs. Over the last several decades, both the public and private sectors have come to recognise the need to invest in HESQ because of the role it plays in preparing a skilled labour force for any country. In order to thrive in this fast-paced and competitive market, HEIs must maximise their efforts towards a goal of constant service enhancement. In order to thrive in this fast-paced, competitive industry, HEIs must maximise their efforts to enhance the quality of their offerings. Quality management at HEIs is very challenging. Government, organisations, educators and students are just a few of the many groups with vested interests in HE. It is critical to understand the effects that market-driven interventions, such the quality of service provided and the student experience, have on the personal development of the students. The chapter provided and justified the rationale for the research conducted by identifying the gap in the context of Pakistan HE, leading to the main research question : How does the stakeholders' perception of the HESQ experience and its contribution towards the personal development of students differ from each other, and how can it be improved in Pakistan? The main question was divided into four sub-questions which were answered in Chapter 5: Finding and Discussion. The details of the research design were also part of this chapter. This chapter also presented the theoretical and managerial significance of this study and the contribution made in the mentioned aspects. The last part of the chapter presented the outline of the research thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

Following the introduction of the research area, the justification for the research and the thesis outline, this chapter presents the literature review pertinent to service marketing, service quality, the dimensions and measurements of service quality, HE and the rankings and accreditations of HEIs in the world and specifically in Pakistan. The literature on the area of HESQ and the HE environment in Pakistan were also explored. The frameworks for evaluating the HESQ and the desired outcomes of HEEs were explored briefly. The existing literature on stakeholders in general and stakeholders of HE, in particular, was reviewed with a focus on the three key stakeholders of HE: (i) students of the HEIs, (ii) academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs and (iii) industry, represented by professionals. This chapter also includes the justification of the research gap identified to conduct this research study.

2.2. Services Marketing

According to Rust and Chung (2006), one trend that has a significant long-term impact and will continue to affect the future of marketing is the rise of the service sector. Since 1900, the percentage of the economy that is comprised of service-related jobs has been growing steadily in every industrialised country throughout the globe (Rust, 2020). There is enough of a distinction between services and goods to necessitate a separate consideration of service marketing and traditional marketing ideas (Missaghian et al., 2018). One of the fundamental contrasts between goods and services is that goods are sold after they are manufactured, while services are sold prior to being supplied to the user (Baron et al., 2018). Two key concepts of service marketing, “customer as coproducer” and “value-in-use”, serve to explain this general application and the deep contrast between the conventional, goods-dominated logic and the new service marketing-based approach (Huotari and Hamari, 2017). This might result in a service experience or value that is mutually created for the benefit of both the provider of the service and the person receiving the service (Ng and Vargo, 2018; Ameen et al., 2021).

According to mainstream marketing theory, manufacturing is carried out by the firm and value is produced throughout the production process and integrated into the finished product. The value is then included in the product, and with the transaction for the product’s transfer to the customer, the value is transferred from the firm to the customer (Huotari and Hamari, 2017; Baron et al., 2018). The value-in-exchange technique, however, loses any relevance in a service

environment since there is not a tangible good to which the value may be linked. According to the literature on service marketing, the client is always a co-producer of the service, taking part in a manufacturing process where value is created after the consumer consumes the product or services. By providing resources for the customers' processes, the firm supports the customers' processes in this value-in-use model (Huotari and Hamari, 2017; Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021).

The success of a service sector company depends on its ability to offer consistently high-quality services to its clients (El-Haddad, 2019). Before attempting to define service marketing, it is important to establish what service means within the marketing environment. There are many different ways to conceptualise service in the academic literature (Pride and Ferrell, 2019; Gronroos, 2020). Definitions of service are dynamic, reflecting changes in industry competitiveness that impact consumers' perceived value (Pride and Ferrell, 2019). Therefore, it may be useful to examine the service strategy from the perspective of value generation (Rust, 2020). A customer-centric business puts the customer at the centre of everything they do, and providing them with excellent service is essential to its success (Tan et al., 2019).

Service delivery generally involves the receiver and provider of service with the help of tangibles components (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). There are emotional implications in the procedure of service provision among the service provider, service receiver and the service environment (Lim and Maglio, 2019). The emotive and experiential aspects of the service experience and the satisfaction due to the experience demands further investigation to gain a better knowledge of services marketing (Arnould and Price, 1993; Vargo and Lusch, 2008; Vargo et al., 2020).

2.3. Service Quality

The scope of services has expanded into many directions and sectors. Services include education, health, law, NGOs, hospitality, finance, and more. The advancement of technology-enabled a rapid growth in the service spectrum. The growth in the service sector is also generating opportunities as well as employment. As Kotler and Keller (2006) mentioned, the service sector has surpassed manufacturing as the leading source of employment in the global economy. Many authors have defined service in different words. Berry (1980) referred to service as an intangible product involving a deed, an act, or an effort that cannot be physically owned.

It is simpler for the customers of service to identify and assess the tangible attributes of the service provided, but the assessment of intangible aspects is not easy, but it must be part of the evaluation of service. Even an in-depth understanding of a product is insufficient to fully comprehend the nature of service, demonstrating that service is more complicated than commodities or products and more difficult to quantify accurately (Zeithaml and Berry, 1985). The differentiation of service from products can be one the basis of the service and product characteristics. Products are tangibles, and services and intangibles; products have the characteristics of homogeneity, which is generally lacking in the services.

Gronroos (1990) presented a popular definition of service which he modified in 2000 “A service is a process consisting of a series of more or less intangible activities that normally, but not necessarily always, take place in interactions between the customer and service employees and/or physical resources or goods and/or systems of the service provider, which are provided as solutions to customer problems” (p.37). Zeithaml and Bitner (2003) defined service as “deed, process and performance” (p.20). Fitzsimmons and Fitzsimmons (2011) were of the view that service is an intangible, time-perishable experience provided to a consumer who acts as a co-producer. Table 2.1 displays a chronological list of service definitions compiled by other researchers. Based on an analysis of the definitions, it is fair to presume that clients benefit from the value that services supply because a service is a good thing (Tan, 2017). It is something designed by the provider with the customer in mind.

Table 2.1: Defining Service

(Adopted from Tan, 2017)

Year	Service Marketing Researcher	Definition
1985	Zeithaml et al.	Services are not items; they are performances that are invisible and intangible. They are intangible, intrinsically tied to progress and consumption, and they come in various forms with perishability.
1990	Shaw	A service significantly improves the condition or position of the recipient.

2004	Schneider and White	A service is something that is performed on us or our behalf.
2008	Vargo and Lusch	Service is applying competencies to the advantage of the receiver through acts, procedures, and performances.
2009	Zeithaml et al.	Services are deeds, processes, and performances.
2010	Walsh and Gordon	A transactional service is a meeting between a company's clients and its employees.
2011	Tjiptono	Service is a process of interaction in doing something to someone.
2017	Gemmel et al.	A service is an experience or a procedure that does not have a distinct point of sale during its delivery.
2019	Parkurar et al.	Services are heterogeneous, intangible and perishable in terms of production and consumption.
2021	Wirtz and Lovelock	Service provides benefits without ownership

Products are produced or manicured at one place and distributed and consumed at a different location, whereas the services are produced, distributed and consumed in a simultaneous manner. The value of a product is created at the place of production, while the value of service is generated in the interaction of provider and receiver (Gronroos, 1990). There is no contribution of the customer to the quality of the product, whereas customers directly contribute to the quality of service (Mills et al., 1983). The quality of the service delivery using system tools has a direct impact on the receiver's perception of service quality.

Comprehending quality as the underlying construct is critical to understanding service quality. Several contemporary quality philosophers have given their perspectives on quality description (Crosby, 1979; Deming, 1986; Garvin, 1987; Juran, 1988). These ideas, on the other hand, are primarily drawn based on the prospect of manufacturing, with a customer-centric approach that implies quality can be measured, has a set of criteria that can be followed, and has room for improvement over time (Tan, 2017). Table 2.2 presents the definitions of quality by

contemporary scholars from a strictly industrial perception. The common aspect amongst these concepts is a focus on the client's need, which implies tangibility and uniformity of goods served, as well as separability between production and use. While these concepts are prescriptive in terms of providing consumer attention, what is obviously missing is an awareness that service, unlike mass-produced goods, is not tangible and varied. As previously stated, service development and usage are inextricably connected.

Table 2.2: Defining Quality

Year	Scholar	Definition
1981	Juran	"Quality is something being fit for use."
1987	Garvin	"Quality means pleasing Consumers."
1988	Juran	"Quality is about fitness for use on purpose."
2007	Yang and Liu	"Quality must satisfy both stated and implied needs."
2007	Kotler	"Quality is the sum of a product or service's traits and attributes that contribute to its ability to meet explicit or implicit demands."
2015	Abdulla and Abdul-Rahman	"Quality is characterised as whatever the buyer sees as a quality."
2019	Pakurár et al.	"How companies meet and exceed customer's expectations."
2021	Vasudevan	"Quality is a physical and non-physical attribute that serves as the foundation for a good or service or one of its distinguishing features."

The findings of Parasuraman et al. (1985) have led to a more widely used definition of service quality, and they describe the quality of service as the difference between the service receiver's expectation and perception (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Hill, 1995). A judgement regarding a service's overall excellence is sometimes defined as service quality (Schneider and White, 2004). However, since service is not the same as a consumer product, the manufacturing

mentality of quality cannot be extended to them all, and it is unsuccessful in the HE service field (Beckford, 2010).

It is helpful to discuss service quality after defining what it is and how customers perceive it (Gronroos, 1990; Atmaja et al., 2020). Since Parasuraman et al. (1985; 1988) original programme to conceptualise the meaning of quality of service, researchers have been working on a universal definition. It is equally crucial to define service quality when attempting to define it. The description of services by Schneider and White (2004) has two parts: what processes are managed and how they are distributed. HE is a service that combines all of these characteristics (Dado and Taborecka-Petrovicova, 2011). The quality of education is a multi-faceted phenomenon that is impacted by shifting tendencies and societal and economic pressures, as well as the progression of the social development of students (Abbas, 2020). Table 2.3 presents the service quality definitions from different authors in chronological order.

Table 2.3. Defining Service Quality

Year	Scholar	Definition
1988	Parasuraman et al.	Service quality is the outcome of a customer's overall rating of a service provider based on a comparison of client expectations and perceived quality attained.
1997	Ibrahim	Service quality is the cornerstone of company strategy because it ensures that the final product or service will satisfy the needs and wants of both internal and external customers.
2007	Chakrabarty et al.	Service quality is the way a service provider adapts to the customer's needs.
2015	Abdullah and Abdul-Rahman	Service quality guarantees total satisfaction.
2018	Kowalik and Klimecka-Tatar	Service quality is the representation of service delivery perfection.
2019	Pakurar et al.	Service quality is how companies meet or exceed customer expectations.

2021	Ali et al.	Service quality is an inclination to focus on the needs of the client as well as their trust and expectations of the service.
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The qualities of service are also crucial to its comprehension. According to Parasuraman et al. (1985), three factual attributes of service which are accepted for the service quality to be fully appreciated are heterogeneousness, inseparability, and diversity. This implies that, as a performed task, service has no tangible shape and varies depending on client contact and is generated and consumed simultaneously (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Schneider and White, 2004). Except that the student is also interested in the delivery of service, HE has all of these characteristics of a service (Kundu, 2017). The main emphasis of HE as a service is on offering high-quality learning opportunities to the student as the customer (Yeo and Li, 2012; Tan et al., 2016).

As defined in perception, quality is described as the ability to interpret something in the services literature. According to Beckford (2010), the role of emotion and perception in determining the quality of service is a theoretical notion that replicates distinct perspectives (p. 14). Standardisation and compliance, which are normative quality assumptions for consumer goods, may not follow the previously described features of service and cannot be presented precisely based on the output that is related to the recipient and scenario in the case of services (Kundu, 2017; Scharager and Goldenberg, 2018).

2.4. Service Quality Dimensions

The dimensional nature of service quality is an important subject because it may be utilised to investigate the theoretical linkages that exist between different service characteristics (John and Senith, 2012). For instance, if researchers know that there are five components that make up service quality, they will be able to investigate the linkage that exists between each component of service quality and constructs like satisfaction and personal development from experience. It is desirable to address the idea of quality into attainable components from the customer's viewpoint to attain quality increases and meet the customers' expectations (Paretorius et al., 2018). Although there are many definitions of quality and quality of service in the available literature, defining and comprehending the quality dimensions that receivers can use to measure the quality of the service in order to assist them in gaining a clearer understanding of the meaning of quality (Abdullah et al., 2014; Dicker et al., 2019).

Parasuraman et al. (1985), were the first to suggest the dimensions of service quality in general. Their proposal was based on exploratory research that identified ten essential categories. These were further developed into the five dimensions of contemporary service quality that are measured by the SERVQUAL scale, which are namely tangibles, assurance, reliability, empathy, and responsiveness (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Since that time, a number of studies have been published, including Gronroos (1990), Shank et al. (1995), Owlia and Aspinwall (1996), Cook (1997), Joseph and Joseph (1997), Kara and Deshields (2004), Tan and Kek (2004), Telford and Masson (2005), Abdula (2006a), Pereda et al. (2007), Angel (2008), Jain et al. (2010), Sultan and Wong (2011), John and Senith (2012), Abdullah et al. (2014) and Parkurar et al. (2019). These studies yielded a number of insights on the quality of HE, which are presented in a chronological format in Table 2.4. Despite the fact that these dimensions are defined using a variety of different terminologies, the dimensions that are shown in the table below are a logical match with the dimensions that are utilised in SERVQUAL (Danjuma et al., 2018).

Table 2.4: Dimensions Of HESQ

(Adopted from Tan, 2017)

Year	Researcher	No	Dimensions
1985	Parasuraman et al.	• 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangibility • Reliability • Responsiveness • Competence • Access • Courtesy • Communication • Credibility • Security • Understanding • Standards of organisation • Assessment and feedback
1990	Gronroos	• 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill and professionalism

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attitude and behaviour • Accessible and flexible • Reliable and trustworthy • Reputed and credible
1995	Shank et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect for student • Faculty knowledge • Physical environment
1996	Owlia and Aspinwall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangibles • Competency • Attitude • Content • Delivery • Reliability
1997	Joseph and Joseph	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical aspects • Cost/Time • Academic issues • Program issues • Career opportunities • Location • Others
2004	Kara and Deshields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faculty • Advising staff • Classes
2006a	Abdula	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reputation • Access • Program issues • Understanding • Recognition

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of instruction and interaction with faculty
2007	Pereda et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource Sufficiency • Faculty Quality • Tangibility • Reliability
2008	Angell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic services • Leisure services • Industry connections • Costs and value
2009	Brochado	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsiveness • Assurance • Empathy
2010	Jain et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual appeal • Result quality • Campus • Reputation • Students' quality • Industry connections • Faculty expertise quality • Interpersonal relation • Curriculum
2011	Sultan and Wong	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic service • Administration service • Quality of facilities
2012	Annamdevula and Bellamkonda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching and course content • Administrative service • Academic facilities • Campus infrastructure

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support services
2012	John and Senith	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faculty communication • Inter-personal behaviour of faculty • Facilities • Administration • Student safety
2019	Parkurar et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability • Assurance • Responsiveness • Tangibles • Empathy • Access to service • Financial aspects • Employee competences
2021	Ramirez-Hurtado et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System characteristics • Efficacy of online teaching • The students' relationships with their professors and the evaluation of the professors • Satisfaction with online teaching

Empirical research has been conducted in the field of HE (Yeo, 2008; Zhang et al., 2017; Allam, 2018; Haw, 2018). Students want educators in to include high-quality teaching and learning as a service responsibility. They expect new techniques are used to convey the knowledge. In order to enhance the process of knowledge transferability in HE, the consideration of students' preferences is vital. HEIs can deliver an improved service by developing an understanding of the attributes of the course participants, HEI environment, lecture support and many other aspects (Husain et al., 2009; Ramirez-Hurtado et al., 2021).

An examination of existing research suggests that students' expectations are inconsistent, which can be based on the educational institution and its country of origin (Haw, 2018). Students

expect individualised attention (Darlaston-Jones et al., 2003). Chonko et al. (2002) mentioned the differences in expectations of the students; few students expect teachers to be demanding and well-informed, despite the fact that these are qualities of a committed educator who is focused on the student's learning. Instead, most students value qualities like "doing my homework for me" and "offering me a break" as more important. Voss et al. (2007) found that students desire educated and engaging teachers, and they like to gain essential teaching experiences in order to pass summative tests and be organised for their future careers.

As discussed above, service quality is a contextual issue; its dimensions vary greatly (Sultan and Wong, 2019). Furthermore, the quality-of-service characteristics cannot be generalised across all service kinds (Chowdhary and Prakash, 2007; Mestrovic, 2017). Even while similar dimensions exist in a variety of situations, the existence of traits unique to each service business necessitates the discovery of its own dimensions (Owlia and Aspinwall, 1996; Lakal et al., 2020). In HE, there is a general lack of agreement on the aspects of service quality (Li and Kaye, 2006), which are influenced by the accessibility of knowledge and previous experience (Sultan and Wong, 2019). This study will be based on the five core dimensions SERVQUAL which has been widely used in the HESQ research.

2.5. Service Quality Measurement

The measurement of service quality dimensions is critical to the evaluation of service quality (Abdullah, 2006; Parasuraman et al., 1998). HEIs must monitor service quality regularly to manage and enhance the services they deliver (Chong and Ahmed, 2012). To measure the quality of service, there is a need for a system or a procedure to be used for the purpose (Sunder and Sunder, 2016). These evaluations enable the HEIs to prioritise the aspects of service quality that are most effective in student satisfaction (Latif et al., 2017). When evaluating service quality, it is significant to look at both consumer expectations of the elements of service quality as well as their overall perception of service quality (Schneider and White, 2004). Numerous measurement models are presented for the improvement in understanding of customer's perception and expectation of service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Abdullah, 2006), just as there are numerous sets of quality service dimensions (Zeithaml et al., 1990).

The deliverance of service quality is guided by human behaviour; service quality parameters may change in different service environments. Healthcare services, for example, may need a high level of "empathy" and "responsiveness," whereas transport services might need a higher

degree of "reliability." Because of its intangible nature and the lack of concrete proof of service, the perception of HESQ is a complicated phenomenon that offers study challenges. SERVQUAL model presented by Parasuraman et al. (1988), the SERVPERF model presented by Cronin and Taylor (1992), and the HEdPERF model presented by Abdulla (2006) along with some other models is for measuring service quality in HE (Abdullah, 2006). Depending on whether standards are used as a predictor of service quality, these models fit into one of two quality-of-service assessment concepts: the disconfirmation paradigm or the perceiving paradigm (Ali et al., 2016). SERVQUAL is a member of the disbelief model, while SERVPERF and HEdPERF are members of the perception paradigm (Brochado, 2009; Ali et al., 2016).

2.5.1. SERVQUAL

The most prevalent measure of service quality is SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al., 1988), which is based on disconfirmation (Angell et al., 2008; Lodesso et al., 2018). The difference between expectation and perception, which indicates how successfully an organisation provides a service to its customers, is used to determine service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Rowley, 1997). Initially, Parasuraman et al. (1988), presented ten dimensions of service quality as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, competence, courtesy, access, security, communication and understanding the customer. After the revisions and refinements, five dimensions of SERVQUAL were developed (Schneider and White, 2004). The five dimensions are tangibles, assurance, reliability, empathy and responsiveness (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

In the start, the instrument was valid for limited services, but later it was said to be suitable for many different service sectors with some modifications (Bojanic and Rosen, 1994). To get the results, the data must be collected twice, before and after the service experience (Clemes et al., 2001). The studies which have adopted the SERVQUAL model as a tool to measure the service quality of HE are Cuthbert (1996), Soutar and McNeil (1996), Pariseau and McDaniell (1997), Arambewela and Hall (2009), Wong et al. (2012), Kashif et al. (2016), Kouchaki and Motaghi (2017), Leonnard (2018), Hwang and Choi (2019), Sibai et al. (2021), Fuchs and Fangpong (2021), Sumi and Kabir (2021) and Magasi et al. (2022).

On the other hand, regardless of the popularity of SERVQUAL, it has received quite a share of criticism as well. The SERVQUAL is considered problematic in HE because it was designed in service and retail settings to assess consumer expectations of service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Parasuraman et al., 1991a). SERVQUAL focuses on "customers' basic areas of

service quality," but it has not been tested in a broad enough range of service organisations to be widely applicable (Cook, 1997, p. 120). SERVQUAL is claimed to focus on customer-important aspects of service quality; however, there have been concerns about its dimensionality, validity, and application (Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Sumi and Kabir, 2021).

According to Ladhari (2009), the SERVQUAL model is insufficiently broad, and that new dimensions should be added to the model in order to quantify service quality more accurately. There are particular characteristics of HE services which are not fulfilled by this scale (Latif et al., 2017). Students' service experiences are complicated and distinct from those of consumers in other service industries. As a result, it is agreed that sector-specific measures of service should be used to assess the quality of service in every sector (Hwang and Choi, 2019). There is still no agreement on the critical success criteria of quality management, especially in developing nations' HE (Asif et al., 2013; Fuchs and Fangpong, 2021).

2.5.2. SERVPERF

Many research studies have focused on the dispute over how to quantify HESQ and presented models that are actually adaptations of SERVQUAL (Seth et al., 2005; Borowaska et al., 2018; Mason et al., 2018). These alternative models are designed to resolve the issues surrounding the value and context of the SERVQUAL disconfirmation-based model's "expectation-perception" distance approach to service quality measurement (Abdullah, 2006; Sonkova and Grabowska, 2015; Bui et al., 2022). The expectation-perception model, which stands for "evaluated results" (Teas, 1993), for example, disputes the utility of SERVQUAL's "expectations-performance" method and instead recommends using a "performance-minus-ideal" gap approach for measuring service quality (Danjuma et al., 2018).

SERVPERF was presented by Cronin and Taylor (1992) and is a popular substitute for SERVQUAL (Ng and Forbes, 2009; Bajraktarill and Atrek, 2010; Park and Yi, 2016; Ingaldi, 2016). SERVPERF believes that evaluating expectations is superfluous and instead uses a perception-only scale, and it is a more precise and valuable tool for assessing service quality (Abdullah, 2006; Angell et al., 2008; Hassan and Jafri, 2017; Tiarawati, 2018). This new model kept perception items in from the SERVQUAL and removed the items related to the expectation and is based on the five aspects of service quality. Cronin and Taylor (1992) referred to it as it may be an improved means of measuring service quality.

Many researchers, including Ekinici and Riley (1998); Parasuraman et al. (1994); Durvasula et al. (1999); Jain and Gupta (2004) and Ganic et al. (2018), recommend utilising the perceptions-

only measure of service quality since it appears to be a more reliable, convergent, and predictive than the perceptions-plus-expectations measure. Cronin and Taylor (1994, pp.129-130) made a claim about the SERVPERF that it can “provide a longitudinal index of the service quality perceptions” and also “provide managers with a summed overall service quality score that can be formed relative to time and certain consumer group”. Their claim was supported by Lee et al. (2000) that this perception-only approach is better than the expectation-perception approach. Even though the SERVPERF became popular and is widely used, it did not reduce the use of SERVQUAL in the research on service quality (Carrillat et al., 2007; Muthugala and Ekanayake, 2018). SERVPERF was criticised for its disadvantages. One of the leading critiques of this model is the absence of fundamental relation between expectations and performance (Shauchenka, 2015). Measuring the quality of service based only on performance is doubtful (Wong and Sultan, 2021).

2.5.3. HEdPERF

HEdPERF was created in response to the shortcomings of SERVQUAL and SERVPERF as models of measuring service quality in HE (Randheer et al., 2015; Silva et al., 2017; Purwanto et al., 2020). HEdPERF is considered more relevant to the HE context as SERVQUAL and SERVPERF are pretty generic to be used for HEIs (Abdullah et al., 2014; Lam and Trang, 2021). It incorporates parts of both SERVQUAL and SERVPERF, as well as academics and the student's overall service environment (Abdullah, 2006; Purgailis and Zaksa, 2012; Silva et al., 2017). The HEdPERF model assesses significant components of service quality, such as educational elements, non-educational features, reliability, and the empathy that HE services should deliver (Abdullah et al., 2014; Khalid et al., 2021).

The HEdPERF was formed with six dimensions academic aspects, non-academic aspects, reputation, access, program issue and understanding (Abdulla, 2006a). After the modification, the dimension of understanding was removed due to the low reliability score (Abdulla, 2006b). The reliability score of the finalised five dimensions was better than the score of SERVPERF (GUO, 2018). Despite the fact that the HEdPERF is a more quality-based service assessment model for HE, research has shown that it has yet to demonstrate that it offers the most reliable measurement ability for HESQ (Brochado, 2009; Ravichandran et al., 2012; Tsinidou et al., 2010; Danjuma et al., 2018). HEdPERF is criticised by the researchers as well. The model uses only positively worded statements, and some researchers consider this as a limitation of the model that a measuring instrument should use both positive and negative statements (Gilmore, 1974; Kaur and Amanpreet, 2020). There are many groups of stakeholders in HE, but the model

is only concentrated on the students, ignoring all the other stakeholder groups, who are also influential on the service quality of HEIs (Abbas, 2020).

2.5.4. SQM-HEI

The Service Quality Measurement in HE in India (SQM-HEI) model was presented as a useful technique to measure the service quality of HEIs (Senthilkumar and Arulraj, 2011). By adopting this model, the data gets collected using structured questionnaires having six sections. The first section of the questionnaire has ten questions addressing the teaching methodology (TM), the second section has five queries concerning the environmental change in the study factor (ECSF), the third section of the questionnaire is based on questions about the corrective actions taken by institutions, the next part is concerned about the placement-related activities, the fifth section covers the area of an overall assessment of service quality (Senthilkumar and Arulraj, 2011). The last section consists of questions about the demographical background of the respondents to the questionnaire (Shauchenka, 2015). SQM-HEI can be referred to as the adaptation of SERVQUAL to measure the HESQ with specific attributes of the Indian HEI service context (Shauchenka, 2015).

Given the consideration of several models established for measuring service quality in the previous sections, it is suitable to say that there is no accurate tool exists so far to measure the service quality in HE. A desirable strategy for assessing service quality in HE has yet to be discovered. Despite the fact that SERVQUAL, SERVPERF, and HEDPERF are commonly recognised as appropriate standard models for measuring the quality of service, there is not enough agreement on their efficiency (Sultan and Wong, 2010; Tsinidou et al., 2010; Teeroovengadum et al., 2016; Latif et al., 2018). The applicability of these general frameworks in this industry is still unclear (Tan, 2017), and a more particular model for measuring service quality in HE is required (Abdullah, 2006; Twaissi and Kilani, 2015; Teerooyegadum et al., 2016).

The model should not only rely on alternative ways to replace the SERVQUAL approach; instead, it can be modified, and the known aspects of service quality should be included (Parasuraman et al., 1994; Tan and Kek, 2004; Abdullah, 2006; Tan, 2017; Tripathi and Siddiqui, 2018). It is also critical to investigate the contribution of service quality towards the personal development of students as an outcome of the quality of students' HEEs (Tan et al., 2016; Tan, 2017). Furthermore, service contracts are said to be an excellent way to manage standards and perceptions in order to produce more favourable quality decisions on service

quality, emphasising the importance of comprehending the complexities while developing instruments for evaluating HESQ (Tan, 2017).

2.6. Higher Education

HE is a tool for shaping a person's character and the character of a society or nation (Singh, 2016). The researchers contend that HE is not about providing a product or service to a client, but rather it is an ongoing process of student transformation (Teeroovangadum et al., 2019). HEIs play an essential part in the growth and prosperity of the country, particularly in light of the increasingly complex nature of today's global environment. In developing nations, the quality of the next generation is dependent on the quality of HE, which both, directly and indirectly impact the progression of the country (Aziz et al., 2018). The most significant human resource, which is essential to the operation of any organisation in management, planning, design, executing, teaching and research, is acquired via HE, which serves as the primary source of this resource (Iqbal and Bhatti, 2020).

HE providers are increasingly seen as being dependent on selling their services (Gibbs and Murphy, 2009; Camilleri, 2020). HE is seen as a service, and there has been an uptick in published work on the topic of service marketing in HE (sultan and Wong, 2014; Latif et al., 2019). In addition to this, HEIs are obligated to consider the implications of their marketing activities from a legal standpoint (Gibbs and Murphy, 2009). HE deserves special consideration because of its crucial role in the creation and implementation of a system of lifelong learning and development. This significance is a result of the standing and influence that HEIs have within the educational systems of the majority of nations, as well as of their contribution to theory development and research (Knapper et al., 2021).

In most parts of the world, the growth of private HE has occurred with little in the way of a deliberate strategy. The private sector was traditionally seen as peripheral to the HE system, but this perception has changed as more students enrol in and are placed by private institutions in the workforce. They are becoming more and more integrated into the general culture and are no longer considered alternatives to the standard university system. Many innovative educational technologies have been developed by private institutes (Altbach et al., 2019).

The emphasis placed by HEIs on designing and deploying systems to gauge student satisfaction with the learning experience, including course experience questionnaires, reflects the importance of conceptualising the HEEs (Grace et al., 2012; Yin et al., 2014). Because of the

economic importance of HE, there are disputes (Altbach, 2001; Tilak, 2008; Van-Damme and Van-Der-Wende, 2018) on whether it should be considered a public or private good (Van-Damme and Van-Der-Wende, 2018). Private commodities are traded between a manufacturer and a customer, and their capacity of consumption is restricted by their financial means, whereas public commodities are freely and routinely available to all consumers (Marginson and Van der Wende, 2007).

HE has long been considered a public good because of the assistance it provides to people and society as a whole, but due to the consequences of globalisation, neoliberal economic policies, and trade liberalisation, it is increasingly being recognised as a viable private good (Tilak, 2008; Teichler, 2017; Bista et al., 2018; McCann et al., 2019). Global trade policies that aim to guide HE towards a private good ignore the essential concept of the social compact, substitute academic ideals, and social issues can collide with commercial considerations and personal interests, resulting in irreversible and unfavourable outcomes for the entire society (Tilak, 2008, Chan, 2016).

The most pressing issue facing HE today includes not just the qualities that society places a premium on in students but also the perspectives that students have on their time in HE (Abdullah, 2006; Khattab, 2018). Tight (2012) identified some of the primary areas of investigation within HE research in which hypotheses are being produced. This serves to illustrate the diverse character of HE. Teaching and learning, the design of courses offered, the student experience throughout the duration of their course, efficiency, system and procedures, academic work, as well as information and study, are some of the subjects that are discussed. Ideas about HEIs and the roles they play are also prevalent in the study literature on HE (Barnacle and Dall'Alba, 2017). The rising number of consumer-like behaviours shown by students has promoted a re-assessment of the connection between value and HE (Tomlinson, 2017).

2.6.1. Ranks And Accreditations

The proliferation of rankings for academic institutions and degree programs has given rise to a new driving force in HE on a local, regional and international scale. The public, institutes and even governments will sometimes take these rankings seriously, despite the fact that they are subject to criticism (Altbach et al., 2019). Individuals use the categories to evaluate different locations in which to pursue their education, and governments are beginning to use them more in the decision-making process about financial allocations for research. HEIs that use English

as the primary language of teaching and research, that are older, that contain a very wide variety of specialities and programs such as medical faculties, and that get major research funding from the government or other sources are favoured by international rankings (Sadlak and Liu, 2007).

Globalisation has changed the character and roles of educational institutions all over the world, and many institutes are adopting business-like strategies to compete in the global HE marketplace (Yeo, 2009; Carter and Yeo, 2009). Because of the inescapable nature of the global environment's effects, it is impossible for the institutions of HE to escape being affected by it. The degree to which institutions are motivated and capable of internationalisation is impacted by a variety of local circumstances, including but not limited to financial aspects, language, academic advancement and other variables (Altbach et al., 2019). Because of globalisation effects, HEIs must now work harder than ever to keep their HE service both competitive and adaptable to the ever-shifting demands of the global marketplace. It is important for countries to practise quality assurance in order to check up on, maintain and improve quality (OECD, 2014).

Quality controls, quality audits, accreditations, validations and quality evaluations and measurements are common features of quality assurance systems in HE that aim to maintain and enhance quality (Maasse and Stensaker, 2011). Quality management at the HEI level, as well as quality assurance and certification systems at the national, provincial and international levels, all fall under this category. Throughout the globe, accreditations are becoming more popular as a means of guaranteeing the external quality of universities and colleges (Altbach et al., 2009; Stensaker and Karakhanyan, 2020).

HEIs are required to show stakeholders that they are responsive. The standard that governmental authorities, accrediting bodies and other stakeholders are establishing for the performance of HEIs has led to increasing expectations (Ludeman et al., 2009). Stakeholders want institutions to back up claims of greatness and effectiveness with evidence, and HEIs are expected to do just that. HEIs require a lot of facts to figure out how they should react to the educational, economic and employment issues in the light of the current global climate and the impact of the pandemic (Toquero, 2020).

Despite the importance of worldwide ranking systems in evaluating and promoting the quality of HEIs, there are concerns and debates regarding how they should be used. Educators should be aware of the disadvantages of global ranking systems for HEIs. A key point of contention is whether ranking systems have methodological problems in terms of the factors utilised to

rate the institutions (Tambi et al., 2008; Van der Wende, 2018). Even if these rating metrics for HEIs are required and appropriate for HEI performance management, academics are concerned (Tambi et al., 2008; Altbach et al., 2009; Longden, 2011; Valmorbida and Ensslin, 2017). With a connection to data collection methods and assumptions, statistical correctness of performance measures, reputation survey reliability, and indicator selection as only indirect markers of educational aim achievement.

In Pakistan, the HECP is the regulatory authority that is formed to regulate all the HEIs in Pakistan. All the HEIs are bound to operate their quality assurance under the supervision of HECP. The HECP rating is not commercial; it gathers information from university administrators rather than from client feedback on service excellence. Because students seek this information before enrolling in university, regardless of their prior experiences, the HECP rating is used as the university's image (Arif et al., 2017). Other than HECP, quality in both public sector and private sector institutes is regularly monitored through visits and inspections by a number of accreditation bodies like the National Accreditation Council for Teachers Education (NACTE), the National Business Education Accreditation Council (NBEAC) and the National Computing Education Accreditation Council (NCEAC). They regularly conduct visits and provide workshops to monitor the delivery of quality education in HEIs (Latif et al., 2017).

The preceding remarks about HEI ranking systems demonstrate that they do not use metrics that adequately represent academic excellence and therefore do not provide knowledge and feedback about the level of education and knowledge that HEIs provide (Van der Wende, 2017). Surprisingly, existential ranking systems' unwillingness to do differently runs against quality assurance requirements, which demand that students have access to high-quality education and learning experience (Tan, 2017).

2.7. Higher Education Pakistan

Pakistan was part of the subcontinent (Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka), which was a British colony until 1947, and its inherited universities ran and governed by the British government. In comparison to the original universities in European nations, the institutions formed in colonial nations had distinct operations and procedures. During the colonial period, a European form of education was taught. Pakistan did not have the means or capacity to overhaul the current British-European HE paradigm after

independence. Therefore, the institutions it acquired were administered in the same capacity (Qureshi, 2012). Punjab University was founded in 1882 and is presently located in Pakistan; It was the only HEI in the country following the partition in 1947.

Initially, the government sector was the only source of HE, but now Pakistan's HE system includes both government and private institutions. All of these institutions are governed by the HECP, which was formed in 2002. The demand for HE, on the other hand, vastly outstripped the government's capacity. The government realised that HE would require a huge influx of funding in the future (Latif et al., 2017). Because government finances were insufficient to maintain many public institutions, the institutions had no choice except to raise funding from their own resources (Hussain, 2005). As a result, the government granted permission for the formation of private HEIs.

The establishment of private-sector education institutions allowed the HE sector to develop and allowed it to focus on quality-based education techniques. The private sector educational institutes contested established systems and proposed new educational models (HEC, 2012). According to Anwar (2007), the 1990s provided more chances for the private sector in Pakistan. In HE, the private sector is creating new opportunities for collaboration (Raza et al., 2020). The most significant shift in their national viewpoint is regarding the hiring of teachers and the admission of students (Qureshi, 2012).

The quality of education in both government and private HEIs is frequently monitored through inspections and workshops conducted by accreditation bodies such as the National Accreditation Council for Teachers Education (NACTE), the National Business Education Accreditation Council (NBEAC), and the National Computing Education Accreditation Council (NCEAC) (Latif et al., 2017). According to the HECP (2022), currently, there are a total of 246 HEIs operating in Pakistan. Out of the total, 147 are government-sector HEIs (including semi-government HEIs), and 99 are private-sector HEIs. These HEIs are based in all seven of the administrative units of Pakistan. There are 25 HEIs offering HE services in Islamabad, the capital city of Pakistan, including 17 HEIs in the public sector and 8 in the private sector. There are 87 HEIs in the province of Punjab, of which 51 are government sector and 36 are private sector HEIs. There are 71 HEIs in Sindh province, 30 of which are public and 41 are private sector HEIs. There are 43 HEIs in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, comprising of 32 government and 11 private sector institutions. There are 11 HEIs in Baluchistan province, 10 of which are government sector HEIs.

In Islamabad, the capital city of Pakistan, there are HEIs providing HE services, 17 of them are government sector HEIs and 8 are private sector HEIs. In province of Punjab there are a total of 87 HEIs, 51 are government and 36 are private sector HEIs. In Sindh province there are 71 HEIs, 30 of these HEIs are government and remaining 41 are private sector HEIs. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, there are 43 HEIs including 32 Government sector and 11 private sector HEIs. In Baluchistan province the total number of HEIs is 11 where 10 are government sector HEIs and one private sector HEI. In Gilgit Baltistan region there are 2 HEIs and both are from government sector. In Azad Jammu and Kashmir region there are 7 HEIs, 5 are government and 2 are private sector HEIs. There are 2 HEIs in the Gilgit Baltistan region, and both are in the government sector. There are 7 HEIs in Azad Jammu and Kashmir region, 5 of them are government and 2 are private sector HEIs.

2.8. Higher Education Service Quality

HE's perception as a service is prevalent in the literature on service marketing (Nadiri et al., 2009; Ng and Forbes, 2009; Osman and Ashraf, 2019). Measurement of the quality of service provided in the education industry is challenging since it requires evaluating the quality of lecturers, administration, the output of research, the production of knowledge (by academics, non-academics and students) and the accomplishments of the institution (Padlee et al., 2021). The theoretical framework for this study is developed based on the service element of HE, as there are overarching theories of services marketing and HE. Even though they are distinct from commercial facilities, research (Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka, 2006) has a proclivity to analyse service marketing and HE theory.

There are variations in the perspective about quality coming from the variety of individuals and organisations in the HE setting; the quality cannot be commonly accepted in the setting of HE (Hayden and Thompson, 2000; Beerkens and Udam, 2017). The notion of service quality is a complicated and ambiguous one (Li and Kaye, 1999; Smith et al., 2007; Gorla et al., 2010, Brockerhoff et al., 2015), therefore, service quality remains a contentious issue for future studies due to the relativity in the notion of quality. Because of disparities in an understanding of quality, it is not easy to reach a common definition of HE (Smith et al., 2007; Latif et al., 2019). Every stakeholder in HE has a unique perspective on quality based on their distinct

demands (Dicker et al., 2019). As a result, service quality is a relative concept, as it differs depending on the personal perspective. One more difficulty in defining service quality is that each of the HEEs is inimitable, and it is affected mainly by the expectations of individuals.

In the HE context, service quality is defined as the “difference between what a student anticipates to have and his or her impressions of actual delivery” (Gorgodz et al., 2020). It is also referred to as the comprehensive deliverance of student-centred service that facilitates students' growth (Dicker and Garcia, 2019; Latif et al., 2019). Education service quality is a continuous process (Nikel and Lowe, 2010) that grows over time, with universities having the chance to continuously develop service for the same consumers (students), providing service providers adequate time to increase their level of service provision. HEIs have a chance to improve by learning from their errors and exceeding students' expectations (Henderson-Smart et al., 2006).

Many HEIs have recognised that they operate in a service sector and that addressing the expectations and demands of their customers, the students, is critical (Russell, 2005; Ramzi et al., 2022). The dynamic regional, national and global development has led to the rapid transformation in the HE context, and this has raised the attention towards HE (De Jager and Gbadamosi, 2013). Quality of service is an ongoing process (Nikel and Lowe, 2010) that keeps on evolving with the passage of time and generates opportunities for the HEIs of opportunities of continuously improve their service to the customers (Latif et al., 2019).

Service quality is also described to as the uniqueness of learning and personal development experience provided by the HEIs to the students (Yeo, 2008). The elements of the uniqueness of experience can be the classroom facilities, teaching methods, extra-curricular activities, supervision, support of administration staff or resource access (Latif et al., 2017). HEIs have begun to adopt quality management principles and practices in order to provide unique experiences. A customer-oriented approach to quality can result in a one-of-a-kind experience (Latif et al., 2017). According to Liu (2002), the teaching process is fundamentally a process of HE services. Education contains the traits of simultaneity, perishability, intangibility, difference, long-term effect, and plurality (Ma, 2004; Dicker and Garcia, 2019).

2.9. Outcomes Of Higher Education

Education increases the marginal productivity of labour, which in turn increases incomes, according to the classic account of Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964). The lifetime wages

of educated labour determine the value of education investment. Education, labour, productivity and income are linear. Graduate wages follow when students develop embodied productivity. HE stimulates private enrichment, professional achievement and national economic development in its original form (Marginson, 2019). For economic and societal reasons, HEIs are graded on how successfully they develop students' skills (Wright, 2011). Students' academic outcomes and personal development should be differentiated. Although a student's learning outcome comprises a wide variety of qualities and talents, HE outcomes solely in the form of grades show students' progress (McCarthy, 2017).

The goal of HE must be clarified in order to define the composition of HE outcomes. As HE is such a vital part of a country's economy and culture, it must provide substantial returns to society by positively improving people's lives and providing the skills and information needed for economic transformation and innovation (Harvey and Knight, 1996; Browne, 2010; Nicholson, 2011; Dicker et al., 2019). In addition to technical skills, students can improve holistically due to their HEEs (Bultjens and Robinson, 2011; Ciobanu, 2013).

The literature has revealed a number of different combinations of outcomes from HEEs. There is still some debate about what exactly defines a successful HEE, but these HE courses are beginning to be developed with outcomes in mind (Gurukkal, 2018). In typical service activities, providers carry out tasks for customers; in HE, the customers are actively engaged in the process (Sharabati et al., 2019). Students join HEIs with the goal of enhancing their own personal and professional growth via the acquisition of new abilities and developing as economically and socially important individuals (Tsinidou et al., 2010; Kovbasyuk and Blessinger, 2013). The student's ongoing and ultimate change reflects the outcomes of their HE experiences in the form of their personal development (Gurukkal, 2018).

HE has a dual purpose in society since it must maintain its relevance. HE's fundamental value remains that it enriches and empowers students via the learning process (Harvey and Knight, 1996; Hadie et al., 2018), responding to society's changing needs while retaining a student-centred, consumer-oriented attitude (Rowan and Townend, 2017). Students becoming empowered consumers of education, with control over the educational processes and a desire to learn for the rest of their lives, is a goal of government policy for HE (Tan, 2017).

In conclusion, of the above discussion about the consequences of HE, it is evident that HEIs collaborate with businesses and the community to provide relevant and marketable courses of study that help students succeed in the workforce (Tan, 2017). Students need to be motivated

and actively involved in their learning if they are to provide the outcomes that stakeholders outside the HE environment need (Duje and Weeks, 2010). As a consequence of this, the personal growth of the students as a direct consequence of their HE, requires collaboration amongst a wide range of stakeholders (Abbas, 2020). A variety of different stakeholders are being successfully engaged in the improvement and realisation of desired results for HE.

2.10. Stakeholders

This section provides a review of the relevant literature in regard to the stakeholders in general as well as stakeholders in HE specifically. Along with discussing the most important stakeholders in HE, the stakeholders' theory and a broad definition of stakeholders are provided in this section. The first step in the direction of gaining a competitive advantage as an educational institution is the identification of key stakeholders for HEI. This step is also a fundamental step toward the identification of the needs of stakeholders and the establishment of the means to meet those needs (Alves et al., 2010). One of the most significant characteristics of competition for HEIs is to provide services that are tailored to the requirement of the many stakeholders (Dobni and Luffman, 2003).

2.10.1. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory's fundamental notion is that an organisation's degree of performance is partly determined by how it handles connections with key individuals and/or groups that are directly or indirectly connected with the organisation (Freeman, 1984; Friedman and Miles, 2006; Freeman et al., 2010). Stakeholder theory, in any framework, is concerned with stakeholders' vitality when they are concerned in an organisation's static or dynamic, possibly good or negative, character (Matlay, 2011; Freeman et al., 2010). Stakeholders have an impact on the opportunity recognition, innovation, and resource usage in a business and provide value to the institution (Dana, 2011).

The purpose of stakeholder theory is to understand the internal and external influences from many walks of life that may function for or against the organisation, which might directly or indirectly impact (Freeman, 1984). In the practical environment, these stakeholding groups can be evident or can become evident during the change process, like a change in the curriculum or academic program (Carmmond, 2018). It becomes essential to deal with the stakeholder in a time of crisis (Gibb and Haskins, 2014). The analysis of stakeholders and the adoption of a stakeholder management strategy involve considering the complex perspective of the value of

stakeholders, what they seek, and new and improved ways of stakeholders' measurement (McAdam et al., 2016). Different scholars have included different groups of stakeholders based on their relevance to the particular organisation. Customers, workers, management, investors, creditors, suppliers, the community, and sometimes even rivals appear to be among the stakeholders (Schilling, 2000).

Different stakeholders have different requirements and interests since an organisation has various stakeholders. If the organisation consider the interests and demands of all stakeholders, it will face several challenges, including cost increases, profit decreases, and even the question of existence, among others (Guo, 2018). Managing many relationships is a difficult task. Bryson (1995) stated that stakeholders must be considered throughout any strategic management process since the fulfilment of the organisation's objectives is contingent on key stakeholders being satisfied according to their view of what is valued. Based on internal and external changes in the corporate environment, Freeman (1984) divided stakeholders into two groups: internal and external. Internal stakeholders are those who are concerned about internal change, whereas external stakeholders are those who are concerned about outward change (Kumar et al., 2016).

Savage et al. (1991) proposed four techniques to manage diverse stakeholders based on their potential capacity to threaten or cooperate with the organisation and grouped them into four categories: supporting, marginal, non-supportive, and mixed-blessing. The supportive stakeholder group of stakeholders are more likely to collaborate and less likely to threaten the organisation, the marginal stakeholder group is less likely to cooperate or threaten the organisation, the non-supportive group of stakeholders is more likely to threaten the organisation and less likely to cooperate and the mixed-blessing group of stakeholder is more likely to threaten as well as cooperate with the organisation.

The Stakeholder Theory is very valuable to HEIs in explaining why they should pay attention to the many groups in the HEI's internal and external environment, as well as the relationship between an HEI and the groups (Jongbloed et al., 2008). It is also not that easy to identify and prioritise the HEI's stakeholders. Szawjkowski (2000) presented the guideline for HEI management to structure and develop the relationship among the HEIs and different stakeholder groups.

- Managers of the HEIs must be able to comprehend and manage the expectations of all HEI stakeholders, as well as take them into account when making choices.

- Managers of the HEIs should engage with stakeholder groups to determine their needs and contributions with respect to the HEI, as well as the risk they assume in this relationship with the HEI.
- Managers of the HEIs must act in ways that are responsive to the needs and capabilities of each stakeholder's group.
- Managers of the HEIs must recognise their interdependence with stakeholder groups and seek to equitably divide benefits while considering the risks and vulnerabilities that exist.
- Managers of the HEIs should seek out opportunities to cooperate with other public and private sector HEIs in order to reduce the risks associated with their HEI.

Stakeholders Theory enables the HEIs to understand their operating surroundings based on the realities that exist in the surroundings. This understanding leads to the improvement in the strategies for meeting the needs of various stakeholder groups. In the current economic situation and the level of competition in the market among HEIs, it is essential for the HEI managers to identify the key stakeholders and to develop a relationship of mutual benefit so that the perception of the quality of the service delivered by the HEIs can improve.

2.10.2. Definition Of Stakeholder

The concept of a stakeholder could be dated back to 1963 when it was presented by name in a Stanford Research Institute paper (Freeman, 1984). Since its inception, the stakeholder hypothesis has gotten a lot of attention (Guo, 2018). Several descriptions of stakeholders have emerged in a number of journal articles. Many stakeholder concepts have been proposed, even in academic circles. Stakeholders are individuals or groups with interest in the organisation or affirmation (Carroll, 1993, p.22; Chapleo and Simms, 2010), and they have been described in various ways by different researchers.

Stakeholders, according to Freeman, are any group or individual who can have an impact on how the organisation's goals are met (Freeman, 1984, p.46). This is the most widely used definition, which has been cited by many scholars and is considered the cornerstone for many other stakeholder definitions (Guo, 2018). Clarkson (1995), defined stakeholders as the constituents who are impacted (positively or negatively) by the organisation's actions, independent of how they are connected to the organisation. Stakeholders, according to Mercier (1999), are all the agents who are concerned about the firm's growth and well-being. Post et al. (2002, p.8) mentioned that individuals and constituencies who contribute freely or

involuntarily to wealth-creating capacities and activities and who are thus potential beneficiaries and/or risk bearers are referred to as stakeholders.

Even if the term "stakeholder" is defined differently by different people, most of them agree that organisations should consider the needs, interests, and impacts of persons and groups who are affected or may be affected by its strategies and procedures (Frederic et al., 1992; Guo, 2018). Individuals, organisations, informal groups, and institutions can all be stakeholders in this idea (Mainardes et al., 2011). Consumers, employees, managers, investors, creditors, suppliers, the government, and sometimes even competitors appear to be included in the stakeholders' list (Schilling, 2000).

The reason for this is that universities have a diverse set of stakeholders, and they must cater to a diverse set of internal and external stakeholders' requirements and desires. According to Bartell (2003), institutions can involve a wide range of internal stakeholders, including local and international undergraduates, graduates and professional students, and mid-career professionals looking for opportunities to continue their education. The surrounding community, the political authority, awarding and accreditation bodies, unions, and the media are all external stakeholders. Despite the fact that universities are different from other businesses in many respects, market share, productivity, return on investment and quality of service they provide are all important to them (LeBlanc and Nguyen, 1997; Trang et al., 2018). They will have to take management practices and models from business organisations. According to Drucker (1994), management is the specific organ of all organisations, and all organisations, whether they use the name or not, require management.

The previous areas of the literature revealed that there are several types of stakeholders, such as internal and external, primary and secondary (Freeman, 1984; Clarkson, 1995). HEIs, like any other, have a variety of stakeholders. They include students, teaching staff, corporate partners, the government, industry and the general public. They can be characterised as internal or external, individual or collective, and academic or non-academic (Hill et al., 2001; Longin, 2002; Jongbloed et al., 2008).

2.10.3. Stakeholders Of Higher Education

The focus of the service industry generally is on the customer while designing the service. Due to the complexity of HE services' nature, defining HE's customers becomes difficult because there it has many groups as stakeholders (Owlia, 1997). To manage the quality of HE services, it is important to satisfy all the stakeholder groups (Gift and Bell-Hutchinson, 2007).

Stakeholders' identification is essential for the HEIs not only to gain competitive advantages for the HEIs but also to understand the requirements of the stakeholders and put in place the strategy to address those requirements. Addressing the requirements of the stakeholder, individual, or group is a critical competitive component for the HEIs (Dobni and Luffman, 2003).

The stakeholder relationship with the HE services provider is vital from the quality perspective (Srikanthan and Dalrymple, 2002). Owlia (1997) identified students, parents of the students, employers, faculty members, government and general society as stakeholder groups of HE, with a variety of stakes adding to the complexity of HE systems. Quinn et al. (2009), identified students, parents, research supporters, government, potential employers of students, academic disciplinary communities, accreditation bodies and staff as the common stakeholder groups of HE. Rowley (1997) presented that being the primary consumer of HE services, students are the most critical stakeholders, and their role in the assessment of the service quality is distinct from every other group.

Telford and Masson (2005) identified stakeholders of HE as students, teaching and non-teaching staff and employers, government and financing institutions, accreditation bodies and the general community. The perspective of these stakeholders varies based on their own criteria. As mentioned, different scholars have identified stakeholders of HE internally and externally, and among them, the key stakeholders are those who affect or get affected by the process or the outcomes directly (Qureshi, 2012). The internal key stakeholders are considered as those who are directly receiving the service (students) and those who are directly providing the service (teaching and non-teaching staff). Other than these two, the third key stakeholder of the HE is the potential employers of the students or industry as they get a direct effect of the outcomes of HE (Hewitt and Clayton, 1999; Small et al., 2018).

In this research study, the emphasis is on the three key stakeholders, as identified by Hewitt and Clayton (1999), who do not underestimate the importance of other stakeholder groups. Significant discrepancies are discovered among the perspectives of HEI personnel and students, and other stakeholders. Differences in perception can occur as a result of students' and HEI personnel's differing perspectives of expectations and experiences (Qureshi, 2012). Student can be viewed as an HE customer or as a product for the employer who is, in this case, a customer (Guibault, 2016). In fact, defining the consumer in HE has long been a challenge (Cuthbert, 1996).

It is probable the fact that these three groups of stakeholders are mentioned the most in HE literature is due to a prevalent image of HEIs as industrial service providers (Teichler, 2004; OECD, 2010; Duarte et al., 2012; Rajah, 2014; Duarte et al., 2017). However, there is currently a scarcity of research on the many types of HE stakeholders. Several researchers have contributed to this study (Gift and Bell-Hutchinson, 2007; Marginson and Van der Wende, 2007; Nusche, 2008; Stodnick and Rogers, 2008; Duarte et al., 2012; Stukalina, 2012; Shams and Belyaeva, 2019) either make just broad mentions of the stakeholder groups or focus the study primarily on the students of HE.

2.10.3.1. Student's Perspective

The role of students in HE is complex and contested (Pitman, 2016) and a popular research area. Students who think of themselves as consumers are more likely to have attitudes and behaviour that are detrimental to their academic performance (Finney and Finney, 2010). Several teachers presume that they have a responsibility to assist in the education of pupils at the behest of and for the good of society as a whole (Weerasinghe and Fernando, 2017) and "challenge the common perception of the students as a consumer on the basis that HE is unlike other types of services supply" (Lomas, 2007, p. 42).

The influence of HE on students cannot be effectively measured until after it has been given; it is impossible to think of students as consumers (Abu-Amuna et al., 2017). The assumption that a student is always right and meeting his or her needs will be in the best interest of the institute is not a correct assumption (Carter and Yeo, 2016). The students-as-consumers is an ongoing debate, as it appears to function on the basis of a perspective that views education as a product, which is in direct opposition to established educational standards (Michael, 1997; Lomas, 2007; Weerasinghe and Fernando, 2017).

The concept of quality as the gap between the expectation of students and the perception they develop after the HE experiences is regarded as a valid and reliable indicator of HE quality (O'Neil and Palmer, 2004). In the services industry, the focus is on quality-oriented activities by the customer; in HE, the consideration of students as a customer has been questioned by many as if it is a suitable approach (Gibbs and Iacovidou, 2004). This approach has been resisted by many academic managers (Johnson and Deem, 2003). They are of the view that if students are treated as customers of HE, there is a need to articulate the student's needs carefully. This generates the need to redefine and clarify students' identity, rights and status

with respect to the teacher, and this can lead to tensions between management and staff (Zachariah, 2007).

There is a variety of perspectives about the student-as-customer prospect; therefore, a number of research scholars have developed a variety of frameworks to show the relationship of the student to the educator. These frameworks imply that both the student and the educator are significant stakeholders in HE (Degtarjova et al., 2018). Students have to be acknowledged as potential customers of professional services so that they may exert a greater amount of influence (Uppal et al., 2018). Ferris (2002) proposed that students need to be given the same rights and responsibilities as partners in a business partnership. He refers to this model as the “student as junior partner idea”. One alternate point of view is that a student may be compared to an employee and that the foundations of performance management as it is practised in workplace organisations can be transferred to the academic setting (Budur et al., 2018).

Some other models clearly seek to explain students' anticipated part and connection with professors in HE. The resistance to the concept of treating students as a customer of HE can root in the concerns that it legitimises all the student's demands which HEIs will have to cater for (Zachariah, 2007). The HE service is not a traditional transaction that involves the monetary payment for the services offered; even without consideration of all the related complexities, there is a consideration of the fact that HEIs have to be regulated by some standards for their awards which also include not rewarding the students whose eligibility does not meet the standards (Zachariah, 2007).

2.10.3.2. Staff's Perspective

It is critical to analyse HE delivery from an organisational standpoint. Organisational dynamics are vital for good service delivery, and a service production system is crucial for delivering high-quality service (Mader et al., 2013; Erasmus et al., 2015; Fazal et al., 2017). The management, academia, and administrative support staff members who work for HEIs jointly own the organisation's perception in connection to the functions of HEIs, as discussed earlier in this section. Observations have demonstrated that organisational processes have an impact on the overall HESQ (Zhu, 2015). It is possible that teaching and non-teaching staff do not have the same conception of what constitutes as high quality as their students, either in terms of the material covered or the manner in which it is presented (Dicker et al., 2019).

Along with the students, the faculty as academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs are contributors in the process and, similarly, recipients of its performance (Marshall, 2018). The perspective of service quality of HE service gets the impact of the service atmosphere in the organisation. This is because customers' impressions of the level of service they receive are frequently reflected in the internal functioning of an organisation in terms of service (Murmura and Bravi, 2018). The faculty's role in institutional governance defines HEIs, and there is evidence that they still have a significant impact, particularly in areas related to teaching (Kaplan, 2004). The faculty, individually or collectively, make the bulk of choices on the operational and pedagogical framework of instruction. Faculty determine whether students have displayed the attributes required of graduates and are mostly accountable for graduating students' capacity to satisfy societal standards (Marshall, 2018).

Academic faculty, like HEIs, are undergoing significant changes in the nature of their roles (Finney and Finney, 2010). Changes in expectations from a rising student body, political pressure (Knott, 2016), instructional burdens, and the responsibilities associated with the increased procedures of management and accountability progressively characterising modern institutes are among the challenges they face. This definition of "teaching to expectations" makes no allowance for the possibility that the instructor does not seek to fulfil the students' expectations but rather to modify those expectations, as well as the student's intellect, character, and sensibility in general (Trow, 1994). For academics, as it does for many other professionals, this entails the way technology blurs the already fragile boundaries between work and other aspects of life (Gregg, 2011; Abbas, 2020).

Non-teaching employees at HEIs form a distinct and robust community, frequently functioning in the form of a corresponding structure to that of the faculty. The distinction between teaching and non-teaching staff is well-known inside HEIs, but the function of non-teaching staff is less well-known in the literature, and their effect is so significant that they are referred to as "invisible" (Szekeres, 2011). The non-teaching personnel of HEIs is further subdivided into a variety of administrative activities, with silos typically forming depending on functional responsibilities and vocations. These many groups, which include administration, library personnel, information technology professionals, marketing, legal compliance, and student recruiting, all have distinct viewpoints on the institution and have diverse beliefs and goals (Marshall, 2018). In this study, the organisational perspective was represented by the academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs.

2.10.3.3. Industry's Perspective

One of the most important groups of stakeholders for HE is the industry due to the consumerist role it plays in the employment of students either after they have completed their education or while they are still in HEIs (Trunina et al., 2019). When it comes to the provision of service to students that are in line with the requirements and expectations of the industry, the business world is seen by HEIs as a useful partner (Tan, 2017). The provision of opportunities for personal development and upgrading of skills is one way in which the industry may continue to play a part in the student's overall growth as individuals (Rajah, 2014; Tan, 2015). Although it is generally acknowledged that the employer or industry does not want to interfere with the academic community's autonomy in any way, it does make demands and expectations on academics.

Evaluation of the quality of HE offered by HEIs to their students should make use of industry requirements as a valuable benchmark (Savga et al., 2018). The industry looks HEIs to provide trained workers as this is a requirement for the industry in order to run and manage business activities amidst a constantly shifting industrial environment, as well as for the purpose of conducting an active review of student learning and development as an outcome of their HEE (Dicker et al., 2019).

Graduates' job success is one conventional measure of educational achievement used by institutions in many nations, a metric determined by governments worried about short-term unemployment in the period of an economic slump causing more significant political strife and societal disruption. As a result of their interaction with sympathetic government organisations responsible for financing and reporting on university performance, companies may increasingly dictate portions of educational programmes (Marshall, 2018). Employers' expectations of institutions are increasingly framed by quality management techniques like using employer-determined graduate qualities and surveys (Shah et al., 2015). Employability and company demands are becoming increasingly important, as seen by the rise of work-integrated learning (Smith, 2016). Work-integrated education is considered a better approach as compared to genuine learning and practice-based learning to guarantee that the curriculum, course material and activities, and the direct continuing experience of employment are all fully linked (Smith, 2012). In this study, the industry perspective was represented by industry professionals.

2.11. Research Gap

The review of research in the areas of services marketing, service quality, HE and stakeholders exposed gaps in the existing literature that need to be filled. The study's goal and perspective are justified by the research gaps. HE as a service is a well-known concept, but its implications for students' personal development as a result of their HEEs have yet to be investigated in Pakistan. HEIs face a more difficult task of creating a balance between service marketing and academic independence (Michael, 1997; Gibbons, 1998). As a result, it's critical to understand how market-driven interventions like service quality and student experience affect a student's personal development.

The majority of research on the HESQ has been undertaken from the prospect of students, who are viewed as the clients of HE (Darlaston-Jones, 2003). Organisational and industrial views, on the other hand, must be addressed (Reynoso and Moores, 1995; Michael, 1997; Schneider and White, 2004; Naidoo et al., 2011). In the HE sector, Saleem et al. (2017) did a research study on service quality and student satisfaction. The study was only focused on the student's point of view. They proposed that research be performed in the context of Pakistani HEIs to examine the perspectives of various stakeholders, including academic and non-academic HEI staff. The procedural variables of service quality are examined in this study via the lens of student experiences. Both the organisational and industrial perspectives contribute to a broader understanding of HE as a service and its influence on students' personal development as a result of their participation in it.

There is a scarcity of studies on the quality of HEI service in Pakistan (Qureshi, 2012). The majority of the existing literature on service quality in HE comes from the perspective of other countries. The existing research in the field of service quality is institution or field-specific, and there is a gap for a study encompassing multiple fields and institutions. It is aimed that by conducting the study in the setting of Pakistan, the researcher will be able to get a more accurate image of the standard of HESQ. The research has been conducted in the area of service quality concerning the stakeholder's perspective but mainly from the perspective of HE students and addressing different angles of the student's perspective of the quality of service provided by HEIs (Abdullah, 2006a; Teervoovengadum et al., 2016), other stakeholders are of prime importance as well. These include teachers (De Jager and Gbadamosi, 2013) and potential employers (Senthilkumar and Arulraj, 2011).

The research is scarce, specifically in the Pakistani context, providing the perspective of the three key stakeholders of HE as the students, academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs and the industry. The academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs add to the student's experience in the form of valuable knowledge and service experience (Latif et al., 2017) that impacts their personal development during and after completing their education. The potential employers are concerned with developing competencies due to education experience to be according to the needs of the industry (Martensen and Grohholdt, 2009). Teeroovengadam et al. (2016), suggested that the research studies should also consider other HE stakeholders' perspectives. In the assessment of HESQ, other stakeholders should be included (Rodman et al., 2013). There are some research studies conducted in the field of stakeholder perception in other countries, but there are minimal studies conducted in Pakistan's context. The studies conducted in Pakistan are limited to a specific institute or are mostly limited to management and business departments.

2.12. Chapter Summary

There has been a consistent increase in the share of the economy that is devoted to service-related occupations in every industrialised nation throughout the world. The literature on service marketing states that at all times, the client is a co-producer of the service, actively participating in the production process that results in value creation after the consumer's use of the product or services. The evolution of service definition is by a list of service definitions presented in chronological order. Service quality may be thought of as an evaluation of a service's overall quality. The degree to which a service provider meets the specific requirements of each individual consumer is an indicator of the quality of the service provided. An examination of the theoretical connections between various service qualities is made possible by studying the dimensional aspects of service quality. Dimensions of service quality measurements are essential for any assessment of service quality. It is important to consider not just how consumers feel about certain aspects of a service but also how they feel about the service as a whole when assessing its quality.

HE is a powerful instrument for forming individual character and societal and national character, and its quality has a direct and indirect influence on the development of emerging countries. Students use the ratings of HEIs to compare them with other HEIs. Quality management at the HEIs level, as well as quality assurance and certification system at the national, provincial and international levels, are all relevant in this comparison. Students, regardless of this background, look to the HECF ranking as a representation of a HEIs quality

before deciding whether or not to attend. In the service marketing literature, the concept of HE as a service is quite common. The quality of the education service is an ongoing process that can be improved over time. HEIs have the opportunity to constantly upgrade their service for the same customers, giving them ample time to boost the level of service they deliver. An approach to quality that places clients at the centre may provide a one-of-a-kind experience for the students, which can then contribute to their personal development.

HEIs are obliged to demonstrate to various stakeholders as being responsive to their needs and want. From a quality point of view, the connection between the HE service provider and the many stakeholders is essential. It is required of HEIs to provide data to back up their claims of excellence and efficacy; stakeholders want HEIs to do precisely that. Because they have different requirements, each stakeholder in HE has a separate point of view on what constitutes excellence. It is possible for there to be disparities in perception as a consequence of the various view that students, HEI staff and industry have about their expectations and experiences.

Chapter 3: Research Framework

3.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the proposed model that is based on the theories of service quality to test the proposed linkages that provide answers for the first and second questions of this research study that were outlined in Chapter 1. The model also provides the base for exploring the difference in the perception of stakeholders of HE in Pakistan. This chapter presents the building of the conceptual model, comprising the many components of the HE service quality, student experience, student satisfaction, student's personal development as an outcome of the HEE and stakeholders. The model that is presented here is a modification of the model that was presented by Tan (2017) to investigate the effect that the quality of the service has on the learning outcomes of HE. Within the scope of this study, the conceptual model investigates how the HESQ contributes to the student experience and the personal development that follows as a direct consequence of this connection.

3.2. Conceptual Model

The model presented below is the adaption of the model that was previously presented by Tan (2017) for the purpose of analysing the impact of the quality of service on the learning outcomes of students attending HEIs in Singapore. Even though Tan (2017) had not yet been published at the time of adoption, it was recognised as a legitimate piece of research. At the very least as credible as a publication, providing that it has been peer-reviewed and defended in the viva examination. Therefore, it is legitimate to adopt the model for this research study conducted in Pakistan. The adopted model and the instrument designed based on this model incorporates the whole experience of HE service, beginning with searching for the HEI and ending with the completion of the degree program.

The study conducted by Tan (2017) was a quantitative study conducted in Singapore, where all the participants of the study filled in questionnaires to provide their perspectives. For this study, the model was adopted for a research to be conducted in Pakistan, where one group of stakeholders participated using an online questionnaire, and the other two groups were

interviewed. The questionnaire for this study was designed to encompass all aspects of the student's experience with HE service, from searching for an institute to experiencing service to the level of recommending or not recommending to family and friends. For the questionnaire, some of the items were adopted from the instrument used by Tan (2017), which were matching with the flow of the questionnaire designed for this study. Some of the new items were added to encompass the overall experience of a HE student in Pakistan. There are a total of 45 items in the instrument designed for the quantitative part of this study. Out of the 45 items, 18 were used from Tan (2017). Along with the statements, 6 open-ended questions were also included, one in each of the 5 sections of the questionnaire, so the participants could express their opinion about any aspect which is not covered in the statements of that section. A more detailed step-by-step description of the instrument design process is presented in Chapter 4.

The proposed linkages among the factors of service quality on student satisfaction with the HEE and the resultant personal development are represented visually in the model that was suggested, which represents the theories in a way that reflects a visual representation of those propositions. The conceptual model that has been presented is depicted in figure 3.1. Within the context of this model, the five dimensions of service quality reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness were considered to be the independent variable, while student satisfaction from the HEE was considered as moderating variable, and personal development was considered to be the dependent variable.

HE outcome or personal development encompasses a variety of student characteristics and skills that are indicative of a student's growth due to their HEEs. The term "results of HE" is frequently used to refer to institutional outcomes and performances that ignore students' growth due to their HEEs (Frye, 1999). HE learning outcomes can be defined as a student's personal development, having both cognitive and affective development, as discussed in the literature review. There are two proposed relationships suggested in the conceptual model of this study. SERVQUAL dimensions can be employed in the proposed conceptual model because SERVQUAL was established via research in many different sectors of the industry, as a result, of evaluation of service quality both at the organisational and industrial levels (Parasuraman et al., 1985,1988,1994). Also SERVQUAL is most widely used in service quality research in HE sector.

Figure 3.1: Proposed Conceptual Model

3.2.1. Aspects Of Service Quality And Student Experience

The impact of service quality has been extensively researched in a variety of services-providing organisations and sectors of industry, including the hotel sector (Hartono and Raharjo, 2015), retailing sector (Ladhari, 2009; Hartono and Raharjo, 2015) finance service sector (Caruana, 2002; Shanka, 2012) and other specialised service sectors of the industries (Sharma and Patterson, 1999; Cameran et al., 2010). In the research area of HE, there are numerous studies that are similar; for example, Sultan and Wong (2012) have looked into a beneficial association of service quality and its effects, which included student happiness, trust, and image.

The majority of research on student success in HEIs has concentrated on the mechanism of course delivery and the quality of teaching (Silva et al., 2017), and only a small amount of attention has been paid to identifying the comprehensive aspects of student success in HEIs through the use of a holistic approach (Abbas, 2020). As a result of this, the creation of a complete instrument that assesses service quality, particularly in HEIs, by taking into consideration both technical and operational aspects remains a significant obstacle (Ali et al.,

2016). In the context of HEIs, operational quality refers to the amenities, both quantifiable and unquantifiable, that are made accessible to students while they are enrolled at the university. It also focuses on how such amenities were made available to them. The term technical quality refers to the extent to which an educational establishment trains its students in accordance with the industry's requirements so that after they have graduated, they are capable of performing well in that sector.

HE performance metrics, such as student satisfaction, may be negatively impacted because nearly every process requires human interaction (Li et al., 2019). This enhances the likelihood of a negative service quality experience occurring over the course of the years it takes to complete a degree (Chandra et al., 2018; Aleu et al., 2021). Purgailis and Zaksa (2012) conducted another investigation about the favourable impact of perceived service quality on student satisfaction, image and loyalty towards the HEI, and the results were presented. Alves and Raposo (2007) presented a conceptual model and tested it for student satisfaction due to the perception of the HESQ. Tan (2017) presented a conceptual model and tested it for the impact of HESQ learning outcomes. Regardless of the industry's sector, the concept of customer satisfaction and how it is associated with the perception of service quality has been a recurring theme in these studies.

In HE, the quality of tangible assets is frequently used to assess service quality along with the student's perceptions of responsiveness, reliability, empathy, and assurance, as well as the resources made available (Parasuraman et al., 1988, Sultan and Wong, 2019). These aspects are drawn from the SERVQUAL model, something that, due to its comprehensiveness of service dimensions, serves as a useful baseline for the quality of service models (Buttle, 1996). Service quality is often referred to as the perception of the total quality of service and its effect on the student experience leading to satisfaction; it is quite possible that the aspects of service quality have a relationship with student experience (Schneider and white, 2004) and the personal development of students due to their experience. Based on the discussion following proposition was assumed which will aid in answering the first research question.

P1: Aspects of HESQ have a positive effect on the student's experiences.

3.2.2. Student Satisfaction From HESQ Experience And Personal Development

Previous studies have shown that clients are happier as a result of receiving services of a higher grade (Annamdevula and Bellamkonda, 2016). The evaluation of the experience that students have had with educational services gives rise to an attitude that might be characterised as

student satisfaction (Latif et al., 2021). Better perceived service quality is linked to greater student satisfaction, according to a number of research studies (Fernandes et al., 2013). Students regularly assess the level of service provided by their HEI. They evaluate the HEI's tuition costs, educational services provided, and physical attributes, including the infrastructure's technical and functional excellence, interactions with academic and administrative staff, corporate image and reputation, among other things (Camilleri, 2021). It is critical for the HEI to consider these aspects of service to improve student satisfaction with the service.

Satisfaction is referred to as the apparent difference between the consumer's prior expectations and the actual performance after the consumption (Tse and Peter, 1988; Meesala and Paul, 2018). Elliott and Shin (2002) presented the concept that the level of satisfaction felt by students consistently fluctuates, which is a reflection of the cumulative experiences of all students is sequentially interlaced. Despite the narrow scope of the debates, the HE and student progress literature encompasses research on the factors that influence HE outcomes (Bae, 2007). The causes for the existence of these disciplines may be deduced by conducting a review of literature about the importance of teaching, learning, and student engagement elements of HE on student personal development in HE and student development literature. One of the reasons is that it is necessary to characterise the student's satisfactory or non-satisfactory experience using HE characteristics, as these characteristics are critical in determining the quality of HE (Harvey and Knight, 1996; Douglas et al., 2006; Sharabi, 2013).

Service quality and customer satisfaction from the experience and the resultant personal development are terms that are essentially distinct from one another yet are positively associated (Abbas, 2020). The higher the quality of the service provided by the HEI, the greater the level of satisfaction of the students from experience (Galeeva, 2016). Mahmood et al. (2014), discovered that students' level of desire to study was positively correlated with the degree to which they were satisfied with the quality of the service they received and the level of their personal development as a result of the HE service. Students will be more encouraged to actively participate in the learning phase if they are happy with the quality of the service they experience during their course (Jupiter et al., 2017).

It is necessary to collect feedback from students in order to improve the understanding of the extent to which students get satisfaction from their HEEs (Alderman et al., 2012; Vasudevan, 2021). HE is a service that is received by the students in order to improve them; consequently,

students' personal development or the qualities and capabilities that student gain due to HE are the best indicators of the quality of HE (Sharipov, 2020). As a consequence of the student's satisfaction and experience, measures may be used to explore the influence of the quality of the student's HE service on the individual development of the student (Harvey and Knight, 1996; Shin, 2017). Therefore it is reasonable to argue that:

P2: Student satisfaction from the HESQ experience has a positive influence on their personal development.

3.3. Concept Development

Following the proposition development, this section presents the theoretic and operationalised descriptions of the aspects used in the conceptual model. A brief discussion is presented about all the constructs as an attempt to justify the construct in the model arrangement.

3.3.1. Tangibles

The tangibles aspects are referred to as the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials (Akhlaghi et al., 2012). According to Setiono and Hidayat (2022), the tangibles are a dimension of service quality that incorporates physical evidence such as the appearance of the physical environment, the ease of equipment and resources provided, the appearance of teaching and non-teaching employees and the communication system. Businesses use tangibles to increase customer satisfaction because they are observable and tangible aspects of a service that can be felt by the receivers of the service (Yousoff et al., 2015). In the service industry, strategies where clients are present and tangibles are frequently emphasised in order to project a positive perception and communicate quality to the clients (Zeithaml et al., 2009). Tangibles are one of the possible aspects of service quality; physical facilities, equipment, and physical appearances are all common aspects of the tangible aspects of the facilities. Equipment and physical outlook are used by different businesses to promote consumer happiness (Yousoff et al., 2015; Pakurar et al., 2019).

In the HE industry, learning spaces like classrooms, library resources, etc., are helpful in educating students and also vital aspects of the physical facility (Teeroovengadam et al., 2016). Learning resources, such as technological equipment, access to databases etc., should be up-to-date and appealing to the eye (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Ardi et al., 2012). Aside from outward appearances, the learning environment should convey a sense of expertise,

confidence, and professionalism, as well as be consistent with the services provided to students (Douglas et al., 2006). As a result, the tangibles construct can be operationalised using the measurement items listed in Table 3.1: Statement of tangibles construct.

Table 3.1: Statements Of Tangibles Construct

Statements		References
1	There are sufficient facilities in the class/lecture rooms.	Parasuraman et al. (1988); Min et al., (2012)
2	There are sufficient learning resources in the university according to your course.	Parasuraman et al. (1988); Ardi et al., (2012)
3	The learning environment conveys a sense of competence and professionalism.	Parasuraman et al. (1988); Min et al., (2012)

3.3.2. Assurance

Within the realm of business and management research, assurance is generally related to the impression of sustainable and quality management (Barnabe and Riccabonni, 2007; Rashid et al., 2009; Teeroovengadum et al., 2016; Tan, 2017). Assurance refers to the activities and procedures used to monitor and ensure that performance and quality meet a predetermined standard, with the goal of ensuring corporate quality and long-term viability. (Barnabe and Riccabonni, 2007; Yousapronpaiboon, 2014; Pakurar et al., 2019). It is the skill, civility and trustworthiness of the provider. Organisation assurance is the ability to provide good assurance to its consumers if the organisation can provide a sense of security for its consumers, provide the discretion of consumer data and be able to deliver professional service for consumers (Natalisa, 2008; Setiono and Hidayat, 2022).

The notions of assurance, trust, confidence, and credibility are all linked (Tan, 2017). If there is no trust and confidence, assurance loses its credibility, according to Dando and Swift (2003). In the literature on service quality, assurance is described as service personnel's expertise and politeness, as well as their capacity to build trust and confidence in people (Ong, 2012). When HEI's staff members are open and honest with students, and complete information is provided, trust and confidence are built, encouraging pupils to feel comfortable

with them in their interactions (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Stukalina, 2012). Based on this discussion, assurance is one of the possible dimensions of service quality. Table 3.2 presents the measurement statements that were used to formulate the assurance concept.

Table 3.2: Statements Of Assurance Construct

Statements		References
1	University's website provides complete information for decision-making.	Douglas et al. (2006); Sultan and Wong (2011)
2	The induction was helpful in knowing the whereabouts of the university.	Parasuraman et al. (1988)
3	The institute's communication network is up-to-date and efficient.	Sultan and Wong, (2011); Min et al. (2012)
4	The institute encourages confidence in students.	Parasuraman et al. (1988)

3.3.3. Reliability

Reliability is referred to as the ability to perform services precisely and reliably (Sardar et al., 2016). Yarimoglu (2014) mentioned that reliability is the "consistency of performance and dependability, accuracy in billing, keeping records correctly, performing the service right at the designated time". The similarity or repeatability of test or event results, observations, or actions is referred to as reliability in psychology and social sciences (Thissen, 2000; Delice, 2010). According to Natalisa (2008), one of the indicators that reveal that a firm is reliable is the precision with which the customers are handled. Reliability can be summarised as the characteristics of service quality that relate to a company's capacity to deliver the agreed service promptly (Setiono and Hidayat, 2022).

Reliability in the field of quality sciences, is a term used to describe a product's or service's ability to withstand external variables that could affect its performance while in use (Zhao and Gallant, 2012). The skills of the individual providing service consistently and precisely are defined as reliability in the literature on service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1985). Reliability in HE primarily relates to the suitability and usefulness of initiatives for students (Teervoovengadam et al., 2016). As discussed, one possible dimension of service quality is

reliability. According to the concept of the definitions in the above paragraphs, correctness, dependence, and relevancy are prevalent themes in reliability definitions. In HE, accuracy is achieved when faculty members use consistent teaching methods. The provision of service is considered against the monetary elements attached (Min et al., 2012) and based on their experience, students will recommend the institute to their friends and family (Min et al., 2012). Based on the discussion, Table 3.3 presents the statements for the reliability construct.

Table 3.3: Statements Of Reliability Construct

Statements		References
1	Teaching staff are consistent in the way they teach.	Douglas et al. (2006); Duque and Weeks (2010)
2	Teaching staff are skilful and competent in what they teach.	Parasuraman et al. (1988); Min et al. (2012)
3	The overall service provided by the university is a good value for the fee.	Min et al. (2012)
4	You will recommend this university to your friends and family.	Min et al. (2012)

3.3.4. Empathy

Empathy is about the relationship and communication between the service provider and the receiver. It is required of the service provider to have an insight and knowledge of their service receivers, to comprehend the particular desires and requirements of their clients and to deliver pleasant service times (Setiono and Hidayat, 2022). Empathy is a vital behaviour and emotion that service-providing individuals demonstrate to customers (Pakurar et al., 2019). Empathy is a multifaceted concept that includes the capability to feel and share other people's emotions, as well as the ability to understand what they are going through (Ang and Goh, 2010; Zembylas, 2012). According to Yarimoglu (2014), empathy is politeness, respect, regard, approachability of the contact person, consideration for the customer, and clean and neat appearance of public contact personnel.

Customers, particularly in service industries, where significant customer interactions and relationship building are important aspects of the process (Malik et al., 2010). Customers want to be understood; therefore, empathy's purpose is to show them that they are special and that their requirements are taken seriously (Zeithaml et al., 2009). Empathy entails sharing the customer's perceived emotion in such a way that the service provider and the customer's emotional states are synchronised in order to achieve this (Eisenberg and Strayer, 1990). As discussed, one of the possible components of service excellence, as well as of HESQ, is Empathy. The attention and educational opportunities offered to the students by the HEI are directly tied to the institution's capacity for empathy (Setiono and Hidayat, 2022).

In the context of HE, there are a variety of ways to provide Empathy. It is demonstrated when staff workers show concern and care for the students and are aware of their needs (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Douglas et al., 2006; Jain et al., 2011). Staff members in an empathic educational setup respect students' feelings, concerns, and ideas (Sharabi, 2013). It is an important factor in determining teaching quality in HE (Ramsden, 1991). Giving students sympathy and comfort when they are experiencing problems promotes trust and confidence (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Douglas et al., 2006). The customised attention students receive from faculty in the learning process is of greater value to students, who are the primary beneficiaries of HE services. (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Min et al., 2012). Based on the discussion, the statements given in Table 3.4 can be used to operationalise the empathy concept.

Table 3.4: Statements Of Empathy Construct

Statements		References
1	Professors/lecturers are available to provide guidance other than the lecture times.	Douglas et al. (2006)
2	The staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems.	Parasuraman et al. (1988)
3	Students feel safe in their interaction with staff members.	Parasuraman et al. (1988)

3.3.5. Responsiveness

According to Malik et al. (2010), responsiveness refers to an institution's system's ability to respond quickly and efficiently. It explains how responsive the system is to the provision of quality service. It is the preparedness or enthusiasm of an employee to provide service, timelines of service and giving quick service (Yarimoglu, 2014). The term "responsiveness" is most commonly used in the context of services to describe a service provider's willingness and promptness in assisting clients (Tsinidou et al., 2010). It is all about being attentive and prompt when it comes to responding to client requests, complaints and inquiries (Pakurar et al., 2019).

A high level of responsiveness indicates that a business provides its customers with a well-defined range of options, a short wait time, prompt attention, and thorough and accurate information (Setiono and Hidayat, 2022). Responsiveness is a complex term (Tan, 2017). The customer expects a range of wants to be addressed in a minimal feasible period and in an efficient way; therefore, variety and lead time are two significant factors (Williamson, 1991). Service providers can retain 'closeness' with consumers by being responsive, increasing market competitiveness and sensitivity to client satisfaction (Gay and Salaman, 1992). Responsiveness is also one of the key measures of service quality.

Students want HEI staff members to be responsive, which is one of the most important qualities they look for. The teaching staff's responsiveness is apparent in their excitement and delivery manner (Teeroovengadum et al., 2016). It is expected that the students that will get a timely response to their requests (Tan, 2017). The will to assist students should also be shown by the staff of the HEI (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Min et al., 2012). The convenience of operating hours of student services is also an important aspect of responsiveness (Parasuraman et al., 1988). There is a sense of dependability if the services are readily available to the students (Parasuraman et al., 1998; Min et al., 2012). The statements listed in Table 3.5 can be used to operationalise the responsiveness concept.

Table 3.5: Statements Of Responsiveness Construct

Statements		References
1	The administrative staff is efficient and supportive.	Parasuraman et al. (1988); Min et al. (2012)

2	Student services are readily available and delivered on time.	Parasuraman et al. (1988); Min et al. (2012)
3	Operating hours of student services are convenient for students.	Parasuraman et al. (1988)

3.3.6. Student Experience

The term customer experience means to the sum of the total of a customer's encounters with the provider of products or services, taking into account the customer's perception of the company and the products or services in question (Ameen et al., 2021). The term "quality of experience" characterises both consumer and service encounters (Otto and Ritchie, 1996; Jain et al., 2011). The feelings and attitudes evoked when utilising a product or service are referred to as the consuming experience (Westbrook and Oliver, 1991; Baron et al., 2018). Fantasy, sensations, and fun are components of a typical hedonic emotional response (Otto and Ritchie, 1996; Kao et al., 2008; Govender and Ramroop, 2012).

The quality of service provided in the field of education is not the same as that provided in the field of manufacturing, which deals with physical objects. In addition to this, it is distinct from services, which often include just a single transaction that determines the overall value of the service (Latif et al., 2017; Mattah et al., 2018). Given that there is not really a product being sold in the education industry, the only way to differentiate oneself from the competition is by developing and offering a distinct service experience to students (Khodayari and Khodayari, 2011; Del Carmen Arrieta and Avolio, 2020).

The quality of experience is measured by the feelings that are evoked by the interaction with the service provider (Hosany et al., 2022). A positive experience is often connected with ideas and emotions relating to pleasure, involvement and fun (Chaney et al., 2018). Emotions and experiencing aspects are responsible for a significant part of contentment, which is governed by the calibre of an individual's whole experience (Bueno et al., 2019). The term social components of the student experience refer to the effect that other individuals, such student's family, friends, class fellows and broader social network, have on the student's overall experience (Ameen et al., 2021). A student's social identity, as well as the mental identity that corresponds to how they see themselves, might be considered social aspects (Keiningham et al., 2017).

When students think that their best interests are being addressed and that the benefit, they get are proportionate with the work that they put in, they have a sense that they are being recognised and engaged in the learning process (Otto and Ritchie, 1995; Douglas et al., 2006; Tan et al., 2016). Physiological experiences are a term that describes the feelings of joy that students feel as a result of their HE (De Rojas and Camarero, 2008; Tan, 2017). Because of the participatory nature of HE, a student’s feeling of engagement in the process contributes to an increase in the overall quality of their educational experience (Kao et al., 2008; Staddon and Standish, 2012). Providing students with a sense of their own identity may also enhance the overall quality of their educational experience (Standdon and Standish, 2012). Finally, there is a feeling of expectation, and it is possible to be empowered through the process of obtaining a HE when there is both a sense of anticipation and intellectual challenge (Peterson and Miller, 2004; Shin, 2017). The statements that could be used to evaluate the quality of student experience are outlined in Table 3.7.

Table 3.6: Statements Of Experience Construct

Statements		References
1	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling that my best interests are being served.	Otto and Richie (1995); Douglas et al. (2006)
2	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling that the rewards gained are consistent with the effort I put into the assessment/exams.	Otto and Richie (1995); Douglas et al. (2006)
3	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of enjoyment with the education experience.	Mano and Oliver (1993); DeRojas and Camaro (2008)
4	I feel involved with the HEI I am attending.	Otto and Richie (1995); Peterson and Miller (2004)
5	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of uniqueness of being associated with it.	Kao et al. (2008)

6	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of anticipation and being challenged intellectually.	Otto and Richie (1995); DeRojas and Camaro (2008)
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3.3.7. Student Satisfaction

A person's level of satisfaction with a product or service might be either high or low depending on how well the product or service met or fell short of that people's expectations (Nasse, 2022). Experts have generally agreed that customer satisfaction may be defined as the degree to which actual performance or outcome meets or exceed those anticipated by the customer (Setiono and Hidayat, 2022). If the actual results fall short of the customer's expectations, they will be dissatisfied or even angry; if they are on par with those expectations, they will be satisfied; if they exceed those expectations, they will be extremely satisfied (Kotler, 2009; Nasse, 2019).

Empirical studies show that service quality is a significant predictor of customer satisfaction (Wu, 2014). In the context of HE, a number of research have investigated the connection between the quality of service provided and the level of satisfaction felt by students, and they have found evidence to support the hypothesis (Dericks et al., 2019). According to Elliott and Shim (2002), student satisfaction is referred to the favourability of a student's subjective assessment of the several outcomes and experiences linked with education. Student satisfaction, like customer satisfaction, is a notion that is theoretically connected to perceived service quality but is different. There is also a paradox regarding the relation between student satisfaction and the experience of service quality (Tan, 2017). Student satisfaction is widely agreed to be a result of service quality (Schneider and White, 2004; Stukalina, 2012).

Student satisfaction HE is significantly achieved by service quality (Alves and Raposo, 2010). Growing regional, national and global competition among HEIs has accelerated recognition of the idea that students are the main client (Yildiz and Kara, 2009). As a result, universities must develop the means to satisfy their students at this level of education, which is accomplished by raising the standard of service they provide (Ramirez-Hurtado, 2021). Student satisfaction is achieved when student expectations are realised, whereas student happiness is derived from the concept of considering students as customers. While a student's rating of the educational experience is dependent on the quality of service delivered, student

happiness is based on the emotional impact of the educational experience. (Schneider and White, 2004) and refers to the level of enjoyment experienced by students when evaluating service attributes (Sultan and Wong, 2014).

A person's level of satisfaction is determined by whether or not the results meet his or her expectations (Kotler and Clarke, 1987). According to Palacio et al. (2002), in the HE industry, students' expectations begin to rise far before they reach a university. Carey et al. (2002), on the other hand, feel that students' perceptions are formed during their university years (AbuHasan et al., 2008). According to Vo (2021), Student satisfaction refers to an individual's attitude towards their subjective assessment of the learning outcomes and experiences they have had. They asserted that students' satisfaction fluctuated continually, representing the sum of students' experiences, including related and succeeding ones (Elliot and Shin, 2002). With rising competition, it is more crucial than ever for institutions to understand students' expectations since they are growing more demanding and precise in their choice of university for their HE (Sukwadi et al., 2011).

Sahney et al. (2004), mentioned that customers of HEIs may be categorised as internal and external. According to prominent quality management scholars in the HE industry, the academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs are the internal customers, whereas students are external customers (Khalid et al., 2019). The satisfaction of external customers is determined by the quality of service provided to internal customers (Hogreve et al., 2017). HEIs are focusing on understanding the factors that influence student satisfaction as well as attempting to improve it (Yusoff et al., 2015; Ramzi et al., 2022). The ability to influence education results by creating a student-centric educational setting depends on an analysis of how the student feels about the educational services, which can be accomplished through periodic feedback from students (Jalali et al., 2011; Stukalina, 2012). In order to manage student satisfaction, it is critical to identify the aspects that influence their satisfaction (Tan, 2017). The course format, course content, feedback system and assessments, and administrative services have all been demonstrated to influence student satisfaction. (Husain et al., 2009).

In order to manage student satisfaction, the results of student satisfaction surveys must be thoroughly comprehended and assessed for relevance and significance. Student satisfaction scores, according to the study, must not be taken literally and should be scrutinised further (Tan, 2017). Students' unrealistic expectations of HE may be to blame for the service gap and hence low satisfaction (Darlaston-Jones et al., 2003). Significant differences in students' and

educators' and other stakeholders' perceptions of the quality of education service delivery have been observed, with professionals evaluating service quality higher than students (Jones and Lee, 2011).

Polling students on all aspects of their academic careers are typically used to measure student happiness (Douglas et al., 2006). The term "satisfaction measurement" refers to determining "how I feel" about service after it has been obtained and consumed (Schneider and White, 2004). Feelings about an HEI's ability to meet a student's HE expectations may be expressed (De Rojas and Camerero, 2008; Duque and Weeks, 2010). Feelings about the overall HEE can also be conveyed (De Rojas and Camerero, 2008; Barnhardt and Ginns, 2014). Another technique to operationalise and measure the satisfaction construct is to look at overall satisfaction (De Rojas and Camarero, 2008). Garbarino and Johnson (1999) take it a step further by comparing service providers in their evaluation of total satisfaction. The following Table 3.7 provides a list of the possible measurement statements of student satisfaction from experience.

Table 3.7: Statements Of Satisfaction Construct

Statements		References
1	The first impression of the HEI met your expectations.	DeRajos and Camaro (2008)
2	The HEI is meeting your expectations of higher education learning.	DeRajos and Camaro (2008)
3	The HEI is meeting your overall expectations.	DeRajos and Camaro (2008)

3.3.8. Personal Development

In addition to academic performance and advancement, students are expected to gain or enhance particular skills and competencies relevant to their course as a consequence of their HEE (Abbot, 2021). Students' personal development as a consequence of their HEE supports them in finding suitable career options and advancing in their careers upon graduation (Audunsson et al., 2020). Personal development is one of the most important outcomes of a HEE. The affective outcomes of HE examines how the learning environment facilitates students' growth and include proof of the particular knowledge and skill gained throughout the

learning process (Nusche, 2008; Toropova et al., 2019). Cognitive learning, on the other hand, is centred on information and its practical use (Shaphard, 2008). The intellectual and practical skills one acquires while studying at university are collectively referred to as knowledge (Tan, 2017). The recognition of the complementary nature of implicit and explicit kinds of knowledge produces both (Simsek, 2020). According to previous research, students may show that they have the necessary general and professional skills for the job after graduation by doing well in practical exercises (Crayford et al., 2012; Tymon, 2013; Abbot, 2021).

Some of the HEIs are focused on emotional development in recognition of the importance of learning for sustainability in the long run. The effectiveness of the HE is analysed by how the experience contributes to students' personal development in the form of emotional and moral growth (Tan, 2017). This includes analysing how HE influences the formation of beliefs and values (Nusche, 2008). Effective national policymaking, such as attitudes toward lifelong learning, can also help the development of emotional outcomes (Tan, 2015). The intended objectives of HE relates to academics, skill development and student employability. In HE, students must master industry-relevant skills (Audunsson et al., 2020; Abbot, 2021). Problem-solving and communication abilities are equally crucial for HE students (Totopova et al., 2019). Developing broad knowledge is a key impact of HE; the capacity to operate, utilise and evaluate data is equally vital (Audunsson et al., 2020).

The theory that underpins the development of effective learning outcomes is based on ideals that drive sustainable business, government, and societal behaviour (Shephard, 2008). The general public expects HEIs to instil a sense of social responsibility and self-accountability (Tan, 2017). Students must develop social consciousness and integrity, which HEIs must instil in them (Davis et al., 2007). Employers prize vital attributes in their employees, such as the ability to be resilient and persevere in the face of adversity in their lives and professions (Tan, 2015). Self-concepts like self-direction (Duque and Weeks, 2010; Lee, 2015) and self-confidence are crucial in the development of students' resilience and independence. Table 3.9 contains statements based on prior presentations that can be used to operationalise the concept of personal development.

Table 3.8: Statements Of Personal Development

Statements		References
1	My higher education experience has developed me to solve problems effectively.	Duque and Weeks (2010)
2	My higher education has developed me to communicate effectively.	Duque and Weeks (2010)
3	My higher education has enabled me to develop skills relevant to the industry.	Duque and Weeks (2010)
4	I have developed good general knowledge as a result of my higher education experience.	Endo and Harpel (1982)
5	My higher education experience enabled me to better manage, use and analyse information.	Duque and Weeks (2010)
6	My level of integrity improved as a result of my higher education.	Trye (1999)

3.3.9. Higher Education Stakeholders

HEIs, according to Baldrige (1983) and Birnbaum (1988), vary from other organisations in many ways, and they feel that though all organisations try to earn a profit, HEIs are often regarded as non-profit organisations. They went on to say that the issues with respect to the stakeholder faced by HEIs are more complicated than those faced by profit-making businesses. As discussed in the literature, there are different types of stakeholders, internal and external, primary and secondary (Freeman, 1984). There are multiple stakeholders of HEIs, and they have different needs and wants based on their stake in the service provided by the HEI and the outcomes of HE, which causes complexities for the HEIs in developing strategies to meet their desires and needs effectively and efficiently (Conway et al., 1994).

HEIs must adapt academic research and study programmes to the needs of various stakeholders and create ways to include them in order for them to comprehend the value of the service provided and the methods to enhance it (Mainardes et al., 2012). Many scholars

have identified different stakeholders of the HEIs, which include but are not limited to students, academics, parents, administration, management, alumni, industry, media, community etc. (Leisyte and Westerheijden, 2014). HEIs should identify their important stakeholders in line with their strategic objectives, according to Mainardes et al. (2012), which is one of the main phases in developing and executing a stakeholder management plan. Universities should also build particular frameworks for managing stakeholder interactions and perception of their service quality in order to improve the effectiveness of their plan. As discussed in the literature, this study will focus on the differences in the perception of the key stakeholders about the HESQ.

The validity of HE in society is progressively judged by the amount and quality of the HEI's contribution to the community of stakeholders and is fundamentally more extensive than basic contact management (Jongbloed et al., 2008). Instead, it implies that the organisation seeks out and implements methods for incorporating stakeholders in order to better understand how they value the services given and how they may be improved (Alves et al., 2010). One probable effect, according to Benneworth and Arbo (2006), is that these expectations will lead to a new strategy for management and social responsibility, as well as highly competent management and a reassessment of the HEI business model. One stakeholder, students of HEIs, participated by completing online questionnaires and the input of the two key stakeholder groups, (i) teaching and non-teaching staff and (ii) industry professionals, was taken in the form of a semi-structured interview. The questions of the guide script were based on the constructs of the proposed model.

3.4. Chapter Summary

The study's approach uses five service quality dimensions. The model presents the anticipated links among the aspects of service quality on student satisfaction with HEE and subsequent personal development. Most research on student success at HEIs has focused on course delivery and teacher quality, and only a little emphasis has been devoted to finding the complete components of student success using a holistic approach. Service quality is the perception of the whole quality of service and its influence on student experience leading to satisfaction; it is probable that service quality features affect the student experience. He is a service that students get to better themselves; their personal development or the characteristics and skills they obtain through HE is the greatest measure of its excellence.

Physical facility, equipment and aesthetics are all examples of the tangible characteristics of the facility that might be used as indicators of service quality. The tangibles were broken down into three separate statements in the survey. Assurance refers to providers' competence, demeanour and trustworthiness. The assurance aspect analysis relied on four statements. In the literature on service quality, reliability is an individual's capacity to provide consistent and accurate service. Four statements were included in the survey to assess the reliability of the HE services. When dealing with individuals, empathy manifests itself in manners like civility, respect and regard. The responsiveness of a service provider is measured by how quickly and readily they respond to customers. Three statements were added for each aspect of empathy and responsiveness for analysis.

Satisfaction is mostly determined by an individual's emotions and experiences; as HE is interactive, a student's involvement improves their educational experience. The instrument includes six statements to analyse student experience in HEI. Student satisfaction results from meeting expectations. Unrealistic student expectations may cause a service gap and poor satisfaction. Three satisfaction statements were analysed. As a result of their HEE, students are expected to improve course-related abilities and competencies. Growth is as important as knowledge and skills during HEE. The questionnaire includes six statements to analyse the personal growth of students as an outcome of HE.

HEIs must adjust research and study programs to the demands of diverse stakeholders and incorporate them so they can understand the value of the service and how to improve it. The validity of HE in society is determined by the HEIs contribution to the community of stakeholders, which is more comprehensive than simple contact management. The student's perspective on their experience from looking for an HEI until graduating was collected using a questionnaire based on the model construct. Academic and non-academic staff and industry professionals were interviewed using a semi-structured interview script which was based on the model construct.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.1. Introduction

Previous chapters of this thesis provided and explored the aim and objectives of this study, the literature review and the conceptual model that was adopted to carry out this research. In this section of the study, the techniques that were used for this study are discussed. The research onion has been used as a guide to address all of the methodological components of the study design, and the decisions that were taken from each layer of the onion have been justified. The data collection process used a combination of different data collection tools. The quantitative data was collected via the use of an online questionnaire, while the qualitative data was collected through the use of semi-structured interviews. This chapter also covers the pertinent ethical concerns that should be made while conducting a research study.

4.2. Methodological Approach

The term methodology, in some cases, is synonymous with methods. According to Crotty (1998), the methodology is referred to as an approach, a plan of action, a procedure or design that provides justifications for the implementation of the particular approaches and then relates that to the outcomes determined, and it denotes the overall approach adopted to act as guidelines on how to effectively conduct a study within the given research philosophy (Sarantakos, 2012; Tamminen and Poucher, 2020). The approach includes the assumptions of philosophy, method, and procedure (Creswell, 2009; Ponce and Pagán-Maldonado, 2015). The framework to collect and analyse the data for the purpose of achieving the research objectives and answering the research questions is provided by the methodological approach (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Graue, 2015; Zukauskas et al., 2018).

An evidence-based approach founded on evidence-based results was used to construct this study's methodological framework and methodologies (Learmonth, 2008; Doeleman and Have, 2014). In this thesis, a literature review is presented in Chapter 3: Research Framework, as an evidence base to justify the proposed model, which enables addressing the objectives and questions of this research. Saunders et al. (2015), compared the research process to an onion by emphasising the different layers. They introduced six layers of the onion, which are demonstrated in figure 4.1., the six layers of the research onion are representing research philosophies, research approaches, research strategies, choice of method, time horizons, and

choice of techniques and procedures (Saunders et al., 2015). The rationale for adopting the research onion is that it is the most appropriate and widely accepted framework to present the methodological choices made for the research study.

Figure 4.1: Research Onion

(Saunders et al., 2015)

4.3. Research Philosophy

It is important to adopt a research philosophy as it influences the practices to be adopted for the study (Creswell, 2009) and provides the norms for underpinning the strategy of research and methods which are chosen to conduct the study (Saunders et al., 2019). Figure 4.1 shows four different research philosophies: positivism, realism, interpretivism and pragmatism (Saunders et al., 2009). Each of the philosophies is relevant to different assumptions about the world (ontology), how we know that world (epistemology) and the nature of knowledge (Saunders et al., 2009). Ontology is referred to the nature of being or the nature of reality (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Crotty, 1998; Pandey and Patnaik, 2014). It is more concerned with the nature of what exists (Blaikie, 2007; Hathcoat et al., 2019). There are two further variants identified in ontology objectivism and subjectivism (Bryman and Bell, 2015, pp 26-35).

Objectivism holds to reality, and those who accept this position believe that significant reality exists independently of any consciousness and experience (Crotty, 1998). Objectivism supports the positivist stands and may use quantitative methods of statistical analysis (Crotty, 1998). Subjectivism except a reality created by the perceptions of social actors. In other words, there is no meaning without a mind, and different people may construct meaning in different ways, even towards the same phenomenon (Blaikie, 2007).

According to Brenner (2015), epistemology simply refers to the philosophy of knowledge. It is about the nature of knowledge, its likelihood, as well as its extent and general basis (Adorno, 2014). The two extremes of epistemology are positivism and interpretivism. Positivism generally uses quantitative methods based on hypothesis testing for generality from a sample of the population and a questionnaire study to yield the results (Collis and Hussey, 2013). This approach can be regarded as a scientific approach (Creswell, 2009) based on what can be observed or experimented with. Although positivism has been described as an empirical, quantitative approach (Saunders et al., 2012), there are examples of qualitative positivism, in which hypothesis testing can be used to discover delicious ships and fix that can be generalised to the population (Kumarapperuma, 2014; Su, 2018).

Interpretivism focuses on people's account of how to make sense of the world and its structures and processes (Fisher, 2004; Irshaidat, 2019). The essence of interpretivism lies in people's determined reality rather than in objective and external factors (Esterby-smith et al., 2012; Irshaidat, 2019). Given the subjective nature of this philosophy, it is usually associated with qualitative approaches to data collection and interviews is most widely used tool for data collection following subjectivism.

4.4. Choice Of Philosophy

Based on the criticism received by both positivism and interpretivism, on the basis of the discussion above and according to the requirements of this research addressing qualitative and quantitative aspects, the combination of interpretivism and positivism has been adopted. The combination of interpretivism and positivism is referred to as pragmatism. Pragmatism is widely adopted in service quality research. According to pragmatists, there are many different ways in which the world can be interpreted, and a single point of view cannot present the entire picture, and they can be multiple realities (Saunders et al., 2012; James, 2020). Morgan (2014) outlines the characteristic of pragmatism as follows:

- Knowledge should be based on practical outcomes and on what works.
- Research should find out what works through empirical investigation.
- There is no single and best scientific method.
- Change is inevitable, so the knowledge is provisional.
- Conventional dualism in research is considered unhelpful.

Following the philosophy of pragmatism, which seems appropriate for this research. The qualitative data in the form of semi-structured interviews were conducted to take the views of individuals from the industry as well as from the teaching and non-teaching staff of the University. The quantitative data in the form of survey questionnaires were collected from the students at different universities, mainly in the capital city of Pakistan.

4.5. Research Approach

There are two contrasting approaches to choose from: detective and inductive. The detective approach is about choosing a set of hypotheses to build a theory with academic literature and then to be tested by collecting data (Chih-Pei and Chang, 2017). It is a reasoning process relating to a specific cause. The deductive approach seems to suit positivism which allows the formulation of a hypothesis and the testing of expected results (Snieder and Lerner, 2009). On the other hand, the inductive approach is about collecting the data for the investigation of office phenomena and then developing a theory. The process starts with a case and leads to a conclusion of broader and more general relevance (Taylor et al., 2006). This approach suits more with interpretivism (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

The inductive approach is about knowing the premises and using them to generate untested conclusions, and the deductive approach is when the assumptions are true, then the conclusion ought to be true as well (Saunders et al., 2009). With respect to generalizability, the inductive approach leads from specific to generalizability, whereas the deductive approach leads from general to specific (Saunders et al., 2009). The data is used to evaluate proposals or hypotheses linked to an existing theory (Saunders et al., 2009). In this research study, a mixed approach is adopted to interpret the collected data effectively. The importance of mixed method lies in the fact that a single method, whether qualitative or quantitative, cannot encompass the whole situation (Biwer et al., 2020). Therefore, both qualitative and quantitative methods balance each other.

4.6. Research Strategies

Research strategy is referred to the way the research is carried out (Saunders et al., 2009). One or more strategies are used in creating the research design, which is the overall structure of the research giving details of the various elements of design (Sahay, 2016). The choice has to be made by the researcher from an experiment, a survey, grounded theory, action research, a case study and ethnography (Yin, 1994). For this research, survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were used to analyse the impact of service quality on the learning outcomes of HE and the stakeholder's perception.

4.7. Choice Of Methodology

According to Oppenheim (1992); Creswell (2003); Rattray and Jones (2007); Creswell (2010); Pattison et al. (2015), the researcher can adopt any methodology in the business field for the attainment of the research aims and objectives, there is no right or wrong methodology in the business field. A researcher can adopt a single method (qualitative or quantitative), multi-method or mixed method (qualitative and quantitative) to collect the required data. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are used for this research to get the views of internal and external stakeholders. Highlighting the advantages of using mixed methods, Saunders et al. (2009) and Bryman (2016), mentioned that this approach has the great ability to achieve the research objectives and increase confidence in the results of the research.

The interest and literature on mixed methods of research have increased recently. Using mixed methods has implications from both sides as it involves the aspects of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Creswell (2009) mentioned this method as more than "simply collecting and analysing both kinds of data; it also involves the use of both approaches in tandem so that the overall strength of a study is greater than either qualitative or quantitative research" (p. 4). This must be considered that both methods have distinguished strengths and weaknesses, and the decision to adopt any method for the research is dependent on the research area and how the research is planning to address the research topic (Bryman, 2016). Choices about the practices to be used depend on the questions to be answered by the study, and the questions would depend on their context.

Both methods complement each other in a way that qualitative methods are about collecting the research data in the form of words and observations and then analysing and emphasising the inductive approach to the relationship between the theory and research, whereas

quantitative research methods are about quantifying the data collection and then analysing the data entailing the deductive approach to the relationship between the theory and research (Bryman and Bell, 2007; Bryman, 2016). The choice of method is dependent upon the nature and type of the research and the needs of the researcher along with what is being researched (Creswell, 2009).

The above discussion about the methods and the research objectives influenced the choice of the mixed research methodology (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The objectives of this research were to (i) to identify the contribution of HESQ in the student's experience, (ii) to examine the importance of student satisfaction from the HESQ experience contributing towards personal development, (iii) to explore the differences in the perceptions of HESQ amongst the stakeholders in Pakistan and (iv) to make suggestions based on the study to enhance the HESQ for the improvement of personal development of students due to their HEEs in Pakistani HEIs.

4.8. Time Horizon

The layer of time horizon defines the time frame for the research. A cross-sectional or short-term research study is when the data is collected at a specific point in time, and a longitudinal research study is when the data collection takes place repeatedly over a long period of time for the purpose of data comparison (Melnikovas, 2018). Bryman (2016) mentioned the cross-sectional time horizon that data can be collected from one or multiple cases at a specific point in time. The data for the longitudinal studies can be collected repetitively over a certain period of time (Saunders et al., 2009). The choice of time horizon is independent of the choice of methodology (Saunders et al., 2012). The choice of research time horizon is made based on the objectives of the research (Melnikovas, 2018), and generally, in the case of research for the doctoral degree, the time is limited (Sahay, 2016). Based on the above discussion cross-sectional time horizon was adopted.

4.9. Data Collection

Data collection is one of the critical points (Bryman and Bell, 2015, p. 12) of the research study. The study will be conducted using a mixed-method approach for the collection of data from the internal stakeholders of HE as students and teaching staff and external stakeholders of HE as industry professionals. The mixed approach is increasingly supported in business research as it allows the researcher to think inductively and deductively together (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016, p. 106). The mixed-method approach enables the integration of both forms of data by

utilising a distinct design that may involve philosophical assumptions and a theoretical framework (Creswell, 2014). Following the mixed-method approach, the qualitative methods will be used to obtain a depth of understanding (Carlsen and Glenton, 2011) and the quantitative methods will be used to obtain a breadth of understanding of the research topic (Palinkas et al., 2015). The primary data will be collected in both qualitative and quantitative formats using the instruments. Both approaches are commonly used individually, as well as a mixed approach in business research along with research in other fields.

The qualitative study involves the practices that attempt to achieve a level of understanding of the existence of attitudes and opinions (Thorne, 2016) and trends. The study does not quantify the number of emotions or opinions but reflects the indications of the prominent trends within the collected data. Qualitative research in business addresses the business objective via techniques that provide an elaborated interpretation of the phenomena without relying on the numerical values, focusing on the inner meanings and insights (Walle, 2015). The quantitative approach will be adopted to test and examine the relationship among the variables, and these relationships are normally measured in numbers and analysed using statistical instruments (Cresswell, 2014).

The instrument selected for the collection of quantitative data will be the questionnaire survey. The questionnaire is a structured data collection instrument (Bryman and Bell, 2015) and is the most commonly used data collection method for quantitative research (Walle, 2015; Mkandawire, 2019). One of the reasons for using a questionnaire is that, at times, the population of the study is not in one geographical location, and it is easier for the researcher to send the questionnaire, and the participants can fill and return it, or, in some cases, they can fill the questionnaire online.

The questions were aimed at getting the data related to the perception of HESQ. Most of the questions will be in the form of statements, and participants will be able to answer using the Likert scale (Walle, 2015). There were some questions where the participants were able to express their opinion in their own words. The procedures and techniques were employed to control bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Mkandawire, 2019). Firstly, the participants will be assured that there is no wrong answer to the questions in the survey. Secondly, the questionnaire was formulated in a way that controls bias while maintaining the flow of the questions (Wang et al., 2016).

The qualitative side of the study was conducted by taking semi-structured interviews with the customers of the service provider and the managers or supervisors working in that company. The semi-structured interviews were conducted following a format, but the participants were free to talk with regard to the related aspect of the main topic, which is not the case in pre-coded interviews (Fisher, 2011). Bernard et al. (2016) referred to semi-structured interviewing as the best form of an interview in situations where the researcher does not get a second chance to interview the same participant. Interviews can be used for multiple purposes co-constructing new knowledge, assessing opinions, assessing service (Cousin, 2009; Halcomb et al., 2007; Mkandawire, 2019), understanding a particular behaviour, and addressing specific issues (Barrett, 2018).

Interviews were conducted with the motive of understanding and finding the trends which might not come up in the questionnaire survey. Face-to-face semi-structured interviews allowed the interviewer to probe the new trends. All of the interviews were conducted online. The online interview can be synchronous, where the researcher and the participant will be online at the same time and the researcher gets the response immediately, or it can be asynchronous, where the researcher can send the questions (Barrett, 2019). The participant can respond later, though this takes a long time; this allows the participant the time to think through the responses before sending them back to the researcher (Quinlan et al., 2015, p. 155). One of the advantages of a face-to-face interview is that interviewer can explain the questions in further detail if required by the interviewee, which is not the case in asynchronous interviews.

4.10. Quantitative Research Design

This section of the study presents the quantitative research design for the collection of quantitative data using a survey questionnaire. Designing the quantitative study requires the formulation of suitable items and scales to measure the constructs to be used to collect the data.

4.10.1. Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is a widely used tool to collect the required data for answering the research questions and for achieving the objectives of the research (Saunders et al., 2003) in the field of business management (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The data collected via questionnaire provides information from the sample in a homogenous form which enables the generalizability of the results on the population (Ratray and Jones, 2007; Mkandawire, 2019). Designing the

questionnaire is an integral part of the quantitative study (Cavana et al. 2001). Bryman and Bell (2011) made suggestions to flow while designing the questionnaire:

- Direct and brief questions
- Simple words/language
- Avoid repetition and overlapping
- Suitable structure and layout
- Sequence of questions
- Ease and convenience of respondent

4.10.1.1 Item Generation

The process of developing a questionnaire starts with the creation of items that are used to inspect the construct (Hinkin, 1998). A detailed literature review of each construct of the model indicates the conceptualisation of the construct in previous studies and the number of components it has (Carpenter, 2018). The literature review about the constructs was enabled by the amount of knowledge available about the service quality, student experience, student satisfaction, and the personal development of students due to their HEE. The questionnaire is aimed to encompass an overall experience of a HE student ranging from getting the initial information regarding the institute of choice to completing the degree and getting into practical life. The questionnaire is kept brief with the rationale of avoiding respondents' boredom.

A well-articulated conceptual basis indicating the content field of concepts lays the foundation for producing questionnaire items that demonstrate the validity of the content (Hinkin, 1998; Rattray and Jones, 2007; Clark and Watson, 2016). Validity of the content is referred to as "the suitability with which a measure evaluates the field of interest" (Hinkin, 1995, p. 968). As every measure requires a verdict, the content's validity was integrated into the items of the scale through content analysis, confirming that the items created are both theoretically constant with the concept and related to the research's topic (Bagozzi and Edwards, 1998; Wright et al., 2017). By evaluating the research questions and objectives and ensuring that items reflect these, they were kept consistent, and relevance was maintained in terms of perspective (Hinkin, 1998; Rattray and Jones, 2007).

4.10.1.2. Scale development

The next step in the process of questionnaire design is the development of scale. Item scales are used to quantify the phenomenon or theoretical variables, which otherwise cannot be easily observed and accessed (Turker, 2009; DeVellis, 2016). The data collected for the research study using a questionnaire gets highly influenced by the type of scale used; the choice of scale also has implications for the data analysis (Rattray and Jones, 2007).

There are many factors that have importance in scale development, including the wording of the statements and the number of items representing the construct, as well as the alignment of items to form a complete scale (Rattray and Jones, 2007; Clark and Watson, 2016). The importance of the scale development factors is also relevant to the reliability of measurement and response bias (Rattray and Jones, 2007). The reliability is the level of repeated occurrence of the measurement used for the construct (Wright et al., 2017), and it is highly influenced by measurement features, with sample characteristics and measures development techniques having a lesser influence (Churchill and Peter, 1984).

The quality of the data collected is considered higher if the sections of the questionnaires have a short introduction (Andrews 1984). The questionnaire of this research study included a short introduction at the start of all five sections. The items were worded using simple, clear and straightforward language that was deemed familiar and appropriate for the target audience (Rattray and Jones, 2007; Clark and Watson, 2016). This results in the reduction of boredom and tiredness amongst the respondents of the questionnaires (Hinkin, 1998). This online survey questionnaire was developed for the students only. The statement used in the questionnaire in a manner that a single statement was addressing a single aspect to avoid the confusion which can occur if more than one aspect is addressed in a single statement (Hinkin, 1998; Clark and Watson, 2016). Even though it is a common practice that researchers use negatively worded statements in questionnaires with the aim of reducing response biases, negatively worded statement was not used in the questionnaire of this study with the aim of avoiding the misconception.

To the reliability of the scale development, multiple items measurement was used for every construct of the conceptual model. Using multiple items is considered better, as the use of a single item for the measurement can lead to errors in measurement and can lead to bias (Churchill and Peter, 1984; Alves and Raposo, 2007; Rattray and Jones, 2007). The reliability

of the measure is positively related to the number of items used in the scale (Churchill and Peter, 1984; DeVellis, 2016).

The balance of the number of items used for each construct is advised as if the researcher uses too many items per construct; it can lead to boredom and tiredness of the respondents of the questionnaire. On the other hand, using lesser items can lead to a lack of validity and reliability (Hinkin, 1995). There are no set rules about using a definite number of items per construct, but the use of three items per construct is recommended for the purpose of testing the homogeneity of the items (Hinkin, 1998; Grace et al., 2012). For this study, a minimum of three items were used for each construct. Items were also grouped into five different sections for the ease of respondents.

In one of the studies by Teclaw et al. (2012), it was mentioned about the demographic questions that the response rate for such question is better when these questions are asked at the beginning of the questionnaire. For this research study, the first section was designed to address the demographics-related questions. Table 4.1 presents the section-wise division of the questionnaire.

Table 4.1: Sections Of The Questionnaire

Section	Aspect	No of statements	No Open-ended Questions
Section 1	Demographic / Background	5	0
Section 2	Service Quality of HE	19	3
Section 3	Student Experience of HE	6	1
Section 4	Student Satisfaction	3	1
Section 5	Personal Development	6	1

The format or the scale of items in which the respondents of the questionnaire can respond to the items is a critical element as it has an impact on the response style (Weijters et al., 2010). To control the response bias and make the data suitable for statistical analysis, the item scale should produce enough variation in replies amongst the respondents (Hinkin, 1995). There is

a need for the provision of enough discrimination among the responses, and for that, there should be a fair number of response categories in the rating scale (DeVellis, 2016).

The suitability of the number of response categories of a rating scale has been debated by many, but as the number of items per construct, there is an acceptable range of response categories, which five to seven is a suitable number of response categories (Miller, 1956; DeVellis, 2016). The provision of fewer categories of responses (lesser than five) leads to less discrimination in the responses. On the other hand, the provision of a higher number of categories for responses (higher than seven) leads to the element of random responses, which affects the validity of the responses negatively (DeVellis, 2016).

There is a variation in the opinions about the even or odd options on a rating scale (Weijters et al., 2010). If the options of response in the scale are in even number, it is considered that the respondents are led to take a side without being given the option of staying neutral, and the data will be influenced by the opinion of the respondents who wanted to stay neutral (Taylor-Powell, 1998). In contrast to the even number, if the response categories are in an odd number, the respondents have the option to either take a side or stay neutral. This way, the respondents are not led, which could have resulted in response bias (Clark and Watson, 2016). To avoid response bias and to allow the respondents to respond to the statements positively, negatively or by staying neutral, seven response categories were provided on the scale for every item. Likert scales are used to measure the respondents' opinions or feelings about their experience (Rattray and Jones, 2007).

For this study, the aspects of HESQ as tangibles, assurance, reliability, empathy and responsiveness, are the independent variables. The personal development of the student is the dependent variable, and the role of moderating variable is played by student experience. The scale chosen for this study was the Likert scale, as it is the most widely used scale in the quantitative research of service quality. The response categories of the scale ranged from 1 as strongly disagree, and seven as strongly agree (Clark and Watson, 2016). These categories were used for the measurement of the responses for the items of the instrument.

4.10.2. Pilot Testing

Pilot testing was conducted for the identification of any problems in the completion of the questionnaire, like time to complete, use of language, clarity of statements, etc. A pilot study helps the researcher to reflect on the time to complete the questionnaire and also to identify

any apparent problems in terms of wording or accompanying instructions (Buckingham and Saunders, 2004).

Pilot testing was conducted on a small group of 5 participants. They were asked to provide feedback on the questionnaire based on the wording of the statements, clarity of the statements, and layout of the questionnaire. They were also asked to suggest if there is a need to add more statements or if there are too many questions and there is a need to remove some statements. It was highlighted by the first participant that the Likert scale description was not visible in the online questionnaire. The error was immediately rectified. There were no other suggestions made, or errors pointed out regarding the online questionnaire design.

4.10.3. Sampling And Survey

The next step after developing the online questionnaire for the students of HE and after the pilot testing was to conduct the online survey. The online survey was conducted by transforming the questionnaire on Google forms. The success of using the questionnaire to collect data depends on the strategy adopted for the administration of the process, considering all the relevant aspects, including cost (Brick, 2011). The online survey was intended to collect the data in large amounts, suitable for the generalisation of the population. While planning for the sample size, it is essential to consider the importance of sample size for the achievement of the significance of the survey results (Buchanan Hvizdak, 2009; Mkandawire, 2019). The importance of sample size is also relevant in testing the hypotheses (MacCallum et al., 1996).

There are many other suggestions about the sample size. Tinsley and Tinsley (1987) and Maxwell (2000) mentioned the appropriate sample size; as a basic practice, the sample size should be at least ten responders for each item in the questionnaire. However, some of the studies are of the opinion that the use of less than 100 samples is appropriate (Grace et al., 2012). This study aimed to collect 100 samples, but due to the limitations hurdling the data collection, discussed in section 4.10.4.3., a total of 59 responses were collected, out of which 53 were used. This also follows the rule of thumb that the sample size should be greater than the number of questions in a questionnaire (MacCallum et al., 1996).

4.10.4. Sampling Technique

The sampling techniques can be characterised into two categories as probability sampling and non-probability sampling (Churchill, 1995; Sekaran, 2000; Saunders et al., 2012). These two categories can be further divided into subcategories.

4.10.4.1. Probability Sampling

Probability sampling provides equal opportunity for the elements of the sample to be chosen for the study. The subcategories of probability sampling are random sampling, systematic sampling, stratified random sampling and cluster sampling. Simple random sampling is a common technique used in probability sampling. This technique provides the elements of the population equal probability of selection, and a certain number of participants are selected out of the potential participants (Vanderstoep and Johnston, 2009). Systematic random sampling differs from simple random sampling because all the elements of the population do not have an equal opportunity for selection (Malhotra and Birks, 2003). If stratified random sampling is adopted, then the population is divided into organised groups, and then the samples are chosen (Malhotra and Birks, 2003). Cluster sampling is adopted by dividing the population into randomly chosen clusters, and then those clusters are selected instead of individual elements of the population (Sekaran, 2000).

4.10.4.2. Non-Probability Sampling

The non-probability sampling technique gives importance to randomness, so the research conducted can be generalised, and bias is avoided (Tansey, 2007). This sampling technique can be sub-categorised as quota sampling, purposive sampling, snowball sampling, self-selection sampling and convenience sampling. The quota sampling technique is adopted to samples are taken from a predetermined proportion of people on a convenience basis, but it does not have a sampling frame (Sekaran, 2000).

The purposive sampling technique is about choosing the elements of the population on the basis of the researcher's judgement of being best for their research (Tansey, 2007). The Snowball sampling technique is adopted when it is not easy to reach the target population, and the participants are requested to point towards potential participants (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Babbie, 2015). The convenience sampling technique is about selecting the elements of the population which are easy to obtain (Saunders et al., 2007; Sultan, 2011).

4.10.4.3. Choice Of Sampling Technique

Quantitative data for this study was collected by adopting a convenience sampling technique. When probability sampling proved impractical or costly due to restricted access to informants, high non-response rates, or other variables confounding randomisation, convenient sampling procedures were used in quantitative research (Ul Haque et al., 2018). The rationale for the

adoption of this technique was aimed at the recruitment of the respondents for the online survey with ease of accessibility to respondents (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Initially, the data was intended to be collected in person from different HEIs in Pakistan, mainly from the capital city, Islamabad. Due to the unforeseen Covid-19 pandemic and the accompanying travel restriction and lockdown in the UK and Pakistan, resulting in the universities in Pakistan being closed for an uncertain period of time, the self-administered online survey mode was adopted.

Respondents from different institutes and universities were contacted in person, utilising personal contacts as well as social media, initially for pilot testing and later for the main data collection. The majority of the respondents were approached via social media. The researcher joined the Facebook pages of different HEIs, and groups of various HEIs, as well as the HE student groups, for the purpose of reaching the potential participants. Along with Facebook, other online social platforms like LinkedIn were also used for the distribution of the questionnaire. The response rate was extremely low, but quantitative data collection was stopped before reaching the target of 100 responses due to the time limitation. A total of 59 responses were generated, out of which 53 were used for this study.

Self-administered online surveys are comparatively easily facilitated by using online facilities (Simsek and Veiga, 2001). The survey for this research study was managed using an online self-completion questionnaire. Potential survey participants were encouraged to access the online survey, which was hosted on Google Forms, by following a hypertext link shared on social media sites such as Facebook groups and pages. As discussed in the previous section, mainly Facebook, along with other social media platforms, were utilised to contact the potential student respondents of this study. The use of social networking platforms is very suitable, especially in the case where the researcher and the respondents are in two different geographical locations. These platforms allow the researcher to get in touch with potential respondents in various forms like a direct message, a post or a video (Ellison et al., 2007, Papacharissi, 2009).

4.11. Qualitative Research Design

This section provides details about the qualitative research design adopted to collect the qualitative data. The qualitative research phase covered the opinions of the two stakeholder groups (i) academic and non-academic staff of HEI and (ii) industry professionals. Creswell (1994, p. 1) defines qualitative research as an "inquiry process of understanding a social or

human problem, based on building a complex, holistic picture, formed with words, reporting detailed views of informants, and conducted in a natural setting". Creswell (2009) further states that "qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem".

Qualitative research is about studying the experiences of people in their natural settings in an effort to the interpretation of the phenomenon in relation to the meaning participants of the study attribute to them. Qualitative researchers, according to Denzin et al. (2008), employ a variety of interlinked interpretative methods in order to gain a more profound knowledge of the subject matter at hand. The data in the qualitative phase of the research was collected using interviews. One of the most important tools for gathering data for the research is the qualitative interview (Gill et al., 2008). In this sense, an interview is a sort of conversation in which one party actively seeks out information from another (Adhabi and Anozie, 2017).

The literature on research methods classifies three different types of interviews: Structured, unstructured and semi-structured (Kajornboon, 2005; Edwards and Holland, 2013). All three types aim to get the view of the participants, but the classifications are made on the basis of the level of flexibility and control (Newman, 2007). Semi-structured and unstructured interviews are commonly used in qualitative research as the structured interview approach often generates quantitative data (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). Out of the two, the semi-structured interview approach is more commonly used (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). For this research study, a semi-structured interview approach was adopted to collect qualitative data.

4.11.1. Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews are a widely used research technique in qualitative research across various disciplines, including business research (Myers and Newman, 2007; Schultz and Avital, 2011). Unlike formal interviews, which follow a pre-set plan of questions, semi-structured interviews focus on specific themes in a conventional manner (Raworth et al., 2012). They often provide valued information that was not expected by the researcher (Raworth et al., 2012). This approach provides an opportunity for the participants of the research to develop their opinions regarding the research phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2012), therefore, permits the researcher to dig deep into the individuals' perspectives (Daymon and Holloway, 2010) and important personal and societal issues (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006).

According to researchers, a good interview entails adequate preparation, demonstrating respect for interview subjects, careful listening by the interviewer, the creation of thoughtful interview

guides, an interview guide script with fewer queries, the formulation of short, open-ended questions, and the interviewer's adaptability to diverge from the established plan when required (Taylor, 2013). The semi-structured interview technique was adopted as it allows the researcher to collect rich and deep information (Schultze and Avital, 2011; Bryman, 2012) about the perceptions of the stakeholders regarding the service quality of the HE. This approach allows the interviewer to utilise a pre-written interview guide script with a series of open-ended questions (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Barrett, 2018), which gives structure and flexibility to the interviewer to identify and investigate new potential issues related to the core research phenomenon (Daymon and Holloway, 2010, Al-Rahbi, 2017).

Scholars have raised some concerns about conducting semi-structured interviews. Choosing whom to speak to is one of the major challenges that researchers have (Witchsey et al., 2013). The “who” question specifies the kind of demographic that the study wishes to reach out to. Is it males, kids or just one particular race (Adhabi and Anozie, 2017)? The communication component is taken into account while determining the who portion of the semi-structured interviews. Both groups of participants, academic and non-academic staff of HEIs and industry professionals, were approached randomly, and all those who showed intent to participate were booked for an interview. Adapting to the ideal interview format and preparing in advance are other significant elements that might compromise the efficacy of qualitative interviews (Witchsey et al., 2013; Barrett, 2018). While conducting the semi-structured interview, the researcher must demonstrate consistency throughout, which may be tough. To overcome this obstacle, the interview questions were asked in the same format to all the participants. The additional aspects of the topic mentioned by the participants were presented to all the other participants to address. Most researchers do not have sufficient time to prepare for their interviews, which hinders their capacity to choose which questions to ask the participants (Drew, 2014; Adhabi and Anozie, 2017). Sufficient time was allocated for the qualitative data collection. After the finalisation of the semi-structured interview script and before conducting the pilot study, the researcher practised conducting the semi-structured interview by performing mock interviews with family members and friends. The actual interviewing only commenced after achieving satisfactory fluency with respect to the format of the interview.

4.11.2. Guide Script Development

This section covers the details of the instrument development for the qualitative phase of research. Section 4.10.1 provide the rationale for adopting the semi-structured interview for data collection. The qualitative data was collected from the participants from the two

stakeholder groups (i) academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs and (ii) industry professionals. The interview script of the semi-structured interviews was developed, which comprised the guide questions (Myers and Newman, 2007). Along with guiding the interviewer, the guide also certifies uniformity and reliability in all the interviews, so all the participants of the qualitative research are asked similar questions.

The instrument was carefully designed based on the literature in Chapter 2 and 3 and the objectives of the research. During the development of the instrument, the flow of the interview was carefully considered. The questions were considered to yield answers and avoid leading questions (Stringer and Genat, 2004) and to make sure that the questions flow produced further descriptions (Myers and Newman, 2007).

The questions have initially been divided into three sections. The first section covered the demographic aspects, including the highest university degree, job role, along with years of experience for the particular job role as well as in the industry. The second section was about asking the opinions of the participants about their perception of the service quality of HEIs. This section of the guide script covered the questions about the expectations of the students, available facilities, and service optimisation.

The third section of the script was about the opinion of the participant with regard to the student’s personal development due to his or her HEEs. This section was focused on the skills and personality development of the students, along with the aspects of improvement. The fourth section was added to the script after the initial interviews. This section covered the questions about the aspects indicated by the participants, covering the aspects of quality vs quantity, the interaction of teacher and students, same curriculum and vocational training. Table 4.2 presents the aspects addressed in each section, along with the number of questions/statements in each section.

Table 4.2: Sections Of The Interview Guide Script

Section	Aspect	No of questions /Statements
Section A	Demographic / Background	10
Section B	Perception of Service Quality	7

Section C	Perception of Personal Development	9
Section D	Evolved Questions	4

4.11.3. Pilot Study

A pilot study can be used in both quantitative research and qualitative research (Al-Rahbi, 2017). It should be examined by the researcher whether the included questions in the interview script make sense by pretesting them with colleagues, friends and at least one member of the target research group (Rowley, 2012). Bell (2014) mentioned that the benefit of the pilot study is to gain probing skills, especially if the researcher is inexperienced in interviewing techniques. Gudmundsdottir and Brock-Utne (2010) argued that piloting increases the reliability and validity of the research and enables early changes to the research direction (Rowley, 2012).

The interview script was pilot tested with two friends and one participant of the stakeholder group. Based on the flow of the interview and the responses of the participants, some of the questions were re-worded to improve the communication between the interviewer and the participants. The pilot study was helpful in identifying the minute errors in the wording and gaining confidence in the interviewing skills, including probing.

4.11.4. Sampling Strategy For Qualitative Data

The selection of the research sample is a vital element of the research design (Creswell, 1998). The choice of sampling affects the quality of the overall research, and it is important to provide unbiased and robust results (Coyne, 1997). The development of a sampling strategy for the selection of a subset of potential participants to represent the whole population is complicated in the research study (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). Therefore, careful consideration is required to develop a sampling strategy (Collins et al., 2007). Even though there are many sampling methods available to choose from (Teddlie and Yu, 2007), it is significant to recognise the potential participants from information-rich (Blandford, 2013) research subjects, who ought to be the most well-informed about the topic of research (Myers and Newman, 2007). Qualitative data was collected from two stakeholder groups in the form of semi-structured interviews. Saunders et al. (2009), mentioned that non-probability convenience sampling suits the exploratory stage of the research.

According to Guest et al. (2006), 12 in-depth interviews are sufficient to get enough data from a homogenous group. Creswell (2013) and Lewis (2015) suggested that the number of interviews should be between 5 and 30. The range for semi-structured interviews for a study is between 5 and 25 (Saunders et al., 2009). For this research study, 12 semi-structured interviews were conducted with the participants of the two stakeholder groups. There were 7 participants from a teaching and a non-teaching group of stakeholders and 5 participants from the industry professionals' group. The guide script for the interviews was developed in English as well as in Urdu (The national language of Pakistan), as some of the potential participants were reluctant to participate in the interview to be conducted in the English language.

4.11.5. Conducting Interviews

The qualitative phase was intended to be conducted in the form of face-to-face semi-structured interviews, but due to the limitations mentioned above, the majority of the interviews were conducted via Zoom. Two of the respondents participated in their interview in written form. The potential participants of the semi-structured interviews were approached via email and social networking platforms. As there is a difference in time zone between Pakistan and the United Kingdom, the researcher carefully considered this element while making the appointments for the interviews. The participants were given an open choice to choose day and time for the interview.

The guide script was sent to the participants in advance, along with the participant information sheet. The reason for sending the guide script was to allow time for participants to familiarise themselves with the questions to be asked so a detailed response could be generated. Two of the participants choose to respond in written form due to personal reasons, both of these participants were from academic and non-academic group of stakeholders. Most of the participants were sent a guide script in English, while a few were sent in Urdu as well.

The total number of potential participants who initially agreed to participate in the interview was 26, but unfortunately, only 12 interviews were conducted. Some participants initially agreed but could not allow time to participate. The interviews were conducted individually and were recorded in the form of videos after the consent of the participants. The average time for each interview was 55 min. The participants were given the freedom to express themselves in the language of their choice. Most of the interviews were conducted in English. Some of the interviews were in a mixed language, English and Urdu, while a couple

of interviews were conducted in Urdu. The transcripts of all the interviews were later translated and written into English using the recorded videos.

The questions were asked according to the responses of the participants and the flow of the interview. The tone of voice of the interviewer was neutral to ensure the reliability of the collected data and avoid bias during the interview. Even though the interviews were recorded, the interviewer listened carefully to the participants to underpin their important opinions, thoughts and aspects.

4.11.6. Validity And Reliability Of The Semi-Structured Interviews

Golafshami (2003) mentioned that validity and reliability are important concepts and part of the research methodology, whether it is qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods research. Validity and reliability are generally referred to as the way research is represented and generalised by the researcher (Winter, 2000). The concepts of validity and reliability are different in qualitative research and have distinct meanings in quantitative research. The validity and reliability of the mixed methods research study are assessed by the quality standards observed in the study (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). In quantitative research, these are achieved by using a credible measuring instrument (Golafshani, 2003). In qualitative research, validity and reliability depend on the ability and skill of the researcher (Golafshani, 2003). In the case of semi-structured interviews, they depend on the expertise of the interviewer/researcher to conduct semi-structured interviews (Byers and Wilcox, 1991).

In qualitative research studies, there are two types of validity internal and external (Burke, 1997). Internal validity depends on the researcher's ability to explain the cause-and-effect relationships in the research in a meaningful way (Byer and Wilcox, 1991). In the case of qualitative research, selecting an accurate sample can enhance validity (Winter, 2000). An accurate sample was selected for this research study by the researcher to ensure validity. Along with selecting a suitable sample researcher carefully followed the standard steps while conducting the semi-structured interview and also while analysing them. Combining the qualitative and quantitative methods of research also improves internal validity. The external validity in qualitative research is characterised by the degree of generalisation of the findings (Riege, 2003). The external validity of this research study was achieved by the comparison of the results attained from the semi-structured interviews with the existing literature.

The reliability of the qualitative research is analysed by the ability of the research to generate similar results when the technique and procedures used in this research are replicated (Winter,

2000). This research study was conducted by carefully following specific techniques, procedures and steps like transcription, coding and finding the themes and patterns for the analysis of the semi-structured interviews. The use of mixed methods to conduct the research study increases the validity and reliability of the research study (Patton, 1990). This approach is helpful in the establishment of a valid proposition and in avoiding bias (Mathison, 1988). Golafshani (2003) referred to the use of mixed methodology as a typical strategy to enhance the validity and reliability of the research and for the evaluation of the findings in an effective manner. The adoption of the mixed methods approach has played a vital role in the generation of valid results.

4.12. Data Analysis

Data analysis is about searching for patterns in data and ideas that enlighten the reasons for the existence of those patterns (Bernardet al., 2006). Data analysis is about breaking down and simplifying the data to clarify the relationship between it (Saunders et al., 2009). Both qualitative data and quantitative data were analysed using suitable techniques and procedures. The qualitative data analysis was conducted by adopting the thematic analysis. Data were analysed in terms of the data content and data themes (Quinlan et al., 2015, p. 133) in a systematic order by categorising the contents and themes (Thomson, 2011). Quantitative data analysis is about analysing the number using statistical methods. The commonly used software for quantitative data analysis is SPSS. The findings of the quantitative data analysis will be presented using various graphs and charts along with the explanation of the found trends and interpreted meanings.

4.12.1. Quantitative Data Analysis

The data for the quantitative research was collected using an online questionnaire via google forms. The participants of the survey were contacted via social media platforms and were requested to follow the link to fill out and submit their responses. A total of 59 participants filled out the questionnaire, out of which 53 responses were used, and six responses were rejected based on an incompleteness. The collected data were transferred to SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for the purpose of analyses. Different analytical tests were conducted to analyse the reliability and validity of the research.

4.12.1.1. Reliability

Reliability is referred to the capacity of the measuring instrument to generate consistent results (Carmines and Zeller, 1979; Taherdoost, 2016). The scale will be considered reliable if the measurement is repeated under the same condition and the same results are generated (Moser and Kalton, 1989). The measuring instrument will be considered to have high internal consistency reliability if the items of the instrument "hang together" and measure the same construct (Huck, 2007; Robinson, 2009). Cronbach's Alpha was used as a tool to analyse the reliability of the instrument. It is the most commonly used and appropriate internal consistency measure of reliability when Likert scales are used (Whitley, 2002; Taherdoost, 2016). Hinton et al. (2004) suggested four levels of reliability:

- Low reliability if the Cronbach Alpha is 0.50 or below.
- High-moderate reliability if the Cronbach Alpha is 0.51 – 0.70.
- High reliability if the Cronbach Alpha is 0.71 – 0.90.
- Excellent reliability if the Cronbach Alpha is 0.91 and above.

There is no general rule about the value of internal consistency, but most agree on the minimum value of 0.70 (Whitley, 2002; Robinson, 2009). Table 4.3 presents the reliability of the scales.

Table 4.3: Reliability Of Scales

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach Alpha
Tangibles	3	0.75
Assurance	4	0.79
Reliability	4	0.87
Empathy	3	0.87
Responsiveness	3	0.81
Student Experience	6	0.93
Student Satisfaction	3	0.90
Personal Development	6	0.93

The compound reliability of all eight scales used ranged from 0.75 to 0.93, indicating the internal consistency of the statements of the survey questionnaire. Table 4.4 presents the descriptive statistics of the quantitative data, including the mean, standard deviation and variance of 53 respondents.

Table 4.4: Descriptive Statistics Of The Quantitative Data

	N	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
University's website provides complete information for decision making.	53	4.89	.251	1.826	3.333
The induction was helpful in knowing the whereabouts of the University.	53	5.02	.255	1.855	3.442
There are sufficient facilities in the class/lecture rooms.	53	5.38	.229	1.667	2.778
There are sufficient learning resources available in the University according to your course.	53	4.75	.238	1.731	2.996
The learning environment conveys a sense of competence and professionalism.	53	5.30	.213	1.551	2.407
Administration staff is efficient and supportive.	53	4.98	.223	1.623	2.634
Student services are readily available and delivered on time.	53	4.68	.238	1.730	2.991
Operating hours of student services are convenient for students.	53	5.04	.230	1.675	2.806
Professors/lecturers are available to provide guidance other than lecture times.	53	4.53	.256	1.867	3.485
Teaching staff are consistent in the way they teach.	53	4.92	.236	1.719	2.956
Teaching staff are skilful and competent in what they teach.	53	5.36	.240	1.744	3.042

The institute's communication network is up to date and efficient.	53	5.11	.228	1.660	2.756
The staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems.	53	4.68	.248	1.806	3.261
Students feel safe in their interaction with the staff member.	53	5.04	.235	1.709	2.922
The institute encourages confidence in the students.	53	4.92	.265	1.930	3.725
The overall service provided by the University is a good value for a fee.	53	4.64	.270	1.962	3.850
You will recommend this University to our family and friends.	53	4.55	.288	2.099	4.406
The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling that my best interests are being served.	53	4.79	.256	1.864	3.475
The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling that the rewards gained are consistent with the effort I put into the assessment/exam.	53	4.92	.244	1.774	3.148
The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of enjoyment with the education experience.	51	5.04	.236	1.685	2.838
I feel involved with the HEI I am attending.	53	4.89	.237	1.728	2.987
The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of uniqueness of being associated with it.	52	4.92	.238	1.713	2.935
The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of anticipation and being intellectually challenged.	53	4.91	.250	1.821	3.318
The first impression of the HEI met your expectations.	53	4.85	.260	1.895	3.592
The HEI is meeting your expectations of higher education learning.	53	4.77	.245	1.783	3.179
The HEI is meeting your overall expectations.	53	5.00	.239	1.743	3.038
My HEI has developed me to solve problems effectively.	53	4.77	.237	1.728	2.986

My higher education experience has developed me to communicate effectively.	53	4.96	.251	1.829	3.345
My higher education has enabled me to develop skills relevant to the industry.	53	4.55	.269	1.957	3.829
I have developed good general knowledge as a result of my higher education experience.	53	5.06	.208	1.512	2.285
My higher education experience enabled me to better manage, use and analyse information.	53	5.02	.211	1.538	2.365
My level of integrity improved as a result of my higher education.	53	5.04	.219	1.593	2.537

4.12.1.2. Validity

Validity reflects how well the collection of data covers the actual area of investigation (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). It means "measure what is intended to be measured" (Field, 2005). To validate the measuring instrument, the following validity tests were conducted. The researcher's instrument was developed based on the literature review and the proposed conceptual model. The items of the scales used to collect data were in accordance with the five dimensions of service quality and the process of service delivery, and the learning outcomes of HE.

The face validity was achieved by modifying, including and excluding the items of the instrument based on the feedback and suggestions of the pilot participants and the expert. It has face validity if its content looks relevant to the person taking the test. It is evaluated on the basis of the appearance of the instrument with respect to feasibility, readability, consistency of style, formatting and the clarity of the language used (Taherdoost, 2016). According to Oluwatayo (2012), face validity refers to the researcher's subjective evaluations of the measuring instrument's presentation and relevance, such as whether the items in the instrument appear to be relevant, logical, unambiguous and clear.

4.12.2. Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis is not a simple or rapid task (Pope et al., 2000). It is commonly acknowledged that qualitative research (unlike quantitative research) generates a large and huge quantity of raw data in the form of transcripts, notes, and other documents (Grbich, 2012). As a result, qualitative research analysis is a complicated, perplexing, time-consuming, and labour-intensive process (Cresswell, 2013). In qualitative research, a variety of data analysis approaches are used. These methods include narrative analysis, discourse analysis, semiotic analysis, content analysis and thematic analysis (Saunders et al., 2009; Braun et al., 2014). Content analysis and thematic analysis are the widely adopted methods of qualitative data analysis in many fields of study. These two types are quite similar, with some differences (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). The point of difference is on the basis of outcomes; the content analysis is inclined to generate results of quantitative nature. On the other hand, the thematic analysis is inclined towards identifying and describing the explicit and implicit ideas (Guest et al., 2011).

To analyse the qualitative data, thematic analysis was adopted, which was defined as the foundational method for qualitative analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis can be adopted with any philosophy due to its flexibility regarding the research question, sampling size, data collection method and approaches to meaning generation (Clarke and Braun, 2014; Terry et al., 2017). This method can be adapted to analyse data collected from widely used qualitative techniques like interviews, focus groups, qualitative surveys and story completion (Braun and Clarke, 2013). This method is very useful with respect to the identification of key themes in the data for further investigation (Barun and Clarke, 2013). Saldana (2015) also mentioned coding and thematic technique as the most suitable methods for qualitative analysis. For this study, the thematic analysis involved transcription of the semi-structured interviews, coding and searching for the themes.

4.12.2.1. Transcription

Data was collected using recorded semi-structured interviews with 12 internal and external stakeholder groups participants via Zoom. The transcripts of the interviews were generated. Writing transcripts improved the familiarity of the data with the researcher. The semi-structured interview videos were watched repeatedly, and the researcher read transcripts many times to identify the themes in the data. Maguire and Delahunt (2017) recommended that the

researcher should be very familiar with all of the collected data. Saunders et al. (2016), also referred to data familiarity as very important.

4.12.2.2. Coding

Coding is about labelling the data with similar meanings in a systematic manner to be analysed in the later stages. Coding is vital for managing, arranging, rearranging and retrieving data as it reduces lots of data into small chunks of meaning (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). Coding allows the arrangement of the data into groups (Bryman, 2016). Arrangement of data occurs based on the meaning; all the similar meaning data gets the same code. This approach enables the extraction and interpretation of important points from the collected data. Open coding was adopted, as the researcher did not have any pre-set codes. Coding was done manually on the hard copies of the interview transcripts. Codes were generated during the process. The researcher was mindful of the main research question, and every relevant segment of the collected data was coded. During the process, the codes were modified to represent the data better.

4.12.2.3. Search For Themes

Braun and Clarke (2006) mentioned that there is no hard and fast set of rules about what makes a theme. The theme is a pattern that highlights something noteworthy or intriguing about the data or study question (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). The generated codes were listed and analysed. The similar codes were grouped together and organised into themes. Further analysis of the data and codes led to the identification of a sub-theme. Four themes were identified during the process.

- Higher Education Experience Of Students
- Student's Personal Development
- Industry's potential, expectations and role
- Service Quality of HE

4.13. Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were a critical part of the research (McAndrew and Jeong, 2012). Ritchie et al. (2013, p.78) mentioned ethical confederation as the heart of high-quality research. It is important to maintain the ethical standards of the research (Blandford, 2013). The function of values that the researcher contributes to the study process is a topic of ethical

discussion in management and social research (Bryman and Bell, 2011). At the same time, the difficulties confronting researchers from different fields may also differ (Bell and Bryman, 2007). This generally entails ensuring that research subjects are able to give informed consent and that they are not injured, deceived, or have their privacy violated while participating in the study (Bryman and Bell, 2011). General ethical principles apply to internet research as well (Rose et al., 2015).

This research study involved the collection of primary data from the human participants, and ethical considerations became vital and essential for the successful completion of the research (Wisker, 2008). Informed consent, voluntary participation, beneficence, risk of harm, confidentiality and anonymity are the central issues in ethical considerations (Trochim, 2006). To conduct this research, a formal Ethical Approval Application was submitted to the Research and Ethics Committee. The reference number for the application is 2020-13084-10581. After getting the approval, the research was started, and the central ethical issues were kept in consideration.

Participants were given a consent form and a participant information sheet to read and approve before proceeding with the survey, which was done in accordance with informed consent protocols. Participants were educated about the research's objective and goals in order to reduce their anxiety about taking part in it. They were also informed about the expected average duration it will take to complete the online questionnaire (15-20 min), and the participants of the interview were also informed about the average time to complete the interview (40-60 min).

The participants were told that taking part in the online survey and semi-structured interviews were entirely optional and that they may opt out at any time during the survey or interview. They were also informed that even if the interview is completed and they want to withdraw from the study, there will be no obligation or social pressure on them to continue. The researcher made sure that no such material, comment or statement is included in the survey questionnaire for the students or in the interview questions for the academic and non-academic staff of the HEIs and industry professionals, which can be considered intimidating, insulting or disrespectful.

Participants were also notified that their comments and answers would be kept personal and private. The identity of the participants was likewise safeguarded because when filling out the questionnaire or participating in the interview, they were not required to reveal any

personal information. As a result, it could not be linked to a person because the data was submitted anonymously. The confidentiality of the information acquired during the survey process was ensured by data protection. The data, which was carefully saved on a computer, is only accessible by the research's chief investigator. The survey and interview participants were informed that the information gathered would be used solely for the purposes of this study.

4.14. Chapter Summary

This chapter presented all of the methodological aspects of the study that have been addressed using the research onion as a framework, and all of the choices made at each level of the onion have been explained and justified. The methodology provides the structure for gathering and analysing data in order to attain the study's aims and give insight into its questions. Taking into account the foregoing debate and the needs of this study addressing qualitative and quantitative components, a mixed approach known as Pragmatism has been adopted, combining elements of positivism and interpretivism. In keeping with this guideline, a mixed strategy was used. The difficulties encountered and overcome during the data collection phase were also discussed in this section. Students of HEIs were queried quantitatively by having them fill out a self-administered online survey. In order to collect qualitative data, interviews were conducted with the other two groups of stakeholders.

The data obtained from the semi-structured interviews were compared to the previously published research in order to establish the external validity of the study. There is an improvement in both the validity and reliability of the research study as a result of the adoption of mixed methodologies (Patton, 1990). This strategy is beneficial in establishing a legitimate thesis and avoiding prejudice, both of which are important considerations in research. As a result of the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire's items, the compound reliability of all the eight scales used in the questionnaire varied from 0.75 to 0.93. this was determined by calculating the average of each scale's individual reliability. Coding and thematic technique were used for qualitative analysis as it is the most appropriate tool for doing qualitative research analysis. The data and the codes were analysed, which ultimately led to the discovery of sub-themes. This chapter contains a discussion of the ethical concerns that were involved in this study. The presentation of the findings of the research, as well as a discussion of those findings, are presented in the following chapter. The next chapter addresses each of the four research questions.

Chapter 5: Findings And Discussion

5.1. Introduction

This chapter will present the findings of the research conducted using mixed methods. The rationale for using the mixed methods has been discussed in detail in Chapter 4, along with the choice of philosophy, research design and analysis. The quantitative research was conducted using a self-administered online survey, and primary quantitative data was collected from the students of HEIs in Pakistan. For the qualitative research, semi-structured interviews were used to collect the primary qualitative data from the teaching and non-teaching staff of the HEIs and the industry professionals.

The quantitative research findings will be presented and discussed in detail in the first section of this chapter. The findings will be presented in the form of figures and tables and will be discussed in detail. Direct quotes from the respondents from the open-ended questions will also be part of the discussion. The first and the second question of the research are answered, and the first and second research objectives are achieved based on the findings of the quantitative research. The second section will present the findings and discussion of the qualitative research. The qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis. The findings and discussion will be carried out following the sub-themes using direct quotes from the participants. The third and fourth research questions are answered and the third and fourth research objectives are achieved based on the findings of quantitative and qualitative research.

5.2. Quantitative Findings And Discussion

This section will present the findings from the quantitative data collected in the form of a self-administered online survey questionnaire from the students of HEIs in Pakistan. The questionnaire was divided into five sections. The first section covered the questions related to the demographics related to the study but did not include any questions about the respondents' personal information. The second section of the questionnaire asked the respondent's opinions about the aspects of service quality of their HEI. The third section covered the questions about the student experience in the HEI. The questions in the fourth section of the survey were about satisfaction, and the last section was about the personal development of the respondents as a result of their HE. The questionnaire included some open-ended questions as well.

5.2.1. Sample Demographics

The respondents were approached via social media and other online mediums due to the Covid-19 restriction discussed in the previous chapter. This section will present the demographics of the respondents in the form of tables and figures. Figure 5.1 presents the participation of the respondents based on gender. As apparent from figure 5.1, the majority of the respondents were males. There is also a representation of those participants who did not reveal their gender.

Figure 5.1: Gender Of The Respondents

Figure 5.2 shows the age group representations of the questionnaire respondents. Respondents were to choose from five age groups ranging from below 20 to over 35. The majority of the respondents were over the age of 25. Most respondents were from the age group of 31-35.

Figure 5.2: Respondent's Age

The students were also asked if they were national students of Pakistan, or they were international students studying in Pakistan. Out of the 53 accepted responses, 47 were national students, and 6 were students from other countries studying in Pakistan. Figure 5.3 in Appendix 2 represents the percentage of students from each group.

Figure 5.3: Presenting Status Of The Students

The respondents were asked about their course and the HEI as well in the first section of the questionnaire. Table 5.1 in Appendix 8 presents the responses about the course respondents were enrolled in. As shown in Table 5.1, most of the respondents were at the graduation level of education. There are also many respondents studying at the master's level, and there were some at the PhD level as well. The areas of study also varied; the respondents were from the areas of management sciences to pure sciences, as well as from engineering to economics. The respondents of the questionnaire survey were from different HEIs, as shown in Table 5.2 in Appendix 9. The majority of the respondents were from HEIs in the capital city of Pakistan. There is a representation of the students of HEIs in other cities as well.

The respondents were asked about their initial source of information about their HEI. Almost half of the respondents mentioned friends and family as the initial source of information about their HEI. The second option chosen by the respondents after friends and family as a source of initial information was the institute's website. 32% of the respondents received the initial information from the HE's website. Out of the 53 accepted responses, only 8% of them mentioned the newspaper as the source of initial information, and the remaining 11% chose the option of other sources like Google, HEC etc.

Figure 5.4: Initial source Of information

Enrolling in a certain institution is crucial not only for the students but also for their families (Guo, 2018). In order to make the best choices, students consult university brochures or websites and seek assistance from friends, teachers, and relatives who may be able to give relevant information (Allen and Higgins, 1994). The respondents of the survey were also asked about the ease and simplicity of the admission process. Where they have an option of sharing their thought in case, they did not find the admission process easy and straightforward. The responses to this particular question are presented in figure 5.5 in Appendix 2. Around 87% of the respondents said they found their HEI admission process simple and easy, while 13 % said their HEI admission process was not simple and easy.

5.2.2. Aspects Of Service Quality

The self-administered online survey questionnaire contained questions according to the aspects of service quality, student experience, satisfaction and personal development. The following parts of this section will present the findings and discussion accordingly.

5.2.2.1. Tangibles

Tangibles are a vital part of the service. The tangibles in the aspects of service quality are the condition of facilities, equipment and appearance of personnel (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The students of HEIs were asked about their perception of tangible aspects of service quality. The research instrument contained three statements related to the tangible aspects of HESQ. The statements and responses to those statements are presented in figure 5.6.

The first statement was about the facilities available in the classroom, and it is represented by a blue coloured bar. As shown in figure 5.6, most of the respondents were on the agreement side of the statement, with 34% “strongly agreeing” that there are sufficient facilities in the lecture/classrooms. It is also visible from the figure that the combined percentage is under 10% of those respondents who have responded in disagreement with the statement.

Figure 5.6: Tangible Aspects Of HESQ

The second statement was about the learning resources available according to the course of the respondents. The majority of the respondents agreed with this statement as well. The highest percentage of the respondents, 26.4%, chose “Agree” as their response. As shown in figure 5.6, the combined percentage of disagreement with this statement is higher than the previous statement. 20.8% of the respondents decided to stay “neutral” about the statement.

The third statement relevant to the tangible aspects of HESQ was about the learning environment of the HEI and the sense of competence and professionalism conveyed by the environment of HEI. The respondent majority was on the agreement side of the statement, with 28.3% “strongly agreeing” with the statement. Less than 18% of the respondents chose to disagree with the statement to different extents, and 9.4% decided to stay “neutral”, as shown in figure 5.6.

5.2.2.2. Assurance

The assurance aspect of service quality is about the knowledge and courteousness of employees and their aptitude to inspire trust and confidence (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The research instrument contained four statements about the assurance aspects of HESQ. The statements about the assurance aspects of HESQ and responses are presented in figure 5.7. Students were asked about the information provided on the website of HEI. The majority of the respondents agreed to different extents that the complete information is provided on the HEI for the decision making, with 24.5% of the respondents choosing the option of “strongly agree”. 24.5% of the respondents decided to stay “neutral”, and the combined disagreement with the statement from almost 19% of the respondents. The second statement was about the induction, and 30.2% of the respondents “strongly agreed”, 7.5% “strongly disagreed”, and 22.6% were “neutral” about the statement that induction helped know the whereabouts of the university.

The third statement was about the perception of the efficiency of the institute’s communication network. The majority of the students who took part in the research were on the agreement side of the statement, and 32.1% “more or less agreed”. The fourth statement was about the institute encouraging confidence in the students and was agreed by the majority of respondents to different extents, including 24.5% as “strongly agree”. The disagreement with the statement from 20.7% of the respondents.

Figure 5.7: Assurance Aspects Of HESQ

5.2.2.3. Reliability

The reliability aspect of service quality is about the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The research instrument contained four statements in relevance to the aspect of reliability. Figure 5.8 presents the statements and the responses of the students who participated in the study. The first statement was about the consistency of the teaching staff concerning the way they teach. The highest percentage of students, 22.6%, “more or less agreed” with the statement and the combined disagreement with the statement was from less than 17% of the responding students. 18.9% of the responding students were “neutral” to this statement.

The second statement was about the skilfulness and competence of the teaching staff, and the majority of the respondents were in agreement with the statement that the teaching staff are skill full and competent in what they teach, with 30.2% of the students “strongly agreed”. Less than 12% of the students chose to disagree with the statement in the extent of “strongly disagree”, “Disagree”, and “more or less disagree” combined, and 7.5% decided to stay “neutral”.

Figure 5.8: Reliability Aspects Of HESQ

The third statement was about the overall service of HEI as good value for a fee. Similar to the previous statements, the respondent majority agreed with the statement in different capacities, including 22.6% “strongly agreed”. Almost 25% of the respondents disagreed with the

statement, and 20.8% stayed “neutral”. The fourth statement was about recommending the university/HEI to your family and friends. Over half of the respondents agreed in different capacities that they would recommend their HEI to their family and friends. Almost 29% of the respondents chose the option of not recommending their HEI to family and friends, whereas 15.1% stayed “neutral”.

5.2.2.4. Empathy

Empathy is referred to the caring, individualised attention provided to students (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The empathy aspect was covered in three statements in this study. Figure 5.9 presents the statements and the responses of the students who participated in this study. The first statement about the empathy aspect of the HESQ addressed the guidance provided by the teaching staff other than the lecture times. The majority of the respondents agreed with the statement that the professors/lecturers are available to provide guidance other than lecture times. 18.9% “strongly agreed”, 17% “agreed”, and 17% “more or less agreed”. The combined disagreement with the statement was from under 31% of the respondents, and 17% were “neutral”.

Figure 5.9: Empathy Aspects Of HESQ

The second statement was about the sympathy and reassurance from the staff when the student faces any problem. Around 53% of the respondents were on the agreement side with the statement, including 20.8% who were “strongly agreed”. Around 29% of the respondents did

not perceive the statement to be correct and disagreed that the staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems. 18.9% were in the middle who did not agree or disagreed. The third statement was about the interaction between staff and students feel safe. Over 67% of the students were on the agreement side of the statement, including 24.5% who chose the option of “agree”. Students who disagreed with the statement to different extents were under 19% of the respondents, and 13.2% of participating students were “neutral” about the statement.

5.2.2.5. Responsiveness

Responsiveness is about the willingness to help students and provide prompt service (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Students were presented with three statements in the questionnaire to analyse the perception of the responsiveness aspect of service quality. The statements and the responses are presented in figure 5.10. The first statement of the responsiveness aspect of the HESQ was about the administration staff being efficient and supportive. Around 64% of the respondent agreed with the statement to different extents, including 24.5% as “more or less agree”. The combined disagreement from the statement was 17%, and 18.9% of the student neither agreed nor disagreed.

Figure 5.10: Responsiveness Aspects Of HESQ

The second statement was about the timely delivery of student services. Around 53% of the responding students agreed with the statement on different levels, including 18.9% who “strongly agree”. The combined percentage of the students who disagreed was 26.4%, and 20.8% were “neutral”. The third statement was about the convenience of operating hours of student services. Around 68% of the respondents were on the statement's agreement side, including 24.5% as “strongly agree” and “more or less agree”. 18.8% of the respondents were on the statement's disagreement side, and 13.2% were neutral.

5.2.3. Student’s Experience Of HEI

In the previous section, the statement discussed were about the service quality aspects that students experience in particular and perceive to be satisfactory or otherwise. In this section of the instrument, the students were presented with statements about their experience and the satisfaction from that experience in broader terms. Figure 5.11 presents the statements presented and the responses of the students.

Students participate in a number of learning activities, according to Kotze and Plessis (2003), and they genuinely co-produced their education by contributing to their own satisfaction, quality, and value judgements. The first statement referred to the student’s feelings about his/her best interests being served by the HEI. Around 65% of the student agreed with the statement on different levels, including 26.4% on the level of “more or less agree”. 24.5% of the responding students did not agree with the statement about their feeling that the HEI is serving their best interests. 11.3% of the students stayed “neutral”. The second statement was about the consistency of rewards against the efforts put in by the student for the assessment/exam. Around 66% of the students chose the agreement option, including 26.4% who chose “more or less agree” as their response to this particular statement. 20.7% of the students did not agree with this statement, and 13.2% were “neutral”.

Figure 5.11: Students' Experience Of HEI

The third statement was about the feeling of enjoyment from the experience at HEI. Almost 68% of the students who responded to this statement agreed that the HEI I am enrolled in provides me with the feeling of enjoyment with the education experience. The respondents who disagreed with the statement were accumulated for 18.9%, and 13.2% stayed “neutral” in their response to this statement. The fourth statement related to the student experience of HEI was about the feeling of involvement with the HEI. Almost 63% of the student who responded to this statement were on the agreement side of the statement. The students who disagreed accumulated 20.7% of the respondents, and 17% stayed “neutral”.

The fifth statement refers to the feeling of uniqueness from being associated with the HEI. More than 62% of the respondents agreed with the statement on different levels. Around 17% of respondents showed their disagreement with the statement, and 18.9% of the responding

students were “neutral” about this statement. The sixth statement refers to the feeling of being intellectually challenged by attending the HEI. The students who agreed with this statement were around 58% of the total respondents, including 26.4% who were “strongly agreed” with the statement. On the disagreement side of this statement, there were around 19% of the students and 22.6% of the students were neutral.

5.2.4. Students’ Satisfaction With HEI

This section will cover the statements of the instrument, which were about the overall satisfaction of the students from the HEI after their experience. According to Wu et al. (2006), the level of satisfaction varies depending on the elements of the service or the characteristics of the students. In this section, the respondents of the survey were presented with three statements referring to satisfaction. The statements of this section, along with the responses from the students, are presented in figure 5.12.

The first statement was about the first impression of the HEI meeting the expectations of the students. Almost 70% of the respondents agreed with the statement, including 30.2% of “more or less agree”. Around 24% of the respondents did not agree with the statement about the HEI meeting their expectations of the first impression. The respondents who were “neutral” about this statement were 5.7% of the total respondents.

The second statement refers to the HEI meeting the expectations of the students regarding learning from HE. The students who agreed with this statement accumulated 58.6%, including 20.8% as “strongly agreed”. The students who disagreed with the statement were accumulated as 22.6%, and 18.9% of the respondents were “neutral”. The third statement of this section was about the HEI meeting the overall expectations of the students. 68% of the students who responded to this statement agreed with the statement, and 30.2% responded as “agree”. The combined percentage of the students who disagreed with the statement was around 15%, and 17% of the student were “neutral” about the statement.

Figure 5.12: Students' Satisfaction With Their HEI

5.2.5. Personal Development Of The Students

This section covered the statement about the personal development of the students as a result of their HEEs. In this section, six statements were presented to the students covering the personal development aspects. Figure 5.13 presents the statements and the responses of the participating students.

The first statement referred to HEI developed the students to solve problems efficiently. Around 60% of the respondents agreed with the statement, with 28.3% “more or less agree”. The combined disagreement with the statement was around 19%, and 20.8% of the respondents were “neutral”. The second statement of this section was about the HEEs in developing students to communicate effectively. Around 62% of the students who responded to this statement agreed with it, including 26.4% who “strongly agree”. The combined disagreement of different levels was 22.7%, and 15.1% of the respondents chose to stay “neutral”.

Figure 5.13: Personal Development Of Students

The third statement was about the HE enabled the development of the skills relevant to the industry. 58.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement to different extents, including 22.6% who “agree”. Around 30% of respondents disagreed with the mentioned statement, and 11.3% of students neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. The fourth statement referred to the development of general knowledge as a result of HEEs. Around 70% of the students who responded to this statement agreed, with 28.3% “more or less agree”. Around 11% of the respondents were on the statement's disagreement side, and 18.9% stayed “neutral”.

The fifth statement was about the better management and analysis of the information due to the HEEs. Around 70% of respondents were on the agreement side of the statement, with 28.3% “more or less agree”. Around 15% of the respondents were those who disagreed with the statement on different levels, and the percentage of “neutral” respondents was 15.1%. The sixth statement of this section was about the improvement in the level of integrity resulting from their HEEs. Around 66% of the students agreed that their level of integrity increased due

to their HEEs. The 66% includes 32.1% of those who choose “agree” as their response to this statement. 17% of the respondents disagreed with the statement, and 17% were “neutral”.

5.3. HESQ And Student Experience

The responses to the statements from the online survey were presented individually in the previous sections in accordance with the aspect of service quality, student experience, student satisfaction and personal development due to the HEE. This section will discuss the findings from the data in accordance with the first proposition formed in chapter 3. The first proposition was formed to find the answer to the first question referring to the positive relation of the HESQ aspects with the student experience as the positive perception of the aspects of the HESQ will have a positive influence on the student’s experience of the service.

The students were presented with statements based on the five aspects of service quality as tangibles, assurance, reliability, empathy and responsiveness. Table 5.3 illustrates the statements of each aspect and the accumulative positive (agree) and negative (disagree) responses. In the responses, the students choose to agree or disagree with the presented statements on different levels, from “more or less agree” to “strongly agree” and from “strongly disagree” to “more or less disagree”, along with the option of staying neutral about the statement. In the broader sense, staying neutral can also be considered as a disagreement with the statement.

As illustrated in Table 5.3, the percentage of agreement of the students with the statements for the tangible aspects ranged from 54.7% to 73.7%, and the range of disagreement from the statements was from 9.5% to 24.6%. These ranges of agreement and disagreement can be translated into satisfaction and dissatisfaction about the experience relevant to the statement, which can lead to a positive perception of the tangible aspects. For the assurance aspects of the service quality, the agreement percentages ranged from 58.5% to 71.7%, along with the disagreement range of 11.3% to 18.8%. This can also be translated into the student’s positive perception of the assurance aspects of the HESQ. For the reliability aspects, the student’s agreement with the statements ranged from 54.7% to 81.1%, and the disagreement of the students with the statement ranged from 11.3% to 28.3%. As mentioned, more than half of the students agreed with the statements, so this can be translated into a positive perception. The agreement percentage for the empathy statements ranged ranging from 52.9% to 67.9%, with the disagreement percentages ranging from 18.8% to 30.2%. The statements about the

responsiveness aspect of the HESQ ranged from 52.9% to 67.9% for agreement and from 17% to 26.4% for disagreement. This can also be translated into the positive perception of the responsiveness aspects of the HESQ.

Table 5.3: Statements And Responses

Section	Aspect	Statements	Comb- ined Agree	Neu- tral	Comb- ined Disag- ree
			Approximate %		
Aspects of Service Quality	Tangibles	There are sufficient facilities in the class/lecture rooms.	73.7	17	9.5
		There are sufficient learning resources in the university according to your course.	54.7	20.8	24.6
		The learning environment conveys a sense of competence and professionalism.	73.5	9.4	17
	Assurance	University's website provides complete information for decision-making.	64.1	17	18.8
		The induction was helpful in knowing the whereabouts of the university.	58.5	22.6	18.8
		The institute's communication network is up-to-date and efficient.	71.7	17	11.3
		The institute encourages confidence in students.	67.9	11.3	20.7

	Reliability	Teaching staff are consistent in the way they teach.	64.2	18.9	16.9
		Teaching staff are skilful and competent in what they teach.	81.1	7.5	11.3
		The overall service provided by the university is a good value for the fee.	54.7	20.8	24.5
		You will recommend this university to your friends and family.	56.6	15.1	28.3
	Empathy	Professors/lecturers are available to provide guidance other than the lecture times.	52.9	17	30.2
		The staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems.	52.9	18.9	28.4
		Students feel safe in their interaction with staff members.	67.9	13.2	18.8
	Responsive-ness	The administrative staff is efficient and supportive.	64.1	18.9	17
		Student services are readily available and delivered on time.	52.9	20.8	26.4
		Operating hours of student services are convenient for students.	67.9	13.2	18.8
	Student Experience	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling that my best interests are being served.	64.2	11.2	24.5
		The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling that the rewards gained are	66	13.2	20.7

	consistent with the effort I put into the assessment/exams.			
	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of enjoyment with the education experience.	67.1	13.2	18.9
	I feel involved with the HEI I am attending.	62.2	17	20.7
	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of uniqueness of being associated with it.	63.4	18.9	17
	The HEI I am attending gives me a feeling of anticipation and being challenged intellectually.	58.5	22.6	18.9
Student Satisfaction	The first impression of the HEI met your expectations.	69.8	5.7	24.4
	The HEI is meeting your expectations of higher education learning.	58.6	18.9	22.6
	The HEI is meeting your overall expectations.	68	17	15.1
Personal Development	My higher education experience has developed me to solve problems effectively.	60.3	20.8	18.9
	My higher education has developed me to communicate effectively.	62.3	15.1	22.7
	My higher education has enabled me to develop skills relevant to the industry.	58.5	11.3	30.1

	I have developed good general knowledge as a result of my higher education experience.	69.8	18.9	11.4
	My higher education experience enabled me to better manage, use and analyse information.	69.8	15.1	15.1
	My level of integrity improved as a result of my higher education.	66.1	17	17

The results show a positive perception of the aspects of HESQ, but it is also evident that for some statements, the percentage of agreement was very close to half of the total responses, which depicts that even though there is satisfaction from the aspects of service, there are visible prospects of improvements. This positive or negative perception directly influences the kind of experience students to have while receiving or utilising the different aspects of service. Based on the results presented above and in Table 5.3, it is evident that the aspects of HESQ have a positive influence on the student's experience.

There were some open-ended questions in the section on service quality aspects, asking the respondents to share their opinion about the different aspects or prospects of improvement. Out of the 53 respondents, 36 respondents answered the open-ended questions for this section of the questionnaire. The students mentioned the infrastructure and facilities in the classrooms of the HEIs as *"noise of the fans makes it difficult to focus on the lecture"*. In relevance to the lectures and facilities, other respondents mentioned the availability of the lectures online and the need for a student portal where students can access them at any time, as *"lectures should be recorded and updated on a portal"*. In the area of online facilities, many of the respondents mentioned the digital library and access to the databases with the latest research papers. One of the respondents said about the required facilities, *"e-library with enough published papers"*. One of the respondents complained about the shortage of materials and equipment in the laboratory as *"there is always a deficiency in performing the relevant courses practical"*.

Students were also concerned about the lack of practicality and creativity in the courses. A respondent mentioned, *"course should build creative and practical skills of students"*. Many students were in favour of using the *"practical approach"* and *"research paper-based"*

knowledge” along with the “*real base examples*”. There were suggestions about the development of the course according to the industry by “*linking academia with industry*”. The students were also concerned about the cooperation from the teaching and non-teaching staff and the need to train and develop the HEI staff as well as the environment, including the “*classes timing*” and “*listening to the student's problems*”. Some of the students referred to the importance of the teacher-student interaction as “*teacher-student interaction must be accessible and efficient*” along with the “*more interactive teaching method and exam criteria as real situations*”. All of the students who responded to the open-ended question gave their opinions in a single or few words, but there were some students who responded to these questions in some detail. One of the respondents commented in detail about the aspects of service quality as “*teaching staff should be cooperative with the students. Administrative management should be effective and active. Students should be provided with all learning facilities and resources related to the course. The fee should be according to the facilities provided to the students. The course should build creative and practical skills of students rather than leading them to cram*”.

5.4. Satisfaction From The Experience And Personal Development

This section will discuss the findings from the data in accordance with the second proposition formed in chapter 3. The second proposition was formed to answer the second question referring to the positive relationship between satisfaction from the HESQ experience and the student's personal development. The relationship will be examined based on the results presented in Table 5.3. As the findings for the aspects of HESQ are discussed in section 5.1.6, the findings of the student experience, student satisfaction from the overall experience and personal development will be discussed in this section. These ranges of agreement and disagreement can be translated into the satisfaction and dissatisfaction about the experience students have relevant to the statements, which can lead to positive or negative perceptions.

The responding students agreed with the statements about the experience of students with the service provided in the HEIs in the range of 58.5% to 67.1%. The same statements were disagreed with by the range of 17% to 24.5% of the students who participated in the online survey. As it is apparent from the mentioned ranges of agreement and disagreement and findings presented in table 5.3, the students of HEI are more inclined towards satisfaction from experience and therefore have a positive perception of it. The range of agreement with the statements in the student satisfaction section of the research instrument was from 58.6% to

69.8%, with a range of 15.1% to 24.4% of students disagreeing with the same statements. The responses can be translated into satisfaction from experience.

The last section of the online survey questionnaire was relevant to the perception of the students about their personal development as a result of their HEEs. 58.5% to 69.8% of the responding students agreed with the statements about their personal development from the HEE, and 11.4% to 30.1% of the respondents disagreed with the same set of statements.

The discussed findings of the research portray the positive perception of the student experience, satisfaction and personal development but like the previous section, the lower ranges of agreement with the statements are close to half of the total responses. Based on that, it can be said that even though the overall responses depict agreement with the statements, there are visible prospects for improvements. The agreement with the statements is translated into a positive perception. Based on the findings discussed above and presented in table 5.3, it is apparent that student satisfaction from experience has a positive influence on their personal development.

The other sections also had open-ended questions at the end of each section as well. The open-ended questions were added to allow the respondents to express their opinion in more detail about any of the mentioned aspects, or they could introduce something which was not part of the statements. In the sections of experience, 30 students responded to the open-ended question. For the experience improvement, one of the students suggested: *“introduce some technical or analytical challenges in the course”*. Some of the respondents were inclined towards the *“practical exposure”* as an element of improvement, while others were concerned about the personality aspects of the students and asked the institute to *“show enough empathy”*, provide *“proactive student counselling”*, and *“manage the workload of the student”*.

In the section on student satisfaction, 30 students responded to the open-ended question. In this section, the students expressed their views about different dimensions, which can improve the students' satisfaction. One of the students mentioned the availability of scholarships for students based on their academic performance. Some students mentioned that a *“practical approach, more focus on skills, career counselling and listening to student's problems”* will improve their satisfaction levels. Using technology for the improvement of service by *“providing lectures online”* along with *“updating teaching style”* was also suggested by the respondents. A student mentioned the importance of feedback to improve the experience as

“frequent feedback of students about the curriculum, teacher, assessment and activities be collected and reformed”.

In the personal development section of the questionnaire, 25 students responded to the open-ended question. One of the students suggested calling guest speakers/ lecturers to increase the exposure of students and about the collaboration between different local and foreign universities, *“more guest speakers and lecturers, more exposure for the students by giving them a chance to attend courses at foreign universities”*. The importance of *“practical experience”* or internships and skills was also highlighted by many of the students in their responses.

5.5. Qualitative Findings And Discussions

This section will present the findings from the qualitative data collected in the form of semi-structured interviews with the teaching and non-teaching staff of the Pakistani HEIs as internal stakeholders and the industry professionals as external stakeholders. The semi-structured interview script was divided into three main sections participants’ demographics, service quality and personal development. The demographic section covered questions about the education, experience, and industry of the participants. The service quality section of the interview consists of the guide questions about the HEIs meeting the expectations, facilities and resources provided by HEIs, a comparison of the HEIs in Pakistan and abroad, challenges faced by HEIs in optimising service quality and the recommendations to improve the service quality of HEIs.

The third section of the guide’s semi-structured interview script focused on the student’s personal development due to their HEE. The question in this section covered the aspects of skills development, cognitive and affective outcomes of HE, important aspects of HE, quality assurance, and student satisfaction. The fourth section was added later into the guide script after the interviews of the initial few participants. The questions in the fourth section of the script we’re about the quality vs quantity issue, student-teacher interaction, single curriculum and vocational training.

5.5.1. Sample Demographics

The total number of participants in the semi-structured interviews was 12, including participants from both stakeholder groups. There were seven participants from the teaching staff of the HEIs, one participant was from the non-teaching staff of the HEIs, and five participants were from the industry working in different industries. The purpose of presenting

the demographic information about the respondents is to provide a generalised view of the participation and improve the quality of reporting (Kelley et al., 2003). Table 5.1 presents the demographic profile of the participants. It is essential to present the demographic information of the participants as one of the objectives of this research study is to identify the differences among the stakeholders regarding the perception of HE.

Table 5.4: Participants’ Demographics

Participants	Gender / Age	Highest University Degree	Job Role	Years in the job role	Industry	Total Experience in Years
P1	Male 33	MBA	Digital Transformation Manager / Motivational Speaker	4	Telecom	9
P2	Male 34	PhD – Finance	Assistant Professor	6	Education	6
P3	Male 35	MPhil – HR	HR Digitalisation	6	Banking	10
P4	Male 37	MBA	Manager Organisational Development	7	Banking	10
P5	Male 38	M.Com	Superintendent HR	8	Education	14
P6	Male 41	MPhil HRM	Assistant Professor	8	Education	21

P7	Female 29	Ms Electrical Engineering	Lecturer	2	Education	2
P8	Male 36	PhD – Mathematics	Assistant Professor	11	Education	11
P9	Male 37	MBA	Head of North Carrier Division	11	Telecom	11
P10	Male 42	MS	Assistant Professor	12	Education	16
P11	Male 40	MPhil – Marketing	Assistant Professor	12	Education	14
P12	Female 37	MBA	New Product Development	1	Food	2

The majority of the participants in the interviews were males; only two out of the twelve participants were females. One of the female participants was from the teaching and a non-teaching group of stakeholders, and one female participant was from the industry. The age range of the participants was from 29 years old to 42 years old.

In terms of the education of the participants, all the participants from both stakeholder groups had achieved at least a master's degree. The experience of the participants in their current job roles ranged from one year to twelve years. The current job role experience range of the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders ranged from two to twelve years. The current job role experience range of the industry professionals ranged from one year to eleven years. The overall working experience of the participants of the study ranged from two years to twenty-one years.

5.5.2. Thematic Analysis Table

Based on the manual thematic analysis of the qualitative data collected for the study, a table has been developed to present the identified themes, sub-themes and codes. The discussion of the findings will follow the layout of the sub-themes to present the perspective of the stakeholders.

Table 5.5: Codes Generation And Themes Identification

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes
Higher Education Experience	Facilities and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well equipped with facilities and resources • Field of study and facilities and resources
	Practical Implication of Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concepts and implication • Local industry • Transition towards modernism
	Teacher-Student Interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of students in a class • Teacher-student relation • Quality vs quality • Quality of faculty
	University / HEI Tier and Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tier of University • Public sector vs private sector HEIs • Expensive Education • Student fee source of funding
	Student Segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student's background • Social life in HEIs • Zero semester • Selection criteria of students • Eagerness to learn • Co-education in HEIs

	Student Centric Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on student • Student coordinator • Student expectations and satisfaction • Customer experience • The communication gap between University and students • Stakeholders' experience
Personal Development of Students	HEIs Meeting Expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student expectations • Focus on covering basic course • Lack of curriculum improvement
	Skills Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on Skills • On the job learning • National vs foreign degree • Communication skills and field of study
	Learning Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to build confidence • Continuous personal development • Learning via the internet
	Student's Exposure and Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scholarships • Add value to students • Student exposure and training • Student's well being • Tolerance for differences
Industry's Potential, Expectations and Role	Industry's Potential and Expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry's potential • Student's concern about the job • Industry expectations • The pace of economic growth • Student evaluation • Market demand and supply
	Industry's Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry academia liaison

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government needs to develop opportunities • Job relevant to the degree
Service Quality of Higher Education	Innovation Vs Set Patterns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online classes due to Covid-19 • Innovative vs traditional • Teacher's individual efforts • Research orientation
	Collaborations and Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdepartmental collaborations • Collaboration with foreign HEIs • Funding and HEC grants • HEC policies • Lack of national research direction
	Politics and Corruption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine like a business • Politics, corruption, and nepotism in HEIs • Government intervention

5.5.3. Higher Education Experience Of Students

This section will discuss the findings related to the student's HEE as it is perceived by the two stakeholder groups. This was the first theme identified during the analysis. With the duration of the process and the range of variables that impact it, the HEE as a service is highly complicated. The degree of quality of such a service is significant since it influences impressions of the overall educational experience (Cerri, 2012). The finding and discussion will be presented according to the sub-themes identified and presented in Table 5.5.

5.5.3.1. Facilities And Resources

Adequate and appealing university facilities substantially influence teachers, student recruitment, and staff retention (Lavy and Nixon, 2017). Many HEIs depict good performance by optimised utilisation of their available resources (Vasudevan, 2021). HE students are enrolled in the HEIs with the aim of learning and personal development. Their experience with

HEIs involves all the direct and indirect aspects of the HE services. Their experience is perceived by the stakeholders differently than by the students themselves. The perception of service quality also differs from internal stakeholders to external stakeholders. Based on their perception, the participants can be divided into three groups. The first group shared the view that sufficient facilities are provided, the second group was of the view that the facilities are there but should be improved, and the third group differed in the view as they believed that the facilities provided are not enough or not provided to all the field of studies. One of the participants of the study, participant 1, who was from the industry practitioner group of the stakeholders with nine years of overall experience working in the industry, mentioned the facilities available for the students in the HEIs.

The universities are well equipped in terms of facilities, whether it is universities in the cities or in the rural areas. They have a good space in terms of classrooms. The classrooms are clean. They have multimedia facilities in the classrooms. They have the technological aid available like the Internet, technology lab, engineering lab etc., so in terms of facilities, everything is there.

This view was not shared by most of the participants from the teaching and non-teaching groups and from the industry practitioner's group of stakeholders. One of the participants referred to the HECP, which is the governing body for all the HEIs in Pakistan and is responsible for devising policies regarding the operations of the HEIs. The new rules and regulations of HEC are positively impacting the facilities in the HEIs. Participant 10, who has been working in the education industry for the last twelve years, was of the view about the resource limitation as:

In Pakistan, I think very limited resources are provided to the universities and students apart from textbooks. Resources wise our students are lacking a lot. Particularly if you compare it with the international context, we are at a bare minimum level.

The disadvantage of HEIs in the private sector is the development of campuses without adequate physical and academic infrastructure to fulfil essential criteria (Qureshi, 2012). Another participant shared this point of view but from the angle as facilities and resources are available only in a few of the HEIs, which are in the major cities of Pakistan and are generally top-tier universities. It has been observed from the interviews that the resources and facilities are generally available but are not up to the standard of modern education requirements at advanced levels and for all fields of study.

The students who want to pursue their educational ambitions in such a field have to go to elite institutes, which are very costly and are not affordable by the masses. Other than going to such institutes, they do not choose but to go abroad to continue their education. Some participants were of the view that these facilities should be enhanced and modernised. The facilities like a digital library and access to different databases should also be provided to the students.

5.5.3.2. Practical Implications Of Knowledge

The HEIs have limited time allocated for each semester. During that time, the teachers have to cover the basic course outline, which is being designed by the relevant departments of the HEI. There is not much flexibility in terms of what teachers could include in the course themselves. They are obliged to cover that course in that time duration along with taking exams etc. The knowledge is imparted via books only, on the lower level and, at times, on the master's level.

The students are guided to follow the books. This time limitation and set course boundaries at time results in the course being delivered just theoretically, and the recipient of the knowledge do not understand the practical implication of the concepts they have learned. The course materials must be updated as needed, and the programme should improve students' specific skills (Qureshi, 2012). It has been mentioned by most of the interviews that the focus of the HEI is on the delivery of lectures and completion of the theory elements of the courses. At times the courses taught are not relevant to the industry requirement anymore, but they are still part of the curriculum. Participant 12, from the industry practitioner's group, shared her perception:

They (HEIs) are just focused on covering the courses regardless of their relevance to the industry, regardless of their relevance to the current environment.

Another participant (3) from the industry practitioner group mentioned:

The curriculum has been the same since the 90s; what a student learns in B.COM or BBA or MSc stays the same. There's no improvement in there.

The world has moved on from imparting knowledge by using just books. The students are presented with real-life problems from the industry and are asked to propose a solution. Some institutes in Pakistan are adopting such methods of education from the very early stages of HE. The pace of adoption varies based on different factors ranging from funding availability to balancing the traditional mode of education with the modern mode of education. Participant

9 of the study has a working experience of 11 years along with being part of the visiting faculty of the HEI, shared his view about the use of books and other learning options as:

I think books are important, but I believe that more of a case study is the best learning. In the case of studies, you are discussing different organisations and learning with real-time examples. We need to encourage our students to learn from case studies, research papers, and even through games. Books are good, but the bookish knowledge is limited.

The time limitation for each course and the lack of drive to learn in students, and the lack of drive in the staff of HEIs to improve the quality of service are also aspects that need to be considered while discussing the implication of knowledge. The students are not aware of the importance of the conferences and workshops and how they can develop them. The arrangement of the research conferences and skill enhancement or development workshops requires additional efforts by the members of the HEIs, along with their regular duties. Another participant 2 from the teaching and non-teaching group of the stakeholders mentioned his concern about students being confined to books and basic courses:

Conferences and workshops are not encouraged, and students are not motivated to attend. This is the reason that students are mostly consulting just books, and they do not have any other form of knowledge which creates problems when the student goes into the market after their education.

Participant 5 from the industry practitioner group of stakeholders also shares a similar perception saying:

Universities are only taking fees and teaching the basic course and not moving towards the research-based program seminars are arranged.

Generally, students lack awareness and motivation to take part in such activities. One of the participants mentioned the use of examples from the American and European markets. The examples used to make the student understand the concepts are generally from the American and European markets. The use of examples from other markets is a good approach, along with examples from Asian and, specifically, Pakistani markets. Such practices develop the concepts in students, but at times they cannot create relevance to the local markets themselves and struggle when they join the industry.

5.5.3.3. Education Process Not Evolved

The participants of the interviews were asked about their HEE along with the HEE of the current students. It has been observed that half of the participants were of the view that the evolution of the education process or the delivery of education had not taken place at all, or it is very slow in comparison to the rest of the world, especially first-world countries. The other half of the participants were of mixed views, some linked the evolution with the access to resources, and some liked it with the effects of Covid-19 and the shift towards online classes and exams, which was nowhere in the perspective of the HEIs. They commend the steps taken by the HEIs to adapt according to the pandemic situation. Participant 11 from the teaching and non-teaching group of the stakeholders, with twelve years of teaching experience, shared his views:

Services are acts, efforts, and processes. Acts, efforts, and processes can be innovated, but in the end, the core of every actual process remains the same. People have been getting an education the same way, and the difference is how you conducted the process.

The basic service remains the same, but the mode of service delivery has changed. The advancement in technology has resulted in the more smooth and more efficient delivery of service. The use of laptops, access to a digital library, multi-media, access to the internet etc., are a few of the elements which make the difference in education delivery. The applications like Zoom and MS Teams have enabled the continuity of education during the pandemic. One of the participants mentioned this pandemic as a blessing for the HEIs in terms of their improvement and shift towards online learning. According to the situation, this adoption was more prominent in the case of the private sector and semi-government sector universities. The response from the government sector universities was slow as compared to the private and semi-government sector universities, as mentioned by Participant 3 of the industry practitioners group:

Especially private sector universities have taught complete semesters online. They have followed the HEC guidelines and provided the same level of service as on campus. The government sector did not respond as promptly.

5.5.3.4. Teacher-Student Interaction

Teacher-student interaction is one of the critical elements of the students' traditional education delivery and HEE. The interaction with the teachers in and out of the classroom is an important factor in improving students' impartiality, motivation, and contentment (Malik et al., 2010). The students learn from the teacher not only about the course but also about the other aspect of life. As mentioned by participant 2 of the teaching and non-teaching group, who has been working in the education industry for the last six years:

When the students enter the classroom, they observe their teachers, how they are dressed, how they communicate, and how different arguments are presented by them. So, the teacher plays a major role, and if they are provided with training on how they can become role models, this will definitely impact the student's personal development.

Teacher quality is one of those factors which closely influence the educational outcomes of the students (Hanushek et al., 2005; Dinh et al., 2021), and it plays a crucial role in the professional success of the students (Postema and Markham, 2018). Unfortunately, student-teacher interaction has reduced a lot in the past few years. One of the reasons is that teachers are teaching in multiple universities at the same time. They only come to the university at the time of their lecture and leave right after. The out-of-the-class interaction of teacher and student plays a vital role in the student's personality development, and at times this allows shy students to ask questions they cannot ask in class.

The study participants were all agreeing that the interaction between teacher and student has reduced, but they had a different opinion about the causes of this reduced interaction. Some are of the view that teachers are teaching in multiple universities and have too many students to deal with, and they do not have any time left for such interactions. The following statements are from participant 3 from the industry practitioner's group described the situation regarding the interaction:

Teachers are teaching in multiple universities, and they cannot interact with each student individually, the way it used to happen in our time. The students are lacking the learning which takes place through student-teacher interaction. Some of the reasons are the increased population, teachers teaching in multiple universities, students being busier now etc. all this is creating a gap in the student-teacher

relationship, and the teachers cannot share their practical experience with the students like they used to do before.

The reasons for the lack of interaction, as mentioned by participant 3, are the commitments of teachers with different universities and also the busier lifestyle of the students in the current times. Another reason for the reduced interaction is the general increase in population and class strength. This reduced interaction results in a lack of experience sharing from the teacher with their students, which ultimately results in less learning for the students. This experience sharing had reduced a lot as compared to the time when the participants were in education. Similar thoughts were shared by participant 9, who is also from the industry practitioner group, along with teaching at the university.

The face-to-face interaction has reduced because the quantity has increased. In our time, there were fewer students, and the teachers were able to give more time to each student.

The others were of the view that the students were not making an effort to reach for the teachers. They are friends with them on social media, but they do not come to the teachers when it comes to learning. The students are busy with other things like social media etc. One of the participants (10) from the internal stakeholder group, who has been in the profession for the last twelve years, gave his own example in relation to the matter and said:

When I started teaching, and I was not married, I was available for my students 18 hours a day which is not the case now. Interaction is still possible today online etc., but there has to be some initiative from the students as well. Teachers are usually available, but if the students are not ready to adopt the technology and use it to interact with teachers, then I think the problem is somewhere else.

This perception of lack of effort from the student in terms of interaction with the teacher was shared by other participants of the same stakeholder group. It was also evident from some of the responses that teachers feel the level of respect students used to have for teachers has reduced. This could be due to their interaction over social media platforms and considering the teacher as their friend.

Another participant from the internal stakeholder group mentioned the open-door policy of the teachers that teachers should have their doors open for students all the time regardless of the location, and whether they are on the cricket ground or in the university, the student should

be able to ask questions to teachers. There need to be some limits to this interaction as well because if the teacher is available all the time, the student might be less considerate of the personal space or time of the teachers, as mentioned by participant 6 from the teaching and non-teaching group:

The students need to show courtesy. They should not take too much liberty. If I am giving them value, they should give me value as well.

It has been observed that universities are giving admission to a higher number of students per class. There are multiple reasons for the higher admission rates in universities, like overall population, the fee paid by the student as the primary source of funding etc. This results in an increased burden on teachers. There used to be 30-40 students in each class, and teachers were able to focus on each student, but now this number has reached up to 90 and 100 and to teach this raised number of students. There is only one teacher. At times, they have help available, but the burden of workload has increased, which impacts the quality of education imparted and the results.

A couple of universities have adopted a change and reduced the number of students in each class and limited the number to 35. This approach has resulted in improved results in the form of the student's academic performance along with the skills developed in the student. Participant 12 from the industry practitioner group, summed up the situation of the number of students in each class and the burden on the teacher leading to reduced interaction as:

Universities, in order to increase their funding and their liquid assets, they enrol more students. When more students are enrolled, the funding will be divided over the span of those students, so I think the quality is being affected. Secondly, I think the limited number of faculty members for a large number of students, so the student-teacher quality interaction is also compromised, impacting the quality results that students are producing in their academic careers.

5.5.3.5. Quality Of Faculty

The quality of faculty is about the competence, personality, emotional intelligence and qualifications of the teaching staff, along with friendliness and communication skills (Qureshi, 2012). The quality of the faculty of the HEI also impacts the student's HEE. Some teachers adopt a teaching strategy that is different from others. In general, the choice of one strategy over another is connected to the teacher's judgments of the content, context, and demands of

various learning activities (Edmunds and Richardson, 2009). During the interviews, many participants referred to the importance of the quality of faculty in the process of education service delivery. The training and development of the teachers should also be part of the university policy. The continuous training of the teaching staff with respect to the development of the industry will lead to improved service as the teachers will be more equipped. Participant 10 from the internal stakeholder group suggested that:

I recognise that teachers, particularly from the business and those who are in other faculties, every two years they must be sent to industry to do a semester of some real industry-oriented tasks. When they come back, they will be upgraded, and we will know exactly what the industry wants.

This point of view is also shared by participant 9, who has experience working in the HEI as a visiting faculty along with working in the telecom industry.

You need to improve the skills set off by the teachers by giving them further education and by giving them training.

The teachers who are providing service as full-time teachers, at times, cannot stay up to date with the current trends in the industry; such training and development programs for teachers are beneficial not only for them but also for the students as well. Along with teacher training, the course content needs to change and be adopted according to the local industry. Participant 11 from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders said:

You cannot always expect a teacher to modify the courses. We are as distant from the industry as students are. I have been teaching her for the last 12 years, and I have not been part of the industry for the last 12 years. The industry is changing every year.

The quality of the teaching and learning environment of the institution is the essence of students' satisfaction with their HEE since students want properly qualified, learned, and experienced faculty for their academic and personal growth. Students desire to be taught by teachers who have the necessary knowledge, skill, liberality, and reasonability (Malik et al., 2010). The suggestions about teacher training and development were made mainly by the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders, which indicates that there is a will and drive to progress in order to improve the teaching at the core, but there needs to be some initiative from the HEIs management and the governing body of the HEIs.

5.5.3.6. University / HEI Tier And Sector

The HEIs / universities are ranked into tiers based on the overall performance of HEC.

- Top tier
- Middle Tier
- Lower Tier

Along with this division, universities are also divided into three sectors as well.

- Government Sector
- Semi-government Sector
- Private Sector

The university's tuition fee is positively related to the university tier. Top-tier universities charge high fees, and the students graduating from the top-tier universities are also generally well-equipped with knowledge, practical implications of knowledge and skills. The available resources and facilities in different-tier universities also vary. Everyone wants to be part of these universities, but not all students can afford to be admitted to these universities even if they fulfil the merit criteria. The universities also target students from different backgrounds. As evident from the data collected, the top-rank universities mainly target students with strong financial backgrounds, those who are well-exposed and groomed. The middle tier mainly targets students from middle-class backgrounds. Participant 6 of the teaching and non-teaching group commented about targeting a specific segment of society:

In our institution, we target that segment of society which is the middle-lower to middle segment.

Participant 4 from the industry group of stakeholders highlighted the tier system from the accessibility to HE and the affordability of the HE point of view, along with addressing the class system as:

It is very expensive, and accessibility to HE is a very large gap. There is a need to make an economic sort of elevation of the country or build upon the educational gap. Your top-tier universities are beyond the capabilities of a normal individual. There is a sense of elitism and class, and that is a problem as well. So, the overall quality of education needs to be elevated to such a level that the classism element

is mitigated to its maximum extent and enables more people to have education, have the right to access equal education and also mitigate the inequalities between the top tier universities and the rest.

In the perfect world for education, things should not be like this, but due to the fact that student fee is the primary source of funding for universities, the occurrence of such market segmentation is inevitable. There is evidence that the learning facilities, access to resources, and infrastructure provided in top-tier institutes are far better than the other tier. Based on the discussion and data collected, it is generally assumed that a graduate from a top-tier institute will be better than a graduate from a middle or lower-tier institute. The assumption about the student from the top tier universities is not always accurate as well. Participant 6, who is a teacher, mentioned:

In one of the conferences which I was part of, there were individuals from different universities. From high-tier universities as well as from lower-tier universities. The person from a lower-tier university was more confident and quality-centric than the higher-tier university.

This could be the case with the individual efforts of the student. However, generally, employers prefer the individual from the higher tier university over the individual from the lower tier university. This is due to their assumption of the quality of the graduate in terms of their knowledge and skill set. While answering the question about the development of industry-relevant skills as a result of HE from the industry practitioner group Participant 4 mentioned:

It varies from institute to institute. Top-tier universities, I feel, are doing a better job. There are lots of graduates from these universities who are doing well and performing well. When we go down to the tiers, the proportion of students who have the skills starts declining, and it continues to decline as you go down the line.

When we analyse the universities based on the sector, there are hardly any government sector universities that are in the top tier. Most of the top-tier universities in the top tier are from the private sector and semi-government universities. In general, government-sector employees are not as driven as private-sector employees because their job is more secure, and job security does not depend on performance, whereas in the private sector, the job is secure only if the

individual is performing. This generates drive and brings innovation and effectiveness. Participant 3 from the industry stakeholder group said:

Lack of ownership is the major reason for government universities not performing well. In the private sector, whether you are in the banking sector or doing a sales job or any other job, you are on the job only if you are performing.

In the government sector, the employees' salaries are also a factor that impacts the drive and motivation of the government sector employee to improve performance. Combined with the lack of ownership, the lesser salaries compared to the private sector result in lower performance and a lack of initiative. Participant 5, who is a superintendent of HR in a government sector university, linked the salaries and motivation as:

The salaries of government university employees are less, which demotivates them from working efficiently.

The differences in the universities based on their sector and tier are not just based on the overall performance of the university or the performance in a specific field. These differences prevail in the source of funding, the fee structure, the facilities provided, the infrastructure, the targeted audience, the quality of graduates, the level of self-confidence, communication and other skill etc. Even the teacher-student interaction differs in different sector universities. This scenario is mentioned by Participant 12 from the industry practitioner group, who has to be part of all three sectors as a student.

I have experience in a government university for my under graduation, a semi-government for my master's and a private university for my research degree. In government universities, students are highly dissatisfied because there is hardly any interaction between students and teachers from the lecturer's point of view. If you have any problem, the teacher is not available. In a semi-government university, student-teacher interaction is there, but it is not much productive, so student satisfaction is of average level. Now the university I am currently part of, there is a huge focus on student-teacher interaction, and that increases satisfaction levels to no bounds.

The universities mentioned by participant 12 were from different sectors and were also from different tiers. The government sector university with the least interaction was from the middle tier, and the semi-government university with the medium level interaction was also from the

middle tier. The private sector university referred to by the participant having a significant focus on student-teacher interaction is from the top tier.

5.5.3.7. Student Segmentation

All the students of HE cannot be equal. Students choose one of two approaches to learning based on how they see learning and how they see themselves as learners (Edmunds and Richardson, 2009). They can be divided into different segments, as mentioned by participant 11, from teaching and non-teaching groups:

Students can be divided into different segments, and you cannot say that all students have the same perception.

The student segmentation can be based on their:

- Background
- Exposure
- Communication and other skills
- Eagerness to learn
- Confidence
- Previous education
- Purpose of enrolling on higher education

The HEE of the student also varies depending upon the mentioned variations. Both groups of stakeholders mentioned the aspects of student segmentation. Hussain (2005) sees the segmentation of the educational system as a factor in the country's creation of a class structure. Following is the structure of education followed in the country; the quality of HEIs and the graduates generated by such institutions are influenced by class and background (Qureshi, 2012). Students belong to different backgrounds, some students come from financially sound families, and some students belong to other segments of society. Along with being financially sound, it also depends on if the student is from a rural or urban area.

The student's background generally relates to the level of exposure a student has before getting into HE. The schooling of the student also impacts confidence, exposure and knowledge of the student. Participant 11 from the teaching and non-teaching group mentioned:

Students who already have lots of self-confidence because they belong to those top families, in terms of their communication skills, they had good schooling, they had a good social life, this kind of students because they already groom, they catch of things pretty quickly, and I am not talking about their academic performance that has nothing to do with these things.

In schooling, there is an aspect of co-education. The majority of the schools and colleges are in rural areas, and many schools in urban areas are not co-education schools and colleges. For a considerable majority of students, universities or HEIs are the first institutes to study with the opposite gender. As referred by Participant 9 from the industry practitioners' group:

In Pakistan, you know that co-education is not very common. Nowadays, 75% of students will try to go into a co-education or some fun university.

The student who has been studying in a co-education school will respond to this scenario differently than the one who was part of boys only or girls-only institute. This issue seems very small but was mentioned by almost all the participants as this impacts the students, and it does impact the personal development of the students in the HEIs.

Students with access to better schooling and exposure ultimately are more confident and possess specific skills like communication. They can express themselves better than others. There is segmentation based on written and oral and the choice of language in communication. English is considered the official language in most institutes and workplaces, while Urdu is the national language of Pakistan.

It has been mentioned in the interviews by many participants that students be reluctant to speak or communicate in English. They understand the concepts and what is being asked of them, but they cannot express themselves in English. The stigma of language exists, which hinders the students from expressing their thoughts and sharing their ideas. The teachers can play a role of a motivator by motivating the student to express themselves in any language and at the same time keep learning and improving English as this will be the language used in the exams and the offices once they reach practical life. Participant 6 of the teaching and non-teaching group mentioned:

In Pakistan, we have various regions. If a person is from a little backwards region and has complexes like not being able to speak good English, it should not be like this. Teachers need to motivate that boy or girl that if you are not speaking good

English, it is not the end of the world. You can explain in your own national language.

The motive to get HE is also the point of difference that distinguish students from each other. Some students join the HEIs to improve themselves and to excel. They are focused on personal development and education. They keep on looking for new opportunities for personal development as well as scholarships and internship opportunities. Participant 3 from the industry practitioner group mentioned such students.

Some bright students take the initiative as well to grasp the opportunities like government internship programs where students are given the opportunity of one-year internships, where students can learn and gain soft skills and practical skills.

Some students are interested in the kind of job they can secure with a certain degree. Some are there just to enjoy the social aspects of the experience and be non-serious about the educational aspects of the experience. Some just want to pass and get the degree and are not bothered about the quality of education they are receiving. Others do not have any personal interest in education and are there just because their parents wish them to be there.

The student selection criteria are one of the steps somewhere the universities need to consider more aspects than just the marks of the students. Universities need to analyse the attitude and aptitude of the student as well as the level of personal development. Participant 10 from the teaching and non-teaching group commented about the selection criteria of the students as:

In this selection criteria, we should be able to differentiate between the students based on their attitude and personality rather than the numbers which they have secured in the previous programs.

Because when the students come from various backgrounds and with poles apart exposure, they should not be taught in the same manner. As mentioned by participant 6, who is from the group of internal stakeholders mentioned:

Students come from different backgrounds, from cities, from villages, from well-off families and from not very-well-off families. They all need to be treated equally.

The universities need to introduce zero semesters where they can work on the students and bring them all to a certain level in terms of their knowledge, skills and exposure. Once the students are accepted by the universities, then they cannot blame everything on the background

of the student in terms of knowledge and exposure. Participant 11, who has been in the teaching profession for the last twelve years, commented:

We cannot change their background, and we cannot entirely blame them for that. When they are here for two years, three years or four years, that is a lot of time; make sure that at least now they are trained and guided.

This student training and guidance can pace up their personal development. They have already decided to come out of their comfort zone with a will to develop skills and improve. If guided and presented with the opportunity, they can be as progressive as any other student from a favourable background. As mentioned by Participant 10, an internal stakeholder who has a similar experience with his education:

I think that when you are exposed to a radically different environment, that helps you to develop yourself. If you are treated with a bit of a change, that does not add much value. This radical environmental change is important, and that gives you a very much different and broad aspect of life, and you are more open to experiences, and your level of acceptability towards others improves a lot. It is a life-changing experience, but again it depends on the individual and how one takes it.

The eagerness to learn from the student is key in such situations. If the students are eager to learn and develop themselves, these hurdles of language and exposure can be looked at as personal development opportunities with the teachers' proper guidance.

5.5.3.8. Student-Centric Approach

The HEIs as a whole is providing education, and students are on the receiving end. In other words, the HEIs are providing a service and the students as the customers. The policies devised, rules and regulations formed, the infrastructure constructed, and the facilities provided should be focused on the needs of students. In theory, this is how the situation should be, but unfortunately, in reality, the services designed and provided are not student centric. HEIs should take a customer-centric approach to service design, focusing on understanding students' perspectives rather than gathering data based on what the institutions believe is relevant to students (Gruber et al., 2010). The universities are more focused on building the physical structures rather than on what facilities provided should be provided for the students in those physical structures. Participant 10, who is an assistant professor, mentioned that:

In a universal view, with regard to the institutions I have seen in Pakistan, our total focus is on building a physical structure. As far as the building is physically visible, everyone is impressed. The actual focus should be on security and facilities.

The processes and procedures of the administration, starting from the admission process till getting the degree, are designed to facilitate the administration rather than the students. Such experiences lead to dissatisfaction of the student with the overall service. The requests by the students about arranging events etc. are delayed in terms of response, and sometimes they do not even get the response. Participant 5, who is from the teaching profession, mentioned that:

Sometimes students want to organise some events, or some get-to-gather, but their application does not reach the right person to get the approval. Secondly, there is also an issue in the admission process that sometimes the admission forms get misplaced.

Participant 10 from the teaching and non-teaching group commented about the processes and procedures which cause delays in students' requests and sometimes problems and issues they face due to any reason. They lack support from the administration and their boundness to follow their set rules, as:

The services provided by the administration, in general, and to the students, in particular, need to be improved instead of treating students as football.

This type of experience does not leave a good taste for the students as it is a waste of time and effort for the students to try to organise activities. These activities also are opportunities for the student to learn and develop skills. Activities and projects enable them to learn and practice many skills, as mentioned by participant 7, a lecturer:

Students divide into groups to complete these projects, which involve project management, teamwork, time management, conflict management, etc.

Participant 5 of the teaching and non-teaching group also mentioned the role of coordinator for students who can help them represent their issues and demands in front of higher authorities.

There should be a separate coordinator for the male and female students who can represent students accordingly in front of the higher authorities.

The voice of students does not reach the top, and there is a communication gap between students and the university. Even data collected from the students generally and the feedback gathered at the end of each semester is nothing other than filling the quality assurance requirement of the HEC. The issues and aspects of concern highlighted by the students do not reach the top levels or the decision-making levels of the university. Participant 7, who is from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders, mentioned the gap in communication between students and the university or the higher authorities:

The communication gap between the university management and students is the key lacking in universities today.

5.5.4. Personal Development Of Students

This section will present the finding and discussion related to the identified theme of the personal development of students. The finding and discussion will be presented according to the sub-themes identified and presented in Table 4.1.

5.5.4.1. HEIs Meeting Expectations

The students join the HEIs with some expectations, including expectations about learning new knowledge, developing skills, enjoying the process and having certain facilities etc. The participants of the interview were asked about their opinion about their expectations from HEIs when they were students and the expectations of current students from the HEE. A clear majority of the participants said that their expectations were met by their HEIs, but almost everyone has said that the HEIs are not meeting the expectations of current students.

Participant 3, a banker:

There are so many new things in the market, and if you ask about the expectations of the students, I think universities are lacking in meeting the expectations of the current students.

Participant 5, HR superintendent:

No, universities are not meeting the expectations of the current students.

Participant 9, a visiting lecturer and head of the career division in the Telecom sector:

If you ask me honestly, I will say the quality of education, instead of getting better, has gone down. The reason is that most of the universities in Pakistan have been

commercialised. The race is not about quality; the race is about having the number of students, and there is a compromise you have to make once you go for a quality versus quantity race.

Participant 10, an assistant professor:

There is a gap all the time. The same goes for the best of the rest institutes.

The HEIs are focused on delivering the basic course, the curriculum has been set, and teachers have to follow that. That set curriculum is about course completion and developing the theoretical concepts, whereas the students join the university with the expectation that at the end of the course, they will be more developed not only in terms of having a degree but also have skills and practical knowledge. The dissatisfaction of expectations not being met can increase as well. This increase in dissatisfaction can be the result of experiences at work or when the student completes the degree and join another institute for further education in Pakistan or abroad. As mentioned by Participant 10 from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders:

Later, when I got the opportunity to study in the UK, that was a completely different game, a completely different pitch. That made me realise the deficiencies we have in the educational institutes in Pakistan, which is where one could not spot them.

5.5.4.2. Skills Development

Universities play a critical role in the training and qualification of their graduates, who are the primary outputs of the HE system; graduates are one of the essential components in the economic growth and development in any developing or developed country (El-Awady, 2013). The participants were asked about the skills like communication, problem-solving, negotiation, project management and conflict management and whether these skills are developed in the students as a result of their HEE. The participant had mixed views about the development of these skills in general and specifically about the industry-relevant skills. HEIs have the responsibility of generating graduates with the skills, competence, and knowledge that the industry requires (Oyo, 2010). The development of the skills can be linked with the student's eagerness to learn and develop, but the HEIs responsibility of developing the students is more relevant. HEIs are meant to engage and motivate the students and guide them along with providing them with opportunities for skills development. Participant 2, an assistant professor, mentioned the students' eagerness to develop as:

HEIs used to focus on developing skills, but as I said before, if the student is not focused completely on their education, there will be problems.

This point of view of HEIs is focused on developing the skills in the students was shared by participants 6 and 7 of the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders as well, saying:

Yes, to some extent, these skills are developed.

In HE, every student gets the opportunity to get involved in such skills.

In contrast, Participants 2 and 7 of the teaching and non-teaching group and Participant 9 of the industry practitioner group mentioned the focus of HEIs towards course completion in the given time and lack of focus on the skill development or personal development of the student from the HEIs as:

If you ask me on the face of it, I will say no. There are subjects on the University level which are being taught on these things but the complete personality and personal development that should be inculcated in the students that are not taking place.

The importance of communication skills, along with other skills, cannot be negated. As mentioned above, communication skills are also taught as a subject, and this is one of the most practised skills during the HE and specifically in the business and management-related courses, where students are expected to give lots of presentations and work on group projects. The perception of the communication skill of the students is not very different from the perception of the other mentioned skills. One of the participants from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders, participant 11, shared his view about the communication skills of the students in relation to the exams:

I would say that I have seen students who are in the final semester and who do not even know how to write a report, and they do not know how to construct an argument, even how to construct a sentence. They come to me later on and say, Sir, this is what I am trying to write; why did you score me less? I told them this was exactly what I was looking for in the answer, but I could not find that when I saw your answer. This does not mean that the student is not hard-working, or he did not understand the question, but he was not able to construct the argument. I think the way coursework is designed is not achieving its objectives.

This is understandable that this example cannot be implemented on all students, but this can be related to a large segment of hardworking students who come from a sort of background where they did not have many opportunities to learn and develop. A detailed discussion about student segmentation is in section 5.5.3.7. HEC can play a part by implying that universities offer such programs which develop and enhance the skills of the graduates. The introduction of zero semesters can be very helpful for these students. The skills development also varies based on the university tier, as mentioned by participant 4 from the industry practitioner group of stakeholders:

I have seen some institutions, which are Tier 1 universities, that have elevated these sorts of areas that have given students more practical application skills, but the majority of the educational institutions are still very far behind in building these capabilities.

Some of the participants were of the view that lack of skill development cannot be fully blamed on the university, teacher, or student. Everyone has to play their part in the development of the relevant skills in the students. Students need to be focused and serious about their education and skill development as universities provide the same education to everyone, and there are certain theoretical aspects that universities have to complete. Participant 3 from the industry practitioner group mentioned:

We cannot just blame universities because universities have a two years programme, and in those two years, they can give you the know-how of what things are but how one will perform those things, how he or she will survive in the market that is a different debate.

When it comes to industry-relevant skills majority of the participant from both stakeholder groups were of the view that HE and the students do not develop such skills once they join the industry and learn these skills on the job, which make the start of their careers hard as compared to those who are either the graduates from higher-tier universities or have the degrees from abroad. When hiring the candidate, foreign degree holders or higher tier degree holders are preferred over the others, but everyone does not have the opportunities or resources to get such degrees. The reason for the preference is based upon the practical approach, communication skills, along with other relevant skills development in those candidates due to their HE. Participant 5 of the teaching and non-teaching group mentioned:

Those students are up to date with the latest technology not only in terms of knowledge but also using that technology.

Participant 9 of the industry practitioner group of stakeholders mentioned his hiring preferences of the graduates with respect to their level of skill development in relation to where they graduated from as:

I believe that students from abroad are more in accord with our needs. If I have to hire someone in my team, I will go for an international student, or I will hire from two to three universities in Pakistan. I will go for a candidate from university A because they have good decision-making skills, or I will go for a student from university B or university C. Students from other universities are very good at following directions but lack decision-making or analytical decision-making.

These preferences were also visible with different justifications in the opinions of other participants as well. A student from a foreign university or tier 1 university will be better than a student from a lower-tier university, which is the perception that has been developed over the years by how the students have been performing in the industry. Even though this generalised perception is not as accurate as it is believed to be true, it prevails in the industry.

5.5.4.3. Learning Opportunities

One of the duties of the HEIs is to provide as many learning opportunities as possible to the student of various disciplines. These opportunities enable the students to not only learn better but also enable them to develop personally and professionally. Students' interest in their institution will be explicitly preserved when they view the institution's efforts to provide a quality and standardised learning environment aided by intellectual faculty, adequate learning facilities, and infrastructure (Alridge and Rowley, 2001). The academic, as well as administrative effectiveness of their school, motivates the students (Malik et al., 2010). Nowadays, with the facility of the internet, the learning spectrum is as broad as one could imagine. In providing opportunities to learn and develop, developing confidence is one of the opportunities that is provided to every single student. Participant 1 of the industry practitioner group of stakeholders mentioned:

They try to give you the opportunity to speak in front of your classmates or coursemates and present your ideas. This is a big opportunity here in Pakistan

because most of the students are shy and do not speak up. Public speaking is a rare skill you will find here.

As mentioned by the participant, the opportunity is provided, but not all of the students are of the same calibre in terms of using that opportunity and turning their weaknesses into strengths. The role of a teacher comes into play, and they need to motivate such less confident students to speak up more than others, and many teachers do try to boost such students, but as mentioned by Participant 6 from the teaching and non-teaching group:

Every teacher is not of the same calibre. Some have knowledge but cannot communicate, some can communicate but do not have the knowledge, and some have both.

The importance of seminars and workshops cannot be negated while discussing the learning and personal development opportunities for the students. The arrangement of seminars and workshops enables the student to learn new aspects from new people other than their teachers. The interaction with the national and international speakers and trainers opens new horizons for the students. Participant 2 of the teaching and non-teaching group mentioned:

Such conferences and workshops are not encouraged, and students are not motivated to attend. This is the reason that students are mostly consulting just books, and they do not have any other form of knowledge with them, which creates problems when the student goes into the market after their education.

There is a common saying, “when there is a will, there is a way”. The opportuning for learning and personal development are also available online. The online facility can be adopted by the university in the form of foreign faculty. This will improve the exposure of the students and will develop the skill to interpret the information and analyse the problems from a new angle. It has been stated that online learning has “succeeded in becoming an integral part of HE, and now it needs to turn its focus from providing access to university education to increasing its quality” (Lee, 2017, p.1). This is because online learning facilitates the use of asynchronous and synchronous interaction and communication within a virtual environment (Viberg et al., 2018).

5.5.4.4. Student's Exposure And Training

Student exposure and training are vital for their personal development. The exposure broadens the minds of students in general. Students who are more exposed to the trends, social media, and industry or have different experiences in life think and perform differently than those who have less or no exposure at all. The provision of training for the purpose of developing students will enable them to perform better right from the start of their carrier, but the scenario is different, as mentioned by participant 1 from the industry group:

The scenario in Pakistan is that majority of the new entrants learn on the job.

The lack of training and exposure can be linked to the findings and scholarships available. The students of the HEIs are considered the future of the industry by any country. Many countries have various funding and scholarship programs for students of HE, sponsored by the government as well as by the industry. Scholarships are provided under these programs to students matching the criteria. These programs not only motivate the students, but they also provide an opportunity to those students who could not have been able to afford them. The arrangement of seminars and training workshops for the students can make a difference in their personal as well as professional development. In Pakistan, there is a scarcity of such scholarship opportunities and training workshops, as mentioned by participant 5 of the teaching and non-teaching group:

The bright student does not have enough scholarship opportunities in the universities locally as well as internationally. There should be more job opportunities for students during and after completing their education. More and more seminars should be organised for student development focusing on student behaviour, psychology etc.

When the students have some industry exposure, their approach towards education becomes different from the approach of those students who do not have such exposure. This exposure helps them to understand the concepts and also the practical implication as well when they are in the educational environment because they have seen how work activities take place in the professional environment. Participant 11, who has been teaching at the university for the last 12 years and have worked in other industries before, shared his HEE. He had some experience working in the industry before he enrolled himself on the master's program.

When I went there, I had no problems in talking to females and understanding the concepts in class. The only development I had received was in terms of my career; passing those courses and learning new ideas, I came across new philosophies.

Along with the career-related personal development of the student, HE enables students to accept the views of others and gives them the spectrum of more than one right point of views about the matter or topic. In a single class, there are people with a variety of exposure, level of intellect and backgrounds, and everyone shares their opinion based on these variables. Participant 12, who have been part of the universities from different sectors and tier, shared her view about her personal development as a result of her HE:

I think overall, I have developed much tolerance for differences in point of view. This is what I have learned from my HEE. I find it really interesting to communicate with other people and know what they are doing, and my tolerance for others' opinions has increased due to HE.

5.5.5. Industry's Potential, Expectations And Role

The industry is one of the key stakeholders in HE. A large majority of the students are accommodated by the industry after they get their degrees. Being one of the key stakeholders, the industry has developed some expectations from graduates and universities. Along with expectations, the industry also has a crucial role in improving the quality of service of the HEIs, which will impact the quality of graduates' development, personally and professionally. This section will present the finding related to the theme of the industry's expectations and role.

5.5.5.1. Industry's Potential And Expectations

Industry's potential is one of the critical concerns for many students when they enrol in HE. A more significant segment of the students chooses the courses in alignment with the specific job they want to do upon completion of their degree. It is also a reality that only a few of the graduates get a job relevant to the degree. One of the factors is the less potential in the industry to provide employment opportunities for everyone. Due to this, graduates grasp any opportunity they get to be employed, regardless of relevance to their degree. As mentioned by Participant 5, who is from the teaching and non-teaching group of the HEI:

A person with a degree of M. Com is working as a medical representative, and a person with BSCS is working in the management field. This is a significant drawback because there is a high level of unemployment, so a person avails

whatever opportunity is there and gets the job. Even students with M Phil management or computer science start working in front-line marketing.

This aspect of job relevant to the degree in the context of the industry's potential was also discussed by Participant 12 from the industry professionals' group:

It is just a matter of squeezed economic conditions. People's jobs and their education, I do not think that there is much relation between them.

One of the reasons for graduates not getting jobs in the relevant fields is the pace of economic growth in Pakistan, which has reduced compared to the pace ten years ago. There was a boom in the market, and economic activities were growing. The economic conditions in Pakistan are not as good. Another factor to be considered is the market trends and what the industry is expecting from the fresh graduates along with the educational degrees. The graduates are expected to have relevant skills and certifications. Many students do attain these skills and certifications to differentiate themselves from others and make them fever able for the job.

The industry is also inclined towards such graduates who have such certifications. The ever-growing population is another factor that influences the job market, and the supply of candidates is higher than the demand for the candidates. Due to this lack of potential in the industry to provide opportunities, the competition in the job market is very high in Pakistan. There is a need to achieve a balance of opportunities and the number of graduates. Achieving the balance between supply and demand is something that requires continuous coordination between HEIs from one side and the industry from the other side (Ahmed, 2020). While comparing the HEE of current students and market conditions with his time in HE and the market conditions at that time, Participant 9, from the industry group of the stakeholders, mentioned:

If you see right now, the economy is not growing as fast as the number of students. The number of students coming out of universities is really high, and the industry is not geared up to accommodate all of them. Secondly, the industry used to go for the University degree only, but now the trend has changed, and they look at the relevant skillset and certifications as well.

The current rules and regulations of the HEC allow every university to open campuses in any city they wish if the university can full fill the requirements of the HEC. Now there are many universities of all three tires that have campuses in multiple cities, targeting students from different segments. The number of students in each university in general and each class

specifically give rise to some concerns, which are discussed in the previous sections of this chapter. All these university campuses in different cities and especially major cities of Pakistan, are producing a large number of graduates bi-annually. As mentioned by Participant 2 from the teaching and non-teaching group:

Supply is greater than demand in the market. This excessive supply is due to the fact that HEC has allowed different universities to open their campuses. Now even in some small cities, there are 4-5 campuses.

5.5.5.2. Industry's Role

The industry's potential and expectations from the students are one side of the equation, and the growing population and number of students, as well as the quality of the graduates, are the other side. There is a need to create equilibrium. There is a desperate need for the HEIs to understand the needs of the industry. In a general view, HEIs are educating and developing the students to be part of the industry, in one way or the other, upon completion of their education. There is a need for the industry-academia liaison to design and introduce courses that enable student development in accordance with the industry's needs. This is only possible if the HEIs and industry are more connected and understand what the industry is expecting from the HEIs in the form of the students. As mentioned by Participant 9 from the industry practitioner group:

The linkage between the industry and the University is very important. Once we have the linkage, then you will know the expectation level of the industry.

This linkage is beneficial for both industry and HEIs, and it will also boost the confidence of the students. Their performance will improve as they will be educated in accordance with the industry. As mentioned by Participant 12 from the industry practitioner group:

I think if there is a collaboration between the university and industry, this will improve the overall confidence of the student when the student is going to complete his or her degree.

To understand the industry's needs and to develop the courses and content according to that, there has to be some input from the industry. Once the industry provides the input, realistic programs can be introduced. One way to have input from the industry is to appoint some professionals from the industry to the Board of Directors or in the decision-making positions related to courses and the content of the courses. In this way, the graduates produced due to the

education process will be of better quality and will have more opportunities available in the market rather than competing for the few. Participant 11, from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders, mentioned:

This is not difficult; you can have a few people from the industry on your Board of studies. They can see what has been taught, and they can introduce new courses.

The efforts need to be made by both HEIs as well as the industry. Traditional forms of HE continues to play a vital role in education, but these institutions' partnerships with industry, government and other organisations need to be strengthened significantly (Penprase, 2018). Some of the participants of the semi-structured interviews were of the opinion that both HEIs and the industry are not taking this seriously. They referred to the first world countries saying that the courses are designed according to the market needs in those countries. The industry needs to give input, and the HEIs and HEC need to be ready to accept that and make changes accordingly. Participant 10 from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders mentioned the seriousness of both parties:

The solution is very simple, and that is getting the industry to tell you what they need and realign our product offerings in the form of students because they are our product. Customising the products and services according to the need of the industry serve everybody very well, teachers, students as well as the country. If that is not done, no matter how much you polish the offerings, they will not do the charm.

He also mentioned that:

It is the university's job to get the students ready for the industry. The issue is that universities or even industry are not serious about connecting with each other.

The collaboration between the two can generate many opportunities for the students, including scholarship and training opportunities. The government can also play the role of mediator to create the linkage between the two. Government regulations can be imposed on the industry to provide such opportunities to students. The government's overall policy for the industry and the proper steps towards economic development can result in opportunities creation in accordance with the number of graduates. As mentioned by Participant 6 from the teaching and non-teaching group:

Government needs to develop opportunities according to the number of students coming out of the institution. It is not about numbers; it is about how you hit the target of providing opportunities.

5.5.6. Service Quality Of Higher Education

Universities have realised that their long-term survival depends on how good their services are and that quality sets one university apart from the rest (Tsinidou et al., 2010). This section will present the findings and discussion related to the sub-theme of the service quality of HE.

5.5.6.1. Innovation Vs Set Patterns

Universities have perceived HE as a product and have been compelled by competition to assess the quality of their services, redefine their product, and evaluate customer satisfaction in methods that service marketing experts are familiar with (Kotler, 1985). Innovation in terms of courses offered and the content of the courses is needed at the time, as the world is different compared to the last few decades. There are different technological aids available to deliver lectures and impart knowledge at one end, and on the other end, there are facilities like portable devices to enhance and pace up the learning. Access to knowledge and resources is a lot better now, and many universities are adopting modern systems to make it easy for students to utilise the available facilities. Participant 2 from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders mentioned:

With the passage of time, there is a transition towards modernism, and things will get better. The reason I am saying that is because Smart Mode is getting more and more common in Pakistan. Whatever is discussed in the class is available for the students on their portals.

Such facilities are a blessing for those students who, for some reason, were not able to attend the university. They can access it from the portals. It seems very common in American and European HEIs, but in the countries like Pakistan, this is a comparatively new addition to the service provided and is still not very common. The arrangement of online classes and exams, as discussed in section 5.5.3.3, is one of the steps towards improvement. Even though that was forced by COVID-19, the transition time was impressive, as mentioned by Participant 3 from the industry practitioner group:

People say coronavirus is a problem, but for some, it was a blessing in the same manner universities have taken this as an opportunity to shift towards online education.

The delay in the adoption of innovative education models is one of the reasons universities are lacking in research orientation. Excluding a few, universities are lacking in research lab facilities and overall research orientation. The students are not motivated and are not provided with appropriate facilities to conduct the research. Students who can afford to go to foreign countries to continue with their area of research. Participants from both stakeholder groups mentioned this lack of research orientation. Participant 9 from the industry practitioner group of stakeholders highlighted the matter as follows:

The research orientation is very limited in Pakistan, whereas students in the UK, Australia and the USA have more materials and resources.

Even though not all universities provide an environment favourable for the students to be motivated to conduct research, there are many teachers who provide guidance and motivation to their students. They help them and guide them towards opportunities as well. Participant 5, who has been performing a job role of HR Superintendent for the last eight years and has been working in the education sector for the last fourteen years, mentioned the support provided by the teachers along with the lack of resources in the universities as:

The teachers guide their students to the maximum extent, including helping them to get scholarships. Universities should give students a free hand in doing experiments. Labs have only a limited number of materials or equipment available.

5.5.6.2. Collaborations And Funding

Collaboration and funding are the two aspects of HE service which were mentioned by a majority of the participants. Collaboration was mentioned in the context of departments, local and international HEIs, public plus private sector HEIs and government, industry and HEIs. Funding was mentioned in the context of scholarships, provision of facilities, training and development etc. Collaboration can make a difference in terms of providing more opportunities for research and personal development for students with limited funding. It can also attract funding from partner organisations for certain aspects.

The lab facilities of one department are generally not available for the other departments, and if they want to use those facilities, there are many procedural delays before they get the permissions. Since a lab in a particular department of an HEI cannot cover all the educational aspects due to lack of funding, there is a need for interdepartmental collaboration, as mentioned by Participant 5 from the teaching and non-teaching group:

Students from different departments should be allowed to use the lab and equipment of the lab in any other department. Interdepartmental projects should be encouraged.

There are many HEC grants available from different perspectives, and even though HEC is the governing body of all the HEIs in Pakistan, these grants are available for the public sector HEIs only. Private Heis's primary source of funding remains the fee collected from the students. Along with interdepartmental collaboration, inter-university collaboration can also have a very positive impact on the quality of research as well as on the personal development of the students. This collaboration can be with international universities as well. There are some top-tier universities in Pakistan which are working in collaboration with international universities. Participant 12 from the industry practitioner group mentioned:

If universities increase their collaboration with the universities with better facilities, I think the satisfaction levels of the students will increase to no bounds.

Also, there is a lack of national research direction in Pakistan. Those who are pursuing the research are from their own interest and initiative. The research direction should be aligned with the industry. If the industry wants specific research to be conducted, they should be providing funding to the researchers as they will be the beneficiary of the research. The collaboration of government, industry and academia can improve the quality of research and can generate monetary benefits for the country as well as industry. Participant 6 from the teaching and non-teaching group mentioned the funding of government or industry-led research as:

I think they should be provided funding to do the research. If you do proper data collection, you need to spend Rs 60-70,000 on data collection. So, if a minister or an organisation requires certain data, they should provide funding to the students for data collection, so the student can go out and do research so that the money is

utilised properly. There should be proper checks and balances, but funding should be provided.

5.5.6.3. Politics And Corruption

Any business in any industry will be negatively affected by politics, corruption, nepotism, or favouritism. The same is the case with the education sector and, specifically, the HEIs. When a person in the decision-making position ignores merit and makes a choice for some personal gain (monetary or non-monetary), the organisation will suffer. Even if a teacher favours any student, this automatically compromises the fairness of the system. As suggested by Participant 7 from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders:

Lobbyism of teachers and favouring the previously enrolled students should be avoided.

The majority of the participants who mentioned politics and corruption were from the teaching and non-teaching group. This could be due to their first-hand experience, or they might have witnessed such acts. Often, a qualified and deserving individual for any particular position does not succeed due to a lack of political connections. When a non-deserving person fills in the space of the deserving person in the HEI, he or she cannot perform the duties efficiently. This ultimately affects the quality of service provided to the students. Even though this happens in the private sector HEIs as well, but it is more common in the government sector HEIs. Participant 4 from the industry professionals group mentioned:

A lot of times, we have people in power or in very strong decision-making positions who are not qualified enough, do not have the background or do not have enough experience to be in that position. This is the first challenge, particularly in the government HEIs.

Participant 11 of the study, who is from the teaching and non-teaching group of stakeholders, mentioned the challenges faced by the HEIs in optimising the service quality:

I think the two major challenges are bureaucracy and corruption third one is the lack of funding. The bureaucracy and nepotism in this industry, or in any other industry in Pakistan, lead to the selection of incompetent people. Even the institutes are run by incompetent people, so you cannot expect something good will come out of it.

These institutes are governed by HEC rules and regulations, including the rules about quality assurance aspects. There is a need to revise the policies about hiring in the HEIs, so the most competent person is selected for the particular position rather than the one with more political or non-political contacts. The need of the time is the direct intervention by the government into the education system, specifically at the HE level, to do the cleansing. Participant 5 from the teaching and non-teaching group mentioned:

There is a need for proper government involvement. HEC is there, but there is a need for more direct involvement with respect to the service provided to the students. There are many programs for faculty development, but there are no such programs for the students. The government needs to make sure that the students are fully facilitated. HEC is only focusing on universities and faculty but not students.

The purity of the system will allow competent individuals to attain decision-making positions. They will be able to make decisions that will benefit the students and improve the quality of service provided by the HEIs.

5.6. Differences Among Stakeholder's Perception In Pakistan

This section of the study will present the difference in the perception of the key stakeholders of HESQ in Pakistan. The presentation of differences answers the third question and will achieve the third objective of the study about the difference in the perception of stakeholders. The perception of service quality differs from person to person based on the differences in context (Lovelock and Wirtz, 2011) and cultural differences (Clemes et al., 2008). The differences are based on the primary data collected for this research study.

5.6.1. Facilities And Resources

There were differences in opinions about the available facilities in the HEIs. The students expressed their opinion in the form of agreeing with the related statements, and around three-quarters of the students agreed that there are enough facilities and around half agreed about the sufficiency of the learning resources. The remaining students disagreed with the availability of suitable facilities and resources. The teaching and non-teaching groups mentioned the lack of facilities and resources, and they are, at the bare minimum level, limited to books. Some of the participants from the same group mentioned about availability of appropriate resources but

only in a few HEIs. The industry professionals group expressed their opinion by saying that nowadays there are good facilities and access to resources is available.

5.6.2. Practical Implication Of Knowledge

In terms of the practicality of knowledge, there were similarities in the three groups from which the data was collected. Students expressed their concern about courses being too theoretical, and they should be focused on building students' creative and practical skills. Teaching and non-teaching staff were concerned about the offered course content and their lack of freedom to improve or modify the content. They also expressed their opinion about the slow evolution of the education process. The industry group referred to the knowledge as outdated and not relevant to the local industry. They were of the view that the basic course is overemphasised, and there is a need to include real-time case studies which will enable practical learning and skills development.

5.6.3. Student-Teacher Interaction

Student-teacher interaction was mentioned by many participants of the interviews as well as mentioned by the respondents of the questionnaires. Many aspects of teacher-student interaction were highlighted during the interviews. The students mentioned briefly about the interaction in the open-ended questions that this aspect needs to be improved as it affects the student's experience of HESQ. The teaching and non-teaching staff also acknowledged the importance of the relationship and mentioned the reasons behind the lack of interaction, including the impact of social media and the lifestyle of students in the HEI. They also pointed out the issue of students in a class and mentioned the rationale for it.

The industry professionals also recognised the importance of the relationship. Their opinion about reducing interaction was focused on the lifestyle and commitment of the teachers with more than one university. The aspect of no student in the class was also evident in the opinions of this group of stakeholders as well. The differences in interaction between the teacher and students were also linked with the tier and sector of the university that it is better in private HEIs, good in semi-government HEIs and not good in government HEIs. The opinion about the tier and sector of the HEIs and HESQ was consistent in the interviews, and the opinions of the participants also had similarities. It was also evident that the industry prefers graduates from certain tiers or foreign qualified due to the perception of those graduates and their association with certain HEIs.

5.6.4. Funding

The fee paid by the student is the primary source of funding for the private sector HEIs and for semi-government HEIs. It is also an important part of the funding of the government sector HEIs. In terms of the tuition fee of the HEI, just over half the responding students agreed that it is good value for a fee, whereas a quarter of the students disagreed with the statement that the service they are receiving is good value for the fee, and the remaining were neutral.

It has been suggested that the facilities provided in the HEIs should be according to the fee charged. The teaching and non-teaching staff were of the opinion that the fee is according to the target segment of the students and the standard of overall service offered in different HEIs. The participants from the industry mainly stated that education, especially HE is expensive, and the government need to take steps to make it accessible for everyone.

5.6.5. Student-Centric Approach

The aspect of the student-centric approach was referred to by the students in relation to the administration and management that they should listen to the problems of the students, there should be less workload of students, and there should be the focus on the skills development along with the development of the concept. The perception of the teaching and non-teaching staff about the matter was more related to the infrastructure design and well-being of the student. They mentioned that the facility is designed by those who think they know what students need. The perception of the industry professionals was influenced by the resultant development of the student after the HESQ experience.

In terms of the HEIs meeting the student's expectations, the students generally seemed satisfied with their responses. The teaching and non-teaching staff perceived that the gap exists in the expectations of students from an HEI and what they get from an HEI. The industry participants believed that students are generally satisfied with their expectations until they are in education, but when they join the practical life, they realise that they were expecting less, and then their satisfaction goes down. The perception of the learning opportunities also varied amongst the stakeholders. The students perceive that they are provided with fewer opportunities, and the HEI and the government should be providing more opportunities in terms of scholarships, conferences and workshops, internships, learning and development etc.

The teaching and non-teaching groups perceive that such opportunities are not encouraged by the management, and the students do not get motivated to participate in such activities of

learning and development. Even if the opportunities are not announced or communicated properly, only the student who is self-motivated and takes the initiative grabs these opportunities. The industry group perceives this aspect of the service as there are some opportunities provided as part of the course, and the government is also offering paid internships, but most of the time, the students are unaware of such opportunities.

5.6.6. Role Of Industry

The role of the industry has been one of the main elements which all three groups in different capacities have addressed. The students were referring in terms of the relevance of the courses, case studies and examples from the local industry. They also mentioned the job opportunities and industry-academia linkage in this regard. The other two groups also emphasise the industry-academia liaison for the improvement of the HESQ and the resultant personal development of the student. There have been many propositions made in terms of the role of industry in the improvement of HESQ in terms of course content, training and development of the faculty, on-the-job learning, collaboration, etc.

5.7. Recommendations For Improvement HESQ in Pakistan

Institutes in Pakistan are not focused on satisfying their customers and improving their services as a result of it (Qureshi et al., 2008). This section of the study gives suggestions based on the findings of quantitative and qualitative research, as well as recommendations from stakeholders who took part in the study via survey and semi-structured interviews. The fourth question will be addressed by presenting the recommendations in this part for improving the HESQ service quality and the student's degree of personal development due to their HEE.

All three stakeholders have identified a number of concerns that influence both the positive and negative perceptions of the HESQ. Stakeholders have also given ideas regarding aspects that might improve the quality of service and contribute to the graduates' personal development. Graduates will have fewer challenges when they enter the job market if these recommendations are considered when the policy, course, and content are developed. During the research, several opportunities for improvement were discovered.

5.7.1. Recommendations For The HEI

To promote growth and development, HEI's management must guarantee that the best possible service is provided (Latif et al., 2017). The capacity to maintain service quality requires continuous improvement (Sunder and Sunder, 2016). Evaluation of service quality should be a

continuous process in HEIs instead of the end-of-term evaluation. Following are the recommendations for the management and administration of the HEIs, which can help them to improve the service quality of their institute.

- It is recommended that education sector managers broaden the scope of quality improvement to include student satisfaction, as it is crucial in shaping students' future behavioural intentions. For long-term revenue generation, HEIs should improve comprehensive service. To meet international educational standards, special attention must be paid to upgrading infrastructure and other auxiliary facilities, as well as improving students' communication skills, establishing efficient quality enhancement and job placement cells, and arranging industrial visits and study tours to enhance students' practical skills.
- It is the responsibility of the HEI to provide them access to the relevant resources and latest research so that they be aware of the latest trends in their respective field. Limiting the students to books only and expecting miracles puts a limit on the growth of students. HEIs have the models of top-tier HEIs in the country as well as the models of higher-ranking universities around the globe. For the improvement of the service quality, they should adopt a model which is the best fit for each HEI based on key elements such as funding requirements, human and technological resource requirements etc. It might not be suitable to adopt a model of a university in a developed country, but adopting a model of a university from a developing country can be the best option for the universities in Pakistan.
- The HEIs have to play a more active role in their relationship with the industry to improve the quality of service for their students. The industry is getting what is required in one way or the other, but the students of the HEIs are the ones who are struggling to present themselves as employable even after the degree and struggling to adjust after getting the job due to lack of readiness. This is the responsibility of the HEIs to educate the students to progress academically as well as in terms of skills development relevant to the industry. HEIs need to approach the industry for their input towards the development of course structure, especially those courses which are targeted towards specific industries. This will improve the service for the direct consumer as students as well as for the indirect consumer as an industry.
- The facilities and resources provided in many of the HEIs in Pakistan need to be brought up to the standard, especially in the HEIs campuses. The learning aid facilities starting

from seats with a suitable level of comfort to multi-media, should be available in every class/lecture room. There is a scarcity of resources in the universities as well as in the form of database access and access to the latest research. These resources are only available in the top tier institutes, which can be counted on fingers. Such facilities and learning resources must be made available to every HE student to provide equal learning and growth opportunities.

- There is a desperate need for improvements and redefinitions of the curriculum taught in the HEIs. This is one of the most repetitive issues highlighted by all three stakeholder groups. The HEIs should revamp the course offerings focused on the personal development of the students in terms of concept development, the practical implication of the concept and the development of the skills for the implication of the concepts into practice.
- The examples and case studies used are mostly from foreign markets, which can be good in conveying the concept but are not helpful for the student to create relevance to the local industry. The examples and case studies must be from the local market as well as from all levels of business activities to familiarise the students with the work practices.
- Based on the discussion in the previous sections, students join HEIs with variations in their experience, exposure, type of schooling, financial background, etc. They do be on the same degree level but on different levels with respect to the mentioned aspects, and their response to the education process also differs. There is a need to manage these differences right from the start of HE. The admission criteria must include the assessment of attitude, aptitude, and level of personal development along with the academic assessment. The students should be offered a zero semester covering the relevant courses to improve their communication skills, exposure, and experience before the start of the first semester.
- One of the very important aspects of the HESQ is student-teacher interaction, in and out of class. Many angles of these aspects have been discussed, along with the impact on the student's personal development. There is a need to mend this relationship as it is critical due to the fact that the teacher delivers the core service of the HE to the actual consumer as a student. If their interaction is not of the suitable level, this only affects the HESQ negatively.

- The current internship system should also be improved and extended. The students should be provided with the opportunity to go into the industry and learn the implication of the concepts they are taught in the classroom so, in the end, they will have more than just the classroom experience. There is a need to introduce a better internship system with the liaison of academia and industry. The internship programs should encompass actual skill development and enhancement rather than a time pass. The system needs to be developed where HEIs collaborate with different organisations so their students can go into the practical environment and learn. In return, the HEIs can offer courses to the human resource of those organisations free or with a minimal fee.
- The training and development of the teaching staff are a very critical aspect of HESQ as the core of the service is delivered by them. There is a need for effective development and implementation of the teachers' training and development policies. The policies do exist but are not implemented effectively. There is a need for the realisation of continuous change in the country and around the world. Being a core player, a teacher's efficiency can influence the whole experience positively or negatively. As mentioned by one of the participants, being in the teaching profession, a teacher is as away from the industry as a student, so the teacher training should also include workshops and seminars about industry trends and technologies.
- The policies and strategies of the HEIs should be student-centric rather than management of administration centric. The student should be the central focus right from designing the physical structures and facilities to the non-tangible aspects of service delivery. The decision-makers should not assume what the students' needs are. Instead, they should ask students and consult the latest research conducted.

5.7.2. Recommendations For The Government

Following are the recommendations for the HEC and the government of Pakistan for the improvement of the HE system in the country.

- HEC is the governing body responsible for maintaining the standards of HE provided in the country via government and private institutes. HEC needs to update and effectively implement the policies regarding the availability of a minimum level of facilities in each and every university and campus. There should be regular and unannounced inspections focused on the facility provided in all 246 universities and campuses across the country. A strict policy formation and its effective implication will

bring the facilities across the country up to the desired standard. The permission to open new campuses should only be granted if the existing ones are up-to-mark in terms of facilities, resources and quality of education imparted.

- To resolve the resource scarcity issue, the government need to make an online central library have books on every field of study available to every HE student and a central database having each and every old or new research paper of all the fields of study. The individualised funding allocated by 246 universities can be combined for the development of this centralised knowledge bank, which should be available to everyone who wants to learn and educate oneself, regardless of the tier and sector of HEI or even regardless of being a registered student or otherwise. This access to knowledge must be free of cost, as thousands and thousands of potential students and researchers have been hindered by the cost of knowledge. Making education in the institute free is a farfetched idea in the current economic conditions of Pakistan but making such changes is not as hard if there is an initiative from the government as the stakeholder with the decision-making power. It can be argued that if the same knowledge is available to everyone, what will be the point of difference in HEIs? The answer is simply that there are many other aspects of service quality to be the point of difference; access to knowledge should not be the one.
- The recommendation above is a long-term solution for tackling the issue in the short run; the government should encourage the HEIs to collaborate in sharing the learning resources. It is understood that there will be resistance, especially from the high-end resourceful HEIs, which should be managed by HEC being the governing body of all the HEI. A student from HEI A should be able to consult with the learning resource of HEI B, C, D or S.
- The scholarships are offered by the provincial governments as well as by the central government of Pakistan based on different quota and merit systems at different levels of education. The number of scholarships offered should be increased and should be specially focused on HE. According to Times HE in Pakistan, less than a quarter of the total educational budget is spent on HE. The government needs to prioritise educational development and invest in mental capital with the purpose of prosperity and economic development.

5.7.3. Recommendations For The Industry

Industry can play a vital role in the personal development of students and their readiness for the industry. Following are the recommendations for the industry about the role it can play in the improvement of HE and to get more developed human resources from the system.

- Working in collaboration with the HEIs and providing training and exposure, firstly to the teachers, so that they can relate the imparting knowledge with the local industry and give an example and case studies to the students from the local industry rather than just from the foreign markets.
- Industry can play an important role in the course and content development. The collaboration of academia and industry should develop the courses and content, so students are taught what is desired by the potential consumer of the product of the whole process.
- The industry in Pakistan needs to get actively involved in support of education as part of its corporate social responsibility. There should be the introduction of scholarship and internship programs offered by different sectors of the industry for the students based on their performance and achievements. There is a need for cultural change in internships. The internees should be treated and trained like the employees of the organisation so they can learn and polish skills instead of just being there to fulfil the requirement of their degree.

The one-word solution and the core recommendation based on this research study to all the issues is “collaboration”. Collaboration among HEIs in Pakistan to share resources and facilities for mutual learning, collaboration with foreign HEIs to improve the knowledge and exposure of the students as well as teachers of HE and most importantly, the collaboration of education institutes and industry with the government acting as moderator to improve the education system's overall structure, so students get more training, knowledge and opportunities of personal development and add to the efficient human resource to play their role in the development of the country.

5.8. Chapter Summary

In this chapter, quantitative and qualitative research findings were presented and discussed. In the first section of this chapter, the quantitative study findings were presented. The findings were presented as graphs and tables and were thoroughly explored. Direct quotes from the

responses to the open-ended questions were used in the discussion. The findings of the qualitative part of the research were presented in the second part of the chapter. The qualitative data was examined using thematic analysis. The findings and discussion were organised around the sub-themes, with direct quotes from the participants.

Due to the Covid-19 restrictions, the respondents were reached via social media and other internet methods. Approximately 87% of respondents thought their HEI admission process was simple and easy. A comprehensive picture of the student's perspective can be acquired based on the findings and table presenting the combined percentages of agreement and disagreement, Table 5.3. except for the statement about learning resources, which only around half of the participants agree with, the combined agreement for the tangible features of the HE service is rather high. There is a medium to a high level of combined agreement with the statements about the aspects of assurance. Except for the statement about the competence and skills of teaching personnel, where students showed a very high degree of agreement. Agreement on the statements about reliability elements was medium level. Students' agreement with the statements of empathy and responsiveness was moderate, highlighting a significant area for HEIs to improve. Students agreed with the statements in the sections on student experience, student satisfaction and personal growth.

The results indicated a positive perception of HESQ, but it is also evident that for some statements, the percentage of respondents who agreed was very close to half of the total responses., which depicts that even if there is satisfaction, there is apparent potential for improvement. This favourable or negative perception affects how students experience the service. The research findings show a good assessment of student experience, satisfaction and personal development; however, almost half of the respondents agree. Even if the overall responses are positive, there remains room for improvement. Positive perception results from an agreement with the statements.

HEI facilities were perceived differently by the key stakeholders. Three-quarters of students believed there were enough facilities, and half said there were enough learning resources. Academic and non-academic stakeholders group mentioned a deficiency of resources, which are confined to books. The three stakeholder groups have a similar perspective about practical knowledge mentioning that the basic or core course is over-emphasised and real-time case studies are needed for practical learning and skill development of the HE students. Many of the participants of the survey and interview remarked on the importance of student-teacher

interaction. In response to open-ended questions, students briefly discussed the importance of engagement and how it impacts their overall experience with HESQ. The HEIs staff recognised the significance of the relationship and offered explanations for the decline in student-teacher interaction. Even the professionals from the industry acknowledged the significance of this interaction. The teachers who work at multiple universities were singled out for criticism because of their busy schedules and dedication to their students.

Students have mentioned the student-centric approach, in which administration and management are urged to pay attention to and address the concerns of students. The faculty saw the issue as more of an issue with the building's layout and student safety and satisfaction. The student's development as a result of the HESQ experience affected how the professionals from the industry saw them. All three groups of stakeholders have, to varying degrees, discussed the importance of the industry's role. Regarding how applicable their coursework was to real-world scenarios in their chosen field, students were making this point. The other two groups place equal importance on the significance of the industry-academia partnership in enhancing HESQ and the student's personal development as a result. At the end of the chapter, recommendations were made to HEIs, the government and the industry on how to better serve students, ultimately fostering their personal development.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1. Introduction

This final chapter of the thesis presents a brief summary of the study, a brief answer to the four research questions, the contribution made by this research study, the theoretical and managerial implications of the research, the limitations of this research study and lastly, the perspective for future research.

6.2. Research Summary

The most valuable resource is people, a talent pool contributed by HEIs. Public and private sectors invest in HESQ because it trains the workforce for any country. Every industrialised country has more service-related jobs. According to marketing literature, the consumer is always a co-producer of the service, creating value after consumption. Service involves a deed, act or effort. Service quality describes excellence and fulfils customer needs. Evaluating service quality entails evaluating service quality dimensions which can be used to examine theoretical linkages. Customer expectations and perceptions should be considered when evaluating service quality.

Education service quality is a continuous process that grows over time, with universities able to continuously develop services for the same consumers, giving service providers enough time to increase their level of service provision. A customer-focused approach to quality can give students a unique, personal-development-enhancing experience. HE affects the next generation and the country's progress. HE shapes people's and societies' character. In this fast-paced, competitive environment, HEIs must improve their services. People compare HEIs using rankings and categories, which are encompassed on the basis of HEI quality management, and national, provincial and worldwide certification systems. In Pakistan university's image is based on HECP ranking, not student experience. The gap in the Pakistani HE services context led to the questions answered in this study.

HE stakeholders include government, organisations, teachers, students and others. Service quality and student experience affect student development. HEIs must demonstrate responsiveness to stakeholders. Quality depends on the stakeholder-provider relationship. Stakeholders expect HEIs to prove their grandeur and effectiveness. Every HE stakeholder has a unique viewpoint depending on their needs.

The study's model uses five service quality dimensions. The model displays the anticipated linkages among the aspects of service quality on student satisfaction with the HEE and the subsequent personal development visually. Most research on student success in HEIs has focused on course delivery and teacher quality, and only a small emphasis has been paid to finding the comprehensive aspects of student success using a holistic approach. Service quality is the perception of the whole quality of service and its effect on student experience leading to satisfaction; it is probable that service quality features affect the student experience. HE is a service that students get to improve themselves; therefore, their personal development or the characteristics and abilities they gain through HE are the best measures of its excellence. Reviewing service quality dimensions led to construct development.

The research onion was utilised to handle all of the study's methodological components, and each layer's choices were justified. The methodological approach provides the foundation for collecting and analysing data to achieve research aims and answer research questions. A mixed research approach was followed. The issues with data collection were discussed. HEI students participated via a survey questionnaire, and the other two groups, (i) academic and non-academic staff and (ii) industry professionals, participated in the study via semi-structured interviews. External validity was accomplished by comparing the results to the literature. The choice of mixed methodology boosts the study's validity and reliability and helps establish a valid claim and eliminates bias.

Due to Covid-19 restrictions imposed, respondents were approached via social media. 87% of respondents thought their institution's admissions procedure was straightforward. From the findings and Table 5.3, a comprehensive understanding of the student's perspective can be gained. For the physical characteristics of the HE services, the agreement is significant, but for the learning resources statement, only about half of the participants concur. Medium to a high agreement for statements regarding reliability was moderated, except for the statement regarding teaching staff's skills and competency. The level of student agreement with empathy and responsiveness statements was moderate, indicating that HEIs have room for improvement. Students concurred with the claims on student experience, student satisfaction and personal development.

The results demonstrated a positive perception of HESQ, but for several items, the percentage of agreement was near to half of the total responses, which depicts that even while there is satisfaction with the service, there is apparent potential for improvement. The research findings

show a positive view of the student experience, satisfaction, and personal development, yet less than half of the respondents agree with the statements. Even though most respondents agreed with the statements, there remains room for improvement. Perceptions differed about the HEI facilities, practicality of knowledge, student-teacher interaction, funding availability and industry's role in the context of HE services. The recommendations were made for the HEIs, Government and industry for the improvement of the overall HE services experience of the students leading to their improved personal development. The core recommendation made was about the collaboration of HEIs, government and industry at the optimised level, including resource sharing and aligning the strategic direction of the country.

6.3. Research Questions

6.3.1. First Question

Q1. How do the aspects of HESQ contribute to the HEE of the students?

The quantitative data revealed the answer to the first question, which was to determine the contribution of HESQ components to the student's experience. The data also support the first proposition that HESQ has a favourable impact on the student's experience. The data in Table 5.3 show that there is a positive relationship between students' perceptions of HESQ aspects and the quality of their experience at the HEI. The agreement and disagreement trends in service quality aspect statements are comparable to the agreement and disagreement trends in student experience statements.

6.3.2. Second Question

Q2. What is the importance of student satisfaction in the student experience of HESQ to contribute to personal development?

The quantitative data also address the second question, which was to determine the significance of student satisfaction with the experience in their personal development. The second proposition was that student satisfaction from the HESQ experience positively impacted their personal development was also confirmed by quantitative evidence. The data in Table 5.3 show that student satisfaction with the experience positively impacts their personal development.

6.3.3. Third Question

Q3. What are the differences in the perception of HESQ amongst the stakeholders of HE in Pakistan?

The third question, which concerned the exploration of variations in stakeholder perceptions, was answered based on the quantitative and qualitative findings of the study. It is established that there are evident differences in stakeholder perceptions of HESQ in Pakistan, and each stakeholder group views this differently depending on their relationship to the service delivery process. Some of the differences were also due to the HEIs' tier and sector.

While receiving the service, students evaluate HESQ as a service user from a primarily short-term viewpoint. The student's viewpoint differs depending on various factors such as their exposure, background, and schooling. They are aware of the service's flaws, and some of them have a good sense of what is lacking from the mix of services. The teaching and non-teaching staff members consider themselves service providers under the institute's rules and regulations, which they are required to observe. This stakeholder group emphasised the need for teacher training and development for the enhancement of service. Industry professionals evaluate the quality of service based on how well-developed the students' knowledge and abilities are due to their HEE compared to what they anticipate from graduates. They take into account the personal characteristics as well as the student's affiliation with certain HEIs. The data also revealed that the perspectives of the three stakeholder groups shared certain commonalities. The importance of teacher-student connection was seen as a vital aspect of the experience's quality and the student's subsequent personal growth.

6.3.4. Fourth Question

Q4. How can HESQ be enhanced to improve the personal development of students as a result of their HESQ experience in Pakistan?

The fourth question is addressed in section 5.7 of this study. The recommendations are based on the study's findings and recommendations from stakeholders on HESQ to improve the student experience, and their personal development. The recommendations section is divided into three sub-sections addressing HEIs, government and industry. Collaboration at all levels among departments, HEIs locally and globally, and academics and industry for mutually beneficial service development is one of the study's most important recommendations. The recommendations are aimed at improving the service quality aspects that will affect the quality of experience students have in their HEIs while they are in education and, ultimately, on their personal development.

6.4. Research Contribution

This research study aided and enhanced the current understanding of service marketing with respect to the student experience of HE services in Pakistan, service quality, and stakeholders of higher education and added new aspects for future research in these areas. The study's key findings include variations in the perception of stakeholder groups about the students' HESQ experience and its contribution to their personal development. The differences in their perceptions were based on aspects that were more directly related to them, such as the student's perception of the service as a recipient; the teaching and non-teaching staff's perception of service delivery aspects, and the industry professionals' perception of how developed students would be after receiving the service. Based on the gaps identified, analysis and findings and discussion of the quantitative and qualitative data collected for this research study, the following are the contributions of this study.

- There are not many studies that have looked at how students perceive the quality of HE services in connection to their personal growth. The purpose of this study is to investigate the disparities in perceptions of service quality and its impact on students' personal development across the three key stakeholder groups in Pakistan's HE system.
- The existing research from the stakeholder's perspective mainly addressed the perception of one or two stakeholder groups. This research study provides a much broader perspective of the stakeholder groups about the aspects of service quality, student experience and personal development of students from HE.
- This study also contributes to the area of student experience and presents the differences in the perception of key stakeholders and the differences in the perception of the stakeholder's experience and the experience of current students.
- The research area of service quality has been deeply explored in developed countries in almost all fields. In developing countries, research on service quality is still exploring different fields, including education and, specifically, HE. This study contributes to the aspects of HESQ aspects with respect to Pakistan, a developing economy. There can be implications with respect to the other countries in that region due to the similarities in development, but that area is needed to be explored.
- Some studies conducted in Pakistan address the service quality with respect to the management and business students, but the scale of the studies is limited to one institute. This study provides a collective view from different institutes and different

disciplines to present a holistic view of the aspects of service quality and how different stakeholders perceive them on the basis of their affiliation with the process or the result of the process.

- The study also contributes in terms of providing a comparative view of the universities of the government sector, semi-government sector and private sector. The differences in the perception of stakeholders about the service quality of the HEI and the personal development of the student of that particular HEI also get distinguished based on the sector to which it belongs.

6.5. Implications Of The Research

This section presents the implications of the research study. The implications of this study are presented as theoretical and practical implications in the following two sections.

6.5.1. Theoretical Implications

The theoretical implications of this research study are as follows:

- In this study, a framework was developed to examine key stakeholders' perceptions of HESQ and its contributions to the personal development of HEI students. This approach allows for further investigation of various internal and external stakeholder groups' perceptions of the HEI's service quality and students' personal development. The framework has the flexibility to be used by HEIs as well as organisations with internal and external stakeholder groups to investigate their perspectives on service quality and customer experience.
- The focus of this research was on HEIs providing services in one of the developing countries in the South Asian Region. This research might inspire further exploration of the differences in HE stakeholders' perceptions, such as a comparative study of two developing nations in the same region as well as in different regions or a comparative study of a developing and developed country. There are numerous research studies in developed countries that focus on various aspects of HESQ, but there is a need to investigate the element of service quality perception with respect to the student's personal development due to the HEE.
- This study presents the perspective of three key stakeholder groups that are most directly related to the service process and the outcomes of the process. The perspective

of students as direct receivers, HEI staff as direct providers and industry as the indirect receiver and consumers of the service in Pakistan.

6.5.2. Managerial Implications

The managerial or practical implications of this research study are as follows:

- This research has uncovered several factors of service quality that are critical to stakeholders' perceptions and students' personal development. The management of HEIs can explore these aspects deeper in the alignment of their particular institute in order to enhance the perception of the institution's service quality as well as the student's personal development. The tool established in this study may be used to obtain institute-specific data on important stakeholders' perceptions, which may then be utilised to enhance service quality.
- Students do not attend HEIs only to obtain a degree; they also hope to obtain a well-paying job and a better quality of life (Arif and Ilyas, 2012). HEI's services are designed and executed with the goal of creating value (Perin et al., 2012, Arif et al., 2013). This service delivery perspective should not be limited to a single moment in time; it should continue to extend for a long time after that. As mentioned in the Findings and Discussion chapter, this perception of the student's experiences also changes with the passage of time and exposure. There is a need to develop the service aspects by keeping students as a central focus rather than the management or administration of HEI. The infrastructure and facility development need to be in accordance with the student-focused strategy.
- This study presents the finding that the managers of HEIs can utilise to improve different aspects of the HESQ. The aspects of learning resources, the fee of HEI, teacher-student interaction, sympathetic staff, student services, course content, practical learning approach, industry-academia collaboration, etc., are some of those aspects that have been perceived as not up to the standard by the participants of the study including students. These aspects need to be focused on by HEI managers to improve the perception of HESQ and the student experience. The aspects of teacher-student interaction and industry-academia collaboration were two of the most persistent elements, and these elements play an essential role in the personal development of the students during and even after their HEE.

- The management of the HEIs needs to understand the importance of providing opportunities for learning, training, and development to students as well as to the teaching and non-teaching staff for the improvement of overall service. The provision of learning and training opportunities about new teaching methods, new research in their fields, relevant field training, and top-up courses for the teaching and non-teaching staff can lead to faculty development and ultimately lead to improved service. Academic scholarships in general, performance-based scholarships to motivate the students, arrangement of training seminars and workshops, and internship programs for the students are some of the aspects being suggested by many participating stakeholders for the personal development of students and staff members and also for the improvement of service quality perception.
- There is a need to adopt service evaluation practices as a continuous approach for the continuous improvement of service in alignment with industry trends and advancements in technology.

6.6. Limitations

This section contains a discussion about the limitations of the study.

- The first and most crucial hurdle faced during the study, specifically in the data collection phase, was the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. The collection of data for quantitative and qualitative research was affected as the researcher could not travel to Pakistan for data collection; this added to the limitations of time to complete the study. The data collected adopting online options were less than the aimed data target, which was realistically set for quantitative and qualitative research. The HEIs in Pakistan have been closed due to the pandemic, and the response rate of the online approach was meagre from all of the stakeholders, especially students. A total of 59 responses to the online questionnaire survey were received after approaching thousands of students via social media groups and pages.
- Due to the time limitation of the DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) program, the study was cross-sectional research, and the data collected for this study was for a specific point in time, and the findings also reflect upon the stakeholder's perception of HESQ at a single point in time. The changes in perception over time cannot be presented with such type of data. Therefore, the study findings of this study are not longitudinal. The perception may or may not have been inclined towards certain aspects of service

due to any event in the current or past times. This limitation can be translated into an opportunity for future research by considering the opinion of students once they are taking their HE courses and again when they have completed their degrees and have started their professional careers. The difference of opinion about the HEE while being part of the experience and after can be analysed for the improvement of the HESQ for the next generation of HE students.

- This study is focused on the perspective of the three stakeholder groups (i) students of HE, (ii) teaching and non-teaching staff of the HEIs and (iii) industry professionals. It would be advisable to conduct a study to explore the perspective of other stakeholders, such as parents, the governing body of HE, government official, and the management of HEI. The perception of every stakeholder group is different and is based upon the notion of how it is related to HE.

6.7. Future Research

The suggestions for future research studies are based on the aspects which could not be addressed in this research study, as well as the aspects which need to be addressed in other contexts to explore the variations in the results.

- This research study provides a basis for a longitudinal study to explore the difference in the stakeholder's perception of the HESQ and its contribution towards the personal development of the students. The differences in the perception can be explored based on time duration at a single point in time. There can be an influence of any ongoing or recent occurrence on the stakeholders' perception. This research can also be conducted using entirely qualitative methods to collect the data from all stakeholder groups to express their opinion about the HESQ perception in detail.
- The sample size of the future study should be appropriate to the population. There were time and Covid-19 limitations, which reduced the possibility of collecting relevant data for the research to be generalised. Future research can be conducted by collecting data from a larger sample from each stakeholder group to make the study suitable for generalisability. The study can use the data and findings for this study to compare the differences based on time. The face-to-face collection of quantitative and qualitative data can also improve the overall quality of data collection by reducing the chances of misinterpreting the question, which is a possibility in the case of online data collection.

- The future research can be extended to the other stakeholders of HE and their perception of the service quality as each stakeholder prospect of the HESQ is developed in the way they are connected with HE and the importance of aspects of service quality can also differ from one stakeholder to another.
- The future research about stakeholders' perception of the HESQ and its contribution towards personal development can be conducted as a comparative case study by examining institutes from one sector and tier with the others to explore the difference in the perception and to explore the importance of different aspects of service quality in different sectors and tiers of HEIs.
- This study has presented the segmentation of students based on different factors like schooling, family background and exposure. A further research study can be conducted to find the difference in HESQ perception in various segments of students.

7. References

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Survey Questionnaire

This study is focused on the stakeholders' perspective of higher education service quality and its contribution towards the personal development of the students due to their higher education experience. You are requested to participate in the survey to contribute towards the improvement of the higher education service in Pakistan.

Section 1

In this section, you are requested to provide some information about yourself. No attempt will be made to identify you during or after this research.

1.1. Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

1.2. Age

- Below 20
- 21 – 25
- 26 – 30
- 31 – 35
- Above 35

1.3. Student Status

- National
- International

1.4. What is your course title?

1.5. Name of the higher education institute/university.

Section 2

In this section, please rate your opinions on the aspects of service quality in the higher education institute you are associated with as a student.

2.1. What was the initial source of information about the higher education institute/university?

- Institute's Website
- Family and Friends
- News Paper
- Other: _____

2.2. Did you find the admission process easy and simple?

- Yes
- No
- If no, why not

2.3. University's website provides complete information for decision making.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.4. The induction was helpful in knowing the whereabouts of the university.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.5. There are sufficient facilities in the class/lecture rooms.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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- How the facilities can be improved?

2.6. There are sufficient learning resources available in the university according to your course.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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What other learning resources should be available?

2.7. The learning environment conveys a sense of competence, confidence and professionalism.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.8. Administration is efficient and supportive.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.9. Student services are readily available and delivered on time.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.10. Operating hours of student services are convenient for students.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.11. Professors/teachers are available to provide guidance other than lecture time

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.12. Teaching staff are consistent in the way they teach.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.13. Teaching staff are skilful and competent in what they teach.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.14. Up-to-date communications are provided to students promptly.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.15. Staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.16. Students feel safe in their interaction with staff members.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.17. The institution inspires confidence in the students.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.18. The overall service provided by the university is a good value for the fee.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.19. You will recommend this university to your friends and family.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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2.20. What suggestions would you make to improve the teaching and learning quality of your institution/university?

Section 3

In the section, please rate your opinion on how you feel of your experience in the higher education institution/university you are associated with as a student.

3.1. The higher education institute/university I am attending gives me a feeling that my best interests are being served.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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3.2. The higher education institute/university I am attending gives me a feeling that rewards gained are consistent with the effort I put into the assessment/exams.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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3.3. The higher education institution/university I am attending gives me a feeling of enjoyment with the education experience.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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3.4. I feel involved with the higher education institution/university I am attending.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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3.5. The higher education institution/university I am attending gives me a feeling of uniqueness of being associated with it.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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3.6. The higher education institution/university I am attending gives me a feeling of anticipation and being intellectually challenged.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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3.7. In your opinion, how could the student's experience of higher education be improved?

Section 4

In this section, please rate your opinion on your satisfaction with the higher education institution/university you are associated with.

4.1. The first impression of the higher education institute/university met your expectations.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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4.2. The higher education institution/university meeting your expectations of higher education learning.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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4.3. The higher education institution/university meeting your overall expectations.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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4.4. What changes would you suggest being made that will improve the student satisfaction level?

Section 5

In this section, please rate your opinion on how you have personally developed as a result of your higher education experiences.

5.1. My higher education experience has developed me to solve problems efficiently.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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5.2. My higher education experience has developed me to communicate effectively.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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5.3. My higher education has enabled me to develop skills relevant to the industry.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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5.4. I have developed good general knowledge as a result of my higher education experience.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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5.5. My higher education experience enabled me to better manage, use and analyse information.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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5.6. My level of integrity improved as a result of my higher education.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Strongly Agree
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5.7. What other aspects of personal development should be included in the higher education experience?

Thank you for your valuable time.

If you are interested in the results of the study, you can contact the research at

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 2: Participant Information Sheet

Research Title: Stakeholders' Perspective of the Higher Education Service Quality and its Contribution Towards the Personal Development of Students

Researcher: Muhammad Sharjeel Qazi

Course: Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

Department: Business and Enterprise

About the Study

This study is conducted within Pakistan's education system to contribute to knowledge and literature concerning the quality of service and quality of experience provided by HEIs in Pakistan. This study aims to explore the differences in the perception of the key stakeholders of higher education service quality and its contribution to students' personal development due to their higher education experience.

Who is responsible for the study?

I am the sole researcher working on this topic, and I will be collecting all the primary data in person, which will be in the form of semi-structured interviews. The interviews will be recorded and kept safe by the researcher.

Risk Involved

The participants of the study will remain anonymous throughout the study. The information obtained from the participants will be kept confidential from the public and will be used for this study only. The participants will be free to withdraw themselves from the study at any stage without providing any reason.

Participation and Monetary Benefits

Participation in the study is voluntary, and there will be no monetary rewards for the participants. The data collected will not be used for any commercial purposes.

Contact

If you have any further questions or concerns about this study, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Name:

Phone:

Email:

Personal details
withheld.

Appendix 3: Research Consent Form

Research Title: Stakeholders' Perspective of the Higher Education Service Quality and its Contribution Towards the Personal Development of Students

Researcher: Muhammad Sharjeel Qazi

Course: Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

Department: Business and Enterprise

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information about the study as provided in the participant information sheet.
- I confirm that I was given the opportunity to ask questions, and I am satisfied by the answers provided by the researcher.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study at any time.
- I understand that any information recorded during the study will remain confidential, and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

- I consent to the use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving for future research.
- I consent to audio interviews being recorded as part of the study.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

Participant's Name _____

Designation / Title _____

Organisation/Institute _____

Participant's Signature _____

Date _____

Appendix 4: Semi-Structured Interviews Script

Section A

A1. Name:

A2. Age:

A3. Gender:

A4. Highest University Degree:

A5. Institute:

A6. Job role:

A7. Organisation:

A8. Years in this job role:

A9. Industry:

A10. Years in the industry:

Section B

In this section, please give your opinions about the perception of service quality of the higher education institutes/Universities in Pakistan.

B1. How do you feel about your HEI/university meeting your expectations of higher education?

B2: Do you think that the HEI/university is meeting the expectations of the current students?

B3: How do you compare your higher education experience with the higher education experience of current students?

B4: What is your opinion about the facilities and resources provided to the students in HEIs/universities?

B5: What is your opinion regarding the HEIs/universities in Pakistan compared with the HEIs/universities outside Pakistan?

B6: What suggestions would you make to improve the quality of service provided by the HEIs/universities?

B7: In HEIs, what are the significant challenges in optimising their service quality and how these challenges can be addressed?

Section C

In this section, please give an opinion about the student's personal development due to their higher education experience?

C1: Do you think HE develops skill like problem-solving, negotiation, project management, conflict management etc., in the students?

C2: How do you think HE experiences allow students to communicate effectively in educational and non-educational environments?

C3: Do you think that HE enables students to develop the skills relevant to the industry?

C4: How would you analyse the student's level of integrity and self-confidence due to their HE experience?

C5: How would you analyse your personal development due to your HE experience compared to the current student?

C6: Compared to your HE experience, which aspects need to be focused more on the current HE experience?

C7: In your view, what is lacking from the HEI's/university's quality assurance?

C8: Do you think that students are satisfied with the HE provided? What changes would you suggest for the improvement of the HE experience?

C9: Along with the currently addressed aspects of student's personal development, what other elements should be included in the HE experiences?

Section D

This section consists of the questions been evolved during the interviews.

D1: Do you think there is an issue of quality versus quantity in the HEIs/universities?

D2: What is your opinion about the teacher-student relationship?

D3: What is your point of view about the same curriculum across different HEIs/universities?

D4: DO you think vocational training should be introduced as part of the higher education experience?

Appendix 5: Interview Transcript – Industry Professional

Section A

A1. Name: P9E

A2. Age: 37

A3. Gender: Male

A4. Highest University Degree: Master of Business Administration

A5. Institute: Bahria University, Islamabad

A6. Job role: Head of North Carrier Division

Visiting Faculty

A7. Organisation: PTCL (Pakistan Telecommunication Company Ltd)

Bahria University, Islamabad

Shaheed Zulfikar Ali Bhutto Institute of Science and Technology,

Islamabad

A8. Years in this job role: 11 years

A9. Industry: Telecommunication and Education

A10. Years in the industry: 11 Years

Section B

In this section, please give your opinions about the perception of service quality of the higher education institutes/Universities in Pakistan.

B1. How do you feel about your HEI/university meeting your expectations of higher education?

Ans: There are three-four factors I would like to see in myself. One is communication skills, and second is presentation because that is a must in today's world, the third thing is having good market know-how, last is the university should be well-reputed in the market. If we talk about these four points, I will say that Bahria university was covering three out of four points. They gave us confidence, the presentation was good, the value was there. As far as the industry alignment is concerned, that is the area that is quite weak, and I feel that it is a quite weak area for all the institutions in Pakistan. The linkage between the industry and the University is very important. Once we have the linkage, then you will know the expectation level of the industry. University has fulfilled my expectations, but as far as the industry is concerned, they might have some more expectations from the University which are not being currently fulfilled.

B2: Do you think that the HEI/university is meeting the expectations of the current students?

Ans: If you ask me honestly, I will say the quality of education, instead of getting better, has gone down. The reason is that most of the universities in Pakistan have been commercialised. How to get maximum students to earn the maximum chunk of money. The race is not about quality the race is about having the quantity of students, and there is a compromise you have to make once you go for quality versus quantity race. However, there are some institutions which have improved a lot, and they have a very good name, for example, FAST (Foundation for Advancement of Science and Technology) has improved a lot, the reason being they have a very selective lot of people in there BBA and other batches, and they give very tough time to students. If you ask me as a professional, when we interview people when they come to us, the students from FAST are pretty much better off. In the overall trend, the quality has been compromised.

B3: How do you compare your higher education experience with the higher education experience of current students?

Ans: When I was in higher education, the industry sector was booming. At that time, the Telecom industry was at its peak. The banking industry was at its peak, the media industry was re-regulated, and lots of media houses came to Pakistan. At that time, there were more opportunities because the economy was growing. If you see right now, the economy is not growing as fast as the number of students. The number of students coming out of the universities is really high, and the industry is not geared up to accommodate all of them. Secondly, the industry used to go for the University degree only, but now the trend has changed, and they look at the relevant skillset and certification as well. This trend was not there in my time, but now they ask for the certification along with the University degree. Now during Covid-19, more organisations are going towards digital learning, and once they adopt this, more jobs will be at risk. This phenomenon will not just be in Pakistan; it will be all over the world.

B4: What is your opinion about the facilities and resources provided to the students in HEIs/universities?

Ans: HEC has been trying to Improve these things, and now the universities have a higher number of PhD and Ms scholars in their staff. If we go four to five years back, there were more members of visiting faculty in the Universities, but now They have hired many PhD and MS scholars with an emphasis on research. HEC is working on the research side, and it is improving. I think they need to have some professionals in the faculty as well. If you look at

IBA (Institute of Business Administration) and LUMS (Lahore University of Management Sciences), They have some professional teachers over there who are working in Pepsi or Nestle etc. So, the shift towards the research side, the research is the focus right now, but again I think the quality needs to be proved.

B5: What is your opinion regarding the HEIs/universities in Pakistan compared with the HEIs/universities outside Pakistan?

Ans: That is a very good question, it varies from person to person, but when you have an individual who has studied abroad, they have more exposure. Anyone who is coming back from UK, USA, Australia or for that matter from European countries, have better exposure and confidence. The decision making of the student who is coming from an international university is much better. The students from Pakistani universities are generally not good decision-maker. Secondly, the research orientation is very limited in Pakistan, whereas students in the UK, Australia and the USA have more materials and resources. So, I believe that students from abroad are more in accord with our needs. If I have to hire someone in my team, I will go for an international student, or I will hire from two to three universities in Pakistan. I will go for a candidate from LUMS because they have good decision-making skills, or I will go for a student from IBA or FAST. Students from other universities are very good at following the directions but lack decision-making or analytical decision making.

B6: What suggestions would you make to improve the quality of service provided by the HEIs/universities?

Ans: I think books are important, but I believe in more of a case study best learning. In the case study, you are discussing different organisations and learning with real-time examples. I always say that the industry and academia linkage has to be improved. The students need to have more mentoring on-premises. I will give you an example of our own company PTCL, we have a mentorship programme in which The different onboard students from universities for six to eight weeks, they are placed with us, and they support us in our role, and we tried to encourage them and get them involved in the decision making.

We need to encourage our students to learn from case studies, research papers, even though games. Books are good, but the bookish knowledge is limited. There is a famous saying that 80% of the revenue comes from 20% off the customers, that is a very factual thing and, but you will only learn this once you are only professional side, so the exposure needs to be improved.

B7: In HEIs, what are the significant challenges in optimising their service quality and how these challenges can be addressed?

Ans: Universities need to have a single curriculum that is regulated by HEC. If a certain thing is taught in Bahria University, that should be taught in Preston University and Allama Iqbal Open University as well. The Prime Minister of Pakistan is coming up with one curricular programme, although it is very odd, you need to give everyone the same opportunity. This is one area where I think HEC needs to be properly regulated, and they need to ensure that the curriculum is the same and the quality of teachers. They need to have the PhDs, they need to have researchers, and they need to have the corporate individuals in their teaching staff. That is when they are going to attain a balance.

Q: If all the universities are following one curriculum, how will the universities create the difference? Like at the minute, FAST, LUMS and IBA are teaching their students a different curriculum compared to middle-level universities like COMSATS and others, and if you go a bit further down to NUML, Arid Agriculture or UDRU University, their curriculum is totally different from the others, how will they differentiate themselves if the curriculum is same for all?

Ans: This is a very basic question; I have been asked this during a discussion in a conference. Once you have the same curriculum in all universities, the people who are sitting there in LUMS or IBA are all seasoned professionals backed by research. They have one of the crème faculty in Pakistan. You are studying in the UK right now, and you will agree to this thing that in Pakistan, the top 2-3 universities are known by everyone, and they are at the top due to some reasons, and I agree that the fee they are charging that way ahead. You need to form a national panel, and you need to involve teachers, corporate professionals and the gurus of industry and design a common curriculum. Once you have a common curriculum, the things which are taught in LUMS and COMSATS will be taught in tier 4 university as well. The same curriculum will at least give everyone the same opportunity. Every individual is different, every university is different, the methodology will be different, but at least the people will be able to understand the basics. The student from different universities will have different culture, but at least they will have the same curriculum.

Section C

In this section, please give an opinion about the student's personal development due to their higher education experience?

C1: Do you think HE develops skill like problem-solving, negotiation, project management, conflict management etc., in the students?

Ans: If you ask me on the face of it, I will say no. There are subjects on the University level which are being taught on these things but the complete personality and personal development that should be inculcated in the students that are not taking place. A question can be asked that if these courses are being taught but why they are not practised and being followed. That is something to do with the culture of the University, and again that varies from University to University. In some universities, you will find that these things are being taught and practised. In some universities, you will find that teachers are more concerned about delivering the lectures, and that's it. Now, what is conflict management? in the book, the definition is very simple, but how to manage a conflict in practice is something which needs to be demonstrated more practically. Again, I will say that they need to have case base scenarios; once they have case-based scenarios, they can present these things in a better way. Similarly, if you talk about consumer behaviour or anything else, I believe that urge is there, but the urge is only till teaching, this is not being inculcated in the life of the students. I believe that universities and industry need to take a step ahead and develop platforms where they can provide on hand training to the students regarding problem-solving, conflict management, project management and so on. Reading something in a book and doing something practically are two different things. Students need to realise that they are not there just to read the books, they need to gear them up to meet the coverage challenges, and if they want to be entrepreneur, they should be ready for that.

C2: How do you think that HE experiences allows students to communicate effectively in educational and non-educational environments?

Ans: In the corporate sector, the one who is good in communication and the one who have deliberative thoughts process and cognitive thought process and the one who speaks out goes quickly ahead. He or she grabs the attention of higher management and everyone else. I believe the communication skills are fine they're not that bad, but then again, It varies from University to University like COMSATS house good students, but they lack confidence, and they lack communication skills. Having some looks like business communication or just communication giving these subjects but more credit hours, I think it will help a lot. Also, this stage fear, I have

seen in many universities, except a few stage fear is there. You need to kill this stage fear and for that universities needs to give student maximum chances to speak out. The teacher should just guide the students and let the students come up with ideas from their own mind. This will give confidence to the students, and once they come into the corporate sector or become entrepreneurs be able to sell their things or market their things in a better manner. Communication is very important. in all society, there is a stigma that if you can communicate in English, it is very good, and if you communicate it is not good, this stigma has to be removed. If a person is expressing himself in English, Pushto or Urdu, let them speak. I understand there is decorum of the corporate world and stuff but let the person speak their heart out. English is a language, and they will learn over time but for now, let them speak the language they speak and let them express themselves.

C3: Do you think that HE enables students to develop the skills relevant to the industry?

Ans: The skills can be improved. Currently, the universities are trying to improve, but I think there is a big gap, and universities can improve the student's readiness for practical life. Did you study many things in the University but want to go out and do things particularly then you will actually learn them. Universities need to have some strict rules like after the bachelor's degree the students need to have practical experience of two years before they can do masters. If you go to the top universities of the UK in Australia, they ask you about your work experience if you want to do the Masters. They need to introduce the mandatory work experience or mandatory internship, and that internship should not be for just six weeks, it should be a continuous process. This is only possible when HEC plays the role of a catalyst, and the industry needs to join hands. Only then the opportunities will be there for the students.

Some universities have moved towards the games in simulation to teach students, and I think if universities adopt the gaming and simulations into learning that will help a lot. If I am interviewing a candidate, I look for three things, I am a business graduate myself, mostly I deal with the sales people. I see confidence in them, if they are able to attain the pressure and the third skill which the university teaches but it is not there, is the Excel skills. When I hire a fresh graduate, I expect him to have strong Excel skills. He should be able to apply all the formulas, he should be able to filter the data, he should be able to put the graphs over there and how to make presentations. On these skills set, skills search every University have a very different output. Universities are needed to add these tools into their curriculum because if the student

learned that in the University it will be very easy for them too adopting except in the corporate sector.

C4: How would you analyse the student's level of integrity and self-confidence due to their HE experience?

Ans: As far as the higher education and confidence is concerned, People who have done their master's do you have the edge on people who did Batchelors. A self-confidence is something which varies person to person and university to university. In some University's students the self confidence is very good, in some university's student the self confidence is average and in some it is very low.

C5: How would you analyse your personal development due to your HE experience compared to the current student?

Ans: In our time the opportunities of personal development were there, but the possibilities are more now. The quantity of students was low in our time. In my Patch they were 80 students for a year, out of which 54 graduated. Now they are around 200 to 250 students for six months programme. The quantity is too much, and the time teacher could invest in students has decreased. On the other hand, the number of opportunities due to social media and other platforms also too much. The population has increased so the quantity of the student hasn't raised, and the quality has been compromised. You cannot have 200 or 300 students in a class with only two or three teachers. You need to improve the skills set off the teachers by giving them further education and by giving them training. Similarly, if you are taking 300 students, you need to grind them properly.

C6: Compared to your HE experience, which aspects need to be focused more on the current HE experience?

Ans: In our time there were three things which institutions were trying to do. First, building the confidence level and communication skills of the students, secondly, they were grinding more and thirdly, follow up, if you are not performing well they will call in the students and even parents to discuss why the student is not performing. The grinding and follow up as missing now. They used to give us additional classes for Excel and power point. These were non-credit hour classes but if the students do not attend, they were not allowed to sit in exam. The attendance was very important as well.

C7: In your view, what is lacking from the HEI's/university's quality assurance?

Ans: I guess the intent from the regulator is missing. HEC is trying to be just a facilitator. Their role is not just to facilitate but to regulate the sector as well. HEC is taking baby steps like asking the higher education institutes to have more PhDs and research scholars in their faculty, they are making a rule that you need to have at least 10 years of corporate experience to teach in any university. This will be implemented soon. These baby steps need to be fastened up now because the world have moved on. They need to invest in the teachers because if they do not invest in teachers and improve and develop them, they cannot expect different results.

The quality of research that we have in Pakistan that is pretty much down they need to enhance and support the research programs. You need to give them grants and these grants can come from the corporate sector of Pakistan and from the government. Make it necessary to have work experience if someone wants to do masters.

C8: Do you think that students are satisfied with the HE provided? What changes would you suggest for the improvement of the HE experience?

Ans: This is a very good question. In Pakistan you know that the co-education is not very common. Now a days, 75% of the students will try to go into a co-education or some fun university. Definitely this was another time as well, but maybe we were more focused because the opportunities were there even though they were not like they are right now. So, the student tried to go into fun universities, we all need to realise that girls are with us in the universities as well as at workplace and home as well. We treat a girl as an alien and that mentality has to stop. You need to treat them with respect and equality, they are there just deal with it normally, but some people be like oh there is a girl blab la. In some of the top universities the students are coming from the elite schools and the co-education is not new for them, and they do not get detract and before more focused. For example, LUMS, normally people from elite background, like giving 1.5million for a year in bachelor's program is no joke. most of the boys and girls who go there are from strong background and those students are pretty much satisfied. they have fun there, they take girls and boys normally, they have resources and a balanced teacher to student ration, so they are satisfied. If you look at tier 2 or 3 universities, things are different there, students are not that satisfied, they mostly try to have fun and are not very focused. Universities need to work on building focus of the students by having industry linkages etc. at the end of the day, it is all about management that how you manage you students.

C9: Along with the currently addressed aspects of student’s personal development, what other elements should be included in the HE experience?

Ans: I believe that being positive is always good. I believe that baby steps are being taken, I might have sounded a bit pessimistic but that is not the case. There are some areas of improvement, and we can improve. We need to focus on skills set. GPA does matter but skills set is also very important. We have a physics that degree is must we also need to consider diplomas as they are also very important. We need to get out of books. We need to adopt by looking at the western side and enhance the skills. Universities need to realise that industry is not looking for students with just degrees. They need to start the diplomas as well. They need to have a national strict scoring system which is being followed by all the universities.

Section D

This section consists of the questions been evolved during the interviews.

D1: Do you think there is an issue of quality versus quantity in the HEIs/universities?

Ans: Covered above

D2: What is your opinion about teacher-student relationship?

Ans: The face to face interaction has reduced because the quantity has increased. In our time there were less students, and the teachers were able to give more time to each student. In our time the teacher and students used to have a very respectful relationship whereas now they have a very casual relationship due to OTT apps. They are contacting each other on WhatsApp, Facebook etc. the mode of communication is there but the number of students has increased, and the quality of teachers has not been improved so there is a gap. Even though HEC is trying to improve but they need to do it with a rapid pace. They need to have a ration of teachers and number of students. They need to reduce the number of student intake, obviously universities will not like that, but HEC needs to enforce that to improve quality.

Appendix 6: Interview Transcript – Teaching And Non-Teaching Staff

Section A

A1. Name: P11E

A2. Age: 40

A3. Gender: Male

A4. Highest University Degree: MPhil Marketing

A5. Institute: COMSATS, Islamabad

A6. Job role: Assistant Professor

A7. Organisation: COMSATS, Islamabad

A8. Years in this job role: 12 Years

A9. Industry: Education

A10. Years in the industry: 14 years

Section B

In this section, please give your opinions about the perception of service quality of the higher education institutes/Universities in Pakistan.

B1. How do you feel about your HEI/university meeting your expectations of higher education?

Ans: To be very honest I did not have any kind of expectations when I was about to join MBA. I had no expectations from the University because I was already working in the industry. I knew what sales and marketing is and how things are in the industry. There are different types of students, those students who have no idea how things work in the industry they might have different expectations then those who have been working in the industry. I just wanted to be a part of the institution which's degree is recognised I was not expecting any high quality of education. I believe that your perception about the University translates into your expectations from the University. When I joined come COMSATS, I was there to just get the degree of MBA, but what I saw there and the education I received it was good. The expectations developed during degree were meet and my experience was very good.

B2: Do you think that the HEI/university is meeting the expectations of the current students?

Ans: It all depends upon the different kind of perceptions student develops. Students can be divided into different segments and you, and you cannot say that all the students have same

perception. I have come across many students who do not care what is being taught, what the teacher is doing, what sort of education they are getting, all they are bothered about the degree they're getting. Students who belong to financially strong families, some are in the University just because their parents want them to get the degree. When you work hard, there have to be a driving motivation that drives you. That group of students is not driven because they don't care. Then you have another group of students who wants to get quality education, they evaluate everything and a perception towards education will obviously be different.

B3: How do you compare your higher education experience with the higher education experience of current students?

Ans: I don't think there's a difference in the quality of education. We are providing a service and services are different than the tangible products. Tangible products have new innovation in them, and they keep on changing. Services are acts, efforts and processes. Acts, efforts and processes can be innovated but at the end the core of every actual process remains the same. People have been getting the education the same way, the difference is how you conducted the process. Now we have laptops, applications like zoom etc but we are still importing education. I don't think there is a difference in quality of education, the difference is of time zone and process.

B4: What is your opinion about the facilities and resources provided to the students in HEIs/universities?

Ans: Facilities and resources have improved a lot but when it comes to services physical evidence is very important. The place where you are receiving the service It has to be accommodated with the physical evidence as well. You might have come across students of a plaza-based education system in Pakistan. There were campuses on a single floor of a building, there were no sportsgrounds, no libraries and it was just who rooms on a single floor of a building where they used to have classes. If you compare the old campus of our University with the existing one there's a lot of difference. Physical infrastructure plays a lot of roles in your development, the socialisation which you can have with your friends and other students, the packaging itself, the physical evidence is like the packaging. In marketing we believe that packaging plays a lot of roles in product attraction. In services we do not have goods, but we have packaging, so this physical evidence, this infrastructure, this building, the colour combination, the classroom ambiance, the heating and cooling arrangements, etc all this is packaging. In so many ways COMSATS and other universities have improved the

infrastructure. There will always be some issue because mostly people who develop these infrastructures are not very customer centric. They believe that they know what a student wants and that is the service gap, and you will always find students who are not happy with the service provided, but overall I believe people are satisfied and we have been able to provide good infrastructure to the students which will contribute towards their development.

B5: What is your opinion regarding the HEIs/universities in Pakistan compared with the HEIs/universities outside Pakistan?

Ans: My comparison will be perceptive as I do not have experience of universities outside Pakistan. I have seen people and I have met people and I have organised lots of international research conferences and I have been in collaboration with so many academics from all over the world. I think every University have certain variables on which they want to excel and how well those variables are implemented and strategized actually defines how good are for University you are. If we talk about the programmes offered in a University and you look at the modern world universities, they do not offer the conventional programmes which are offered in Pakistan. Will hardly find a University offering a degree of industrial marketing, data Sciences or artificial intelligence. There are differences in infrastructure as well. We have teachers who are qualified from the same University and now they're teaching in that University. Same happens in universities like Oxford as well. Universities there have big campuses we have become with his head as well we have infrastructure and we have some sort of infrastructure as well, the point of difference is what sort of students you are getting. I don't believe that universities groomed students, I believe they receive students who are already driven and motivated and then he is given the facilities make and nurture himself. Top Universities of the world they have never received a pathetic student and it's useless to say that they develop students, no, they already received developed students. Here in Pakistan we have two problems, one is the grass root education and second is the investment of funding literacy receives to provide the environment.

B6: What suggestions would you make to improve the quality of service provided by the HEIs/universities?

Ans: Now don't get me started on that, it can take entire day. Whenever I teach service marketing course, majority of the examples I have are from universities. Universities are one of the biggest sectors in the service sector. You can start from the economic programmes they are offering; these programmes have to be innovative, realistic and updated, stop providing

them degrees of MBA marketing, MBA finance, MBA human resource, No such thing as MBA marketing or human resource, you cannot be a specialist by teaching four additional subjects. You need to see what industry needs, so you can offer them realistic programmes, so at least these students have some actual chance in the industry. This is not difficult; you can have few people from the industry in your Board of studies. They can see what has been taught and they can introduce new courses. You cannot always expect from a teacher to modify the courses, we are as distant from the industry as students are. I have been teaching her from last 12 years and I have not been part of the industry from last 12 years, industry is changing every year. Information I'm receiving wild industry is my own individual effort. I have few students who are in the industry, and they keep me posted with the new trends, new strategies being adopted etc. Training is very important; I believe it can do wonders. What kind of organisation do not provide can you get development opportunities to its own employees. There is no career development is for teachers or students. there's no programme to engage the aluminise.

Many of the outsiders how told me that our University campus looks likes more of a five-star hotel then a University. it clearly means that whoever had designed the campus was not customer centric. He did not consider students physical and psychological contribution in the campus. The campus does not only provide you the classrooms it also enables your psychological physiological wellbeing. Come here you see there's no place for students to sit. Recently, a student died in the campus because we help could not reach him in time, the ambulance could not reach him because of the boundaries being created.

Students career development in universities responsibility, it is their responsibility that their students are positioned in the right place, they are presented with the right opportunities. In Pakistan, majority of the universities do not care about the development of the students' order aluminise. Apart from this there will be million other factors, but I think these 3 or 4 are the most important ones.

B7: In HEIs, what are the significant challenges in optimising their service quality and how these challenges can be addressed?

Ans: I think the two major challenges are bureaucracy and corruption third one is the lack of funding. The bureaucracy and nepotism in this industry or in any other industry in Pakistan leads to the selection of incompetent people. Even the institutes are run by incompetent people so you cannot expect something good will come out of it. There is lack of support from the government in terms of infrastructure and financial support. Adding to this problem is that you

do not have any support from your aluminate. Primarily there are three types of funding in Pakistan, one that you receive through fees from the students, second you receive grants from the government or any other donation agency and the third is the one which receive through your own ventures. Funding corruption and bureaucracy are the genetic factors which affect everything.

Section C

In this section, please give an opinion about the student's personal development due to their higher education experience?

C1: Do you think HE develops skill like problem-solving, negotiation, project management, conflict management etc., in the students?

Ans: It all depends upon the type of curriculum you are developing. Every course is able to develop individuals, not just theoretical. When you talk about the great institutes of the work or the top ten, what differs in them and us is that they actually try to develop students and we try to teach them the basic curriculum. We teach students many courses finance, human resource, project management, that shows that we are trying to develop them from every possible angle which is needed by the industry, in order for them to be successful. Every higher education institute has the capacity to develop, but either they are developing or not it all depends on the individual effort, the vision of the organisation and how much the regulatory authority play their role in this.

C2: How do you think that HE experiences allows students to communicate effectively in educational and non-educational environments?

Ans: There are few things that are relevant here. First is the course work you are teaching them, the scheme of study that you are having, we also teach to the business communication, communication skills are to enable student for real life, how to write, how to read, how to speak and other aspects of communication skills that are needed. Again, I would say that I have seen students who are in the final semester, and they don't even know how to write a report, they don't know how to construct an argument even how to construct a sentence. I have come across students many times who do not know what the topic is, what it means what I'm asking them in the examination, but they are unable to construct those arguments. They come to me later on and say Sir, this is what I'm trying to write why did you scored me less. I tell them this is exactly what I was looking for in the answer, but I could not find that when I see your answer.

This does not mean that student is not hard working, or he did not understand the question, but he was not able to construct the argument. I think the way coursework is designed is not achieving its objectives. I cannot hold those teachers accountable who are teaching this course. You cannot make somebody capable just by teaching them one course. If somebody is coming to this institute from village, he did not have any interaction in terms of communication skills. We have people coming from all over the country, some are from really backward areas where the basic communication skills are lacking. If you think that just teaching them one course will enable them to be part of the corporate sector, I do not think that is possible. They need to start a zero semester where they groom students and bring them up to the mark then start teaching them courses. I think the universities are not enabling the student with the communication skills.

C3: Do you think that HE enables students to develop the skills relevant to the industry?

Ans: I have answered this question in the previous questions. They are not actually, and lots of people blame universities for not developing students with the necessary skills relevant to the industry. I will say that a lot of this blame can be attributed towards the curriculum and towards the teacher. The issue of curriculum can be attributed towards the authorities and all those departments and the institutions who are responsible for developing or designing these curriculums. Most of the marketing students the first job they are offered after they complete their education is of sales and distribution, And majority of universities that teach you what sales, but they don't teach you about distribution, then how would you expect a student to be good at that. When you do not give them these skills then they learn by experience. when you talk about learning by experience you also need to understand that do you make lots of mistakes in the process.

C4: How would you analyse the student's level of integrity and self-confidence due to their HE experience?

Ans: There are many aspects to this thing. first of all is the kind of students that we receive, again they can be divided into various segments. We have students who already have lots of self-confidence because they belong to those top families, in terms of their communication skills, they had good schooling, they had good social life, These kinds of students because they already groom they catch of things pretty quickly, and I'm not talking about their academic performance that has nothing to do with these things. Then we have other type of students who did not have good schooling and they belong to villages. Almost 60 to 70% of the student

intake in our institutes is from the underdeveloped areas. Their parents are not qualified or educated much, and this speak the native language all the time, and they are asked to speak English and produced their ideas in English. A year ago, I have met a student who did not have any idea off what Facebook is, what is Intel Corporation. What can you expect from this sort of students, and it is not their fault? When you process different type of students from the same assembly line the standardisation is not possible, you need same ingredients to produce same product.

C5: How would you analyse your personal development due to your HE experiences compared to the current student?

Ans: My higher education experience was good, as I mentioned that I already had an industry experience. I already had an experience of communicating with people and I belong to a family who is good with education. My father used to live abroad, and he always used to speak with me in English, I used to read English newspaper, so my experience cannot be attributed towards the whole higher education experiences. When I went there, I had no problems in talking to females and understanding the concepts in class, the only development I had received was in terms of my career, by passing those courses, learning new ideas, I came across new philosophies. Most of the universities focus on completing the course in that limited time. Even the students are concerned about passing those courses, rather than learning something. They talk about wellbeing and carrier development centres, but I have not seen much happening there or a big change in their personality, most of the time it is their personal effort.

C6: Compared to your HE experiences, which aspects need to be focused more on the current HE experience?

Ans: First and foremost is the academic programs you are offering; the content of those programs is very important. The selection criteria of the students, you need to isolate the group of students and you need to work on them before you put them in one class. The personal development opportunities, the career development opportunities, workshops training, and the most important thing is the integration off the University with the industry. I think everything is important one reason I'm saying this is because everything is bad in Pakistan, you name any aspect of the University education, and you will always find a loophole. The only thing which is better is the cafeteria and that maybe is because of our passion for food.

C7: In your view, what is lacking from the HEI's/university's quality assurance?

Ans: There is no such thing as quality assurance, that is just one Department of the University and all they do is to serve HEC. Higher education Commission is a very useless Department of Pakistan, all they do is collect data. They collect the data through the quality assurance Department. In the last few years HEC has made sure that every University have a quality enhancement cell, they call it QEC. QEC collect data from the institution and submitted to HEC. That data has to be used for the development of education system and students, but it is just collected and used for finding out how many students are there how many have passed, how many degrees are issued, what courses are offered etc. I have not seen a single improvement in terms of the quality of education, in terms of the content that is been delivered, all they do is to make your life more miserable by asking you to fill more forms and provide more details. I am willing to provide those details if I know that this information that I am sharing with them can lead to some sort of quality improvement. The data received from these universities is a goldmine, and you can do miracles with that, but who will do that. Those people working in the Higher Education Commission, they do not have the relevant qualification for the job, and they are there due to nepotism, corruption and quota system.

C8: Do you think that students are satisfied with the HE provided? What changes would you suggest for the improvement of the HE experience?

Ans: We cannot change their background, and we cannot entirely blame on that. When they are here for two years three years or four years, that is a lot of time. Make sure that at least now they are trained and guided because it is not only bad for them, but also for us. If these students do something bad, that is not good for University either. We have class counsellors, but you will hardly ever see a student coming to the class counsellor. They don't have anything to do with counselling because this is an additional task for the teacher who is already teaching three to four classes and checking their assignments and quizzes.

C9: Along with the currently addressed aspects of student's personal development, what other elements should be included in the HE experiences?

Ans: I think I have covered almost everything from industry integration to physical evidence.

Section D

This section consists of the questions been evolved during the interviews.

D1: Do you think there is an issue of quality versus quantity in the HEIs/universities?

Ans: Yes, obviously. Everyone wants to go for quality, but they cannot because the quantity generates the funding, and that is the reality. Money inflow is the basic issue for all the universities. I don't think hiring lots of student is a bad thing what you need to do is manage them.

D2: What is your opinion about the teacher-student relationship?

Ans: Nothing has changed, the only thing which I have seen different is that now they are friending you on Facebook. The interaction and socialisation you believe you need to have with students is totally a subjective and perceptive matter, and it all depends on the teacher.

Appendix 7: Figure 5.5: Ease And Simplicity Of Admission Process

Appendix 8: Correlation Tables

Tangibles

		Correlations		
		There are sufficient facilities in the class/lecture rooms.	There are sufficient learning resources available in the university according to your course.	The learning environment conveys a sense of competence and professionalism.
There are sufficient facilities in the class/lecture rooms.	Pearson Correlation	1	.593	.357
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.009
There are sufficient learning resources available in the university according to your course.	Pearson Correlation	.593	1	.565
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
The learning environment conveys a sense of competence and professionalism.	Pearson Correlation	.357	.565	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.000	

a. Listwise N=53

Assurance

		Correlations			
		University's website provides complete information for the decision making.	The induction was helpful in knowing the whereabouts in the university.	The institute's communication network is u-to date and efficient.	The institute encourages confidence in the students.
University's website provides complete information for the decision making.	Pearson Correlation	1	.665	.448	.380
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.005
The induction was helpful in knowing the whereabouts in the university.	Pearson Correlation	.665	1	.542	.537
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
The institute's communication network is u-to date and efficient.	Pearson Correlation	.448	.542	1	.351
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.010
The institute encourages confidence in the students.	Pearson Correlation	.380	.537	.351	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.000	.010	

a. Listwise N=53

Reliability

		Correlations			
		Teaching staff are consistent in the way they teach.	Teaching staff are skilful and competent in what they teach.	The overall service provided by the university is a good value for fee.	You will recommend this university to our family and friends.
Teaching staff are consistent in the way they teach.	Pearson Correlation	1	.785	.636	.507
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
Teaching staff are skilful and competent in what they teach.	Pearson Correlation	.785	1	.662	.471
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
The overall service provided by the university is a good value for fee.	Pearson Correlation	.636	.662	1	.819
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
You will recommend this university to our family and friends.	Pearson Correlation	.507	.471	.819	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	

a. Listwise N=53

Empathy

		Correlations		
		Professors/lecturers are available to provide guidance other than lecture times.	The staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems.	Students feel safe in their interaction with staff member.
Professors/lecturers are available to provide guidance other than lecture times.	Pearson Correlation	1	.679	.711
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
The staff are sympathetic and reassuring with the students who face problems.	Pearson Correlation	.679	1	.721
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
Students feel safe in their interaction with staff member.	Pearson Correlation	.711	.721	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	

a. Listwise N=53

Responsiveness

Correlations

		Administration staff is efficient and supportive.	Student services are readily available and delivered on time.	Operating hours of student services are continent for students.
Administration staff is efficient and supportive.	Pearson Correlation	1	.628	.510
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
Student services are readily available and delivered on time.	Pearson Correlation	.628	1	.628
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
Operating hours of student services are continent for students.	Pearson Correlation	.510	.628	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	

a. Listwise N=53

Student Experience

Correlations

		Best Interest	Rewards	Enjoyment	Involvement	Uniqueness	Intellectually Challenged
Best Interest	Pearson Correlation	1	.855	.741	.694	.652	.600
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Rewards	Pearson Correlation	.855	1	.663	.765	.700	.638
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
Enjoyment	Pearson Correlation	.741	.663	1	.780	.756	.636
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
Involvement	Pearson Correlation	.694	.765	.780	1	.816	.769
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
Uniqueness	Pearson Correlation	.652	.700	.756	.816	1	.733
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
Intellectually Challenged	Pearson Correlation	.600	.638	.636	.769	.733	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

a. Listwise N=50

Student Satisfaction

Correlations

		The first impression of the HEI met your expectations.	The HEI is meeting your expectations of a higher education learning.	The HEI is meeting your overall expectations.
The first impression of the HEI met your expectations.	Pearson Correlation	1	.747	.669
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
The HEI is meeting your expectations of a higher education learning.	Pearson Correlation	.747	1	.885
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
The HEI is meeting your overall expectations.	Pearson Correlation	.669	.885	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	

a. Listwise N=53

Personal Development

Correlations

		Integrity	Analyse Information	General Knowledge	Industry Skills	Communication Skills	Problem Solving
Integrity	Pearson Correlation	1	.659	.766	.727	.753	.632
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Analyse Information	Pearson Correlation	.659	1	.827	.578	.650	.675
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
General Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	.766	.827	1	.678	.655	.594
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
Industry Skills	Pearson Correlation	.727	.578	.678	1	.807	.799
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
Communication Skills	Pearson Correlation	.753	.650	.655	.807	1	.831
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
Problem Solving	Pearson Correlation	.632	.675	.594	.799	.831	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

a. Listwise N=53

Appendix 9: Table 5.1: Presenting Course Titles Of The Respondents

What is your course title?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agricultural	1	1.9	1.9	1.9
	BA	1	1.9	1.9	3.8
	BACHELOR OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION	1	1.9	1.9	5.7
	Bachelor of Science in Nursing	1	1.9	1.9	7.5
	BBA	2	3.8	3.8	11.3
	BDS	1	1.9	1.9	13.2
	BECE	1	1.9	1.9	15.1
	Biosciences	1	1.9	1.9	17.0
	Bs economics	1	1.9	1.9	18.9
	BS Mathematics 4 years program	1	1.9	1.9	20.8
	bsds bachelors data science	1	1.9	1.9	22.6
	BSN	1	1.9	1.9	24.5
	BSSE	1	1.9	1.9	26.4
	Civil Engineering	1	1.9	1.9	28.3
	Dpt	1	1.9	1.9	30.2
	Economics	1	1.9	1.9	32.1
	EE	1	1.9	1.9	34.0
	Electrical Engineering	1	1.9	1.9	35.8

English language and literature	1	1.9	1.9	37.7
f business-to-business e-commerce adoption and its impact on SMEs competitive advantage	1	1.9	1.9	39.6
Finance	2	3.8	3.8	43.4
HR	1	1.9	1.9	45.3
ICAEW	1	1.9	1.9	47.2
Impact of Information Technology on SMEs	1	1.9	1.9	49.1
Information security	1	1.9	1.9	50.9
M.Phil HRM	1	1.9	1.9	52.8
MA English	1	1.9	1.9	54.7
Management Philosophy	1	1.9	1.9	56.6
Management sciences	2	3.8	3.8	60.4
Master in English linguistics and literature	1	1.9	1.9	62.3
Math	1	1.9	1.9	64.2
Mba	1	1.9	1.9	66.0
MBA	2	3.8	3.8	69.8
MBA Finance	1	1.9	1.9	71.7
Mba Hr	1	1.9	1.9	73.6
MBA Marketing	1	1.9	1.9	75.5
Media Literacy	1	1.9	1.9	77.4
MS	1	1.9	1.9	79.2
MS Information security	1	1.9	1.9	81.1
MS ISLAMIC BANKING	1	1.9	1.9	83.0

Msc Economic	1	1.9	1.9	84.9
Msc economics	1	1.9	1.9	86.8
Msc mass communication in media	2	3.8	3.8	90.6
Phd	1	1.9	1.9	92.5
Signals and systems	1	1.9	1.9	94.3
Software	1	1.9	1.9	96.2
Software engineering	1	1.9	1.9	98.1
Tourism and hospitality management	1	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Appendix 10: Table 5.2: Presenting HEIs Of The Respondents

Name of the institute

			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	"Allama Iqbal Open University		1	1.9	1.9	1.9
	"Comsats University		1	1.9	1.9	3.8
	Abasyn University Islamabad		1	1.9	1.9	5.7
	Abasyn university Islamabad campus		1	1.9	1.9	7.5
	Abasyn University Islamabad Campus		1	1.9	1.9	9.4
	Agricultural university Peshawar		1	1.9	1.9	11.3

Air university	1	1.9	1.9	13.2
Bahria uni	1	1.9	1.9	15.1
Comsats	3	5.7	5.7	20.8
COMSATS	2	3.8	3.8	24.5
Comsats Islamabad	1	1.9	1.9	26.4
Comsats University Islamabad	1	1.9	1.9	28.3
CUI	1	1.9	1.9	30.2
CUST	1	1.9	1.9	32.1
FUUASTISB	1	1.9	1.9	34.0
ICAEW	1	1.9	1.9	35.8
Iqra University	1	1.9	1.9	37.7
MIHS	1	1.9	1.9	39.6
N/A	1	1.9	1.9	41.5
North Western polytechnic university Xian china	1	1.9	1.9	43.4
NUML	6	11.3	11.3	54.7
NUS	1	1.9	1.9	56.6
NUST	2	3.8	3.8	60.4
PMAS-ARID AGRICULTURE UNIVERSITY RAWALPINDI	1	1.9	1.9	62.3
Preston	1	1.9	1.9	64.2
Preston University	3	5.7	5.7	69.8
Preston university Islamabad	1	1.9	1.9	71.7
Preston University Islamabad	1	1.9	1.9	73.6
Punjab Uni	1	1.9	1.9	75.5
Qcet	1	1.9	1.9	77.4

Qmul	1	1.9	1.9	79.2
RIPHAH	1	1.9	1.9	81.1
Riphah International university Islamabad	1	1.9	1.9	83.0
Rise	1	1.9	1.9	84.9
RISE (Riphah International University Islamabad)	1	1.9	1.9	86.8
RIUI	1	1.9	1.9	88.7
SWUFE	1	1.9	1.9	90.6
The university of Lahore	1	1.9	1.9	92.5
University of Bedfordshire	1	1.9	1.9	94.3
University of Lahore	1	1.9	1.9	96.2
University of Lahore - Pakistan	1	1.9	1.9	98.1
UOB	1	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total	53	100.0	100.0	